

URHOBO TONE SYSTEM

BY

ROSELINE ORIORO AZIZA (MRS.) (Nee Olomukoro)
B.A. (Hons) English (Ife), M.A. Linguistics (Ibadan)

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DEDICATION

Dedicated to:

God Almighty, who is ever so faithful,

Moses, my husband,

Oghenetega

Oghenerukeywe

Onoriode

)
)
)

my children

who had to bear so much.

ABSTRACT

The primary aim of this study is to describe aspects of the phonology of Urhobo with particular reference to its tone system. This is the first indepth linguistic description of this language within a theoretical framework of phonological representation. The Urhobo language is widely spoken in Delta State, Nigeria.

Ten of the twenty dialects of the language have been extensively studied and data include the Ibadan 400-Wordlist, 300 randomly selected additional words from the language, 200 varied syntactic patterns and five short stories. Twelve of the thirteen informants engaged in the data collection reside in villages in which the language is in active use. Instrumental investigation was conducted using a tone box and a Computerised Speech Laboratory which gave instrumental tracings of selected tokens.

The theoretical framework used for analysing the data is the autosegmental model of generative phonology which is one of the recent models of phonology designed to cater for non-segmental phenomena such as tone.

The results from this work provide further evidence for the claim by autosegmental phonologists that phenomena such as vowel harmony, nasality and tone belong to separate tiers which are independent of the segments that bear them in the phonetic realisation. More importantly, the work shows that both downstep and downdrift exist in Urhobo and the position that non-automatic downstep is derivable from lost or floating low tones cannot be sustained in all languages. Rather, a case is made for the recognition, in underlying representation, of a phonemic downstep level, along with the more basic high and low tones.

The study would help the teaching and learning of the language in formal institutions of learning as well as streamline the writing system so as to help future writers in the language.

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CERTIFICATION

I certify that this work was carried out by R. O. Aziza (Mrs.) in the Department of Linguistics and African Languages, University of Ibadan.

(Supervisor)

Ben Ohi Elugbe

B.A., Ph.D (Ibadan)

Professor in the Department of

Linguistics and African

Languages, University of

Ibadan, Nigeria.

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ABBREVIATIONS AND NOTATIONS

The following abbreviations and notations have been used in this work:

[^ˀ]	=	H = /	=	The high tone
[_ˀ]	=	L = \	=	The Low tone
[⁻]	=	DS = = !/	=	The downstep
(H)	=	Ḥ	=	Floating high tone
(L)	=	Ḷ	=	Floating low tone
TS	=			Tonal segmentalisation
QM	=			Question tomorph
NM	=			Negative tomorph
ATM	=			Associative tone marker
RTM	=			Reduplication tone marker
OTM	=			Object tone marker
FTM	=			Future tone marker
⋮	=			Establish a link between two slots
	=			Linked elements
⊥	=			Delinked elements
∅	=			Empty slot
V	=			Vowel slot
v	=			Vowel segment
ṽ	=			Nasal/Nasalised vowel segment

C	=	Consonant slot
c	=	Consonant segment
VE	=	Vowel elision
GF	=	Glide formation
AM	=	Associative marker
RM	=	Reduplication marker
σ	=	Syllable node
μ	=	Morpheme node

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" 2	:	ɛ̀sɛ̀ d̄ɔ̄ kàāā	'Ese did not buy maize'
" 3	:	ɛ̀sɛ̀ d̄ɔ̄ kà ?	'Did Ese buy maize?'
" 4	:	ɔ̄ d̄ɔ̄ n̄ɛ̀	'he bought yam'
" 5	:	éwũ r̄ajè	'a woman's dress'
" 6a	:	ɔ̄ s̄ɛ̄soma	'a cricket from Oma'
" 6b	:	s̄ɔ̄kpa	'about a cock'
" 7	:	ɔ̄obɔ̄	'a hand'
" 8	:	ɔ̄okɔ̄	'a boat, canoe'
" 9	:	áɡóɡó 'metal gong';	odibò 'a slave, servant'
" 10	:	usínǎ	'the fame'
" 11	:	ɔ̄bò nǎ d̄ɔ̄t̄ nǎ	'the doctor bought the (parcel of) land'
" 12	:	ɔ̄ocɛ̄ramè	'a water pot'
" 13	:	ɔ̄ob̄ɔ̄rá ĩmǎ rov̄jè r̄ajè	'tail-end of a queen's wrapper'
" 14	:	ɔ̄ d̄ɔ̄kà nǎ	'he bought the maize'
" 15	:	úrè r̄ɔ̄bò nǎ ɔ̄ɔ̄ɔ̄ɔ̄	'the doctor's tree has honey'
" 16	:	íɣ̄ò r̄urè r̄ɔ̄ḡɔ̄ r̄ajè	'money for the wood of the woman's in-law'

- " 17 : ɔ̌ ḡɔ̄ mē̄ d̄ur̄ē n̄à 'my in-law bought the wood'
- " 18 : ɔ̌ ḡɔ̄ n̄à d̄ot̄ɔ̄ r̄ɔ̄ɔ̄ n̄à 'my in-law drank the dregs
of the honey'
- " 19 : ɔ̌ɔ̄ n̄à s̄ɔ̄ s̄ɛ̄ mē̄ ʊ̄ot̄ɔ̄ r̄ɔ̄ḡɔ̄ n̄à 'the bee stung my
father on the in-law's land'

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 URHOBO SPEAKERS

The 1992 census puts the population of Nigeria at 88.5 million and that of Delta State at 2.5 million ("Nigerian Tribune," March 20, 1992). As the largest ethnic group in Delta State, we can project that the present population of Urhobo speakers is about one million. In addition, Otite (1982) has reported that Urhobo is classified among the first ten major ethnic groups in Nigeria. The people are today to be found in the Southern part of Delta State. The Urhobo people speak Urhobo, a language with various dialects in twelve of the twenty-five Local Government Areas of the State.

According to tradition, the Urhobo nation is made up of twenty-two clans, namely, Agbarha, Agbarha-Ame, Agbarho, Agbon, Arhavwarien, Avwraka, Eghwu, Ephron-Oto, Ewreni, Idjerhe, Oghara, Ogo, Okparabe, Okere, Okpe, Olomu, Orogun, Udu, Ughelli, Ughievwen, Ughwerun, and Uvwie. Although linguistic studies have shown that Okpe and Uvwie speak languages that are significantly different from the general Urhobo, the majority of the people in the twenty-two clans listed above regard themselves politically and culturally as one people. Each of the twenty clans, apart from Okpe and Uvwie, speaks its own dialect of Urhobo, although there is a high level of mutual intelligibility among them. In Okpe and Uvwie areas, the central Agbarho dialect is commonly used both among themselves and with other Urhobo speakers.

The Agbarho dialect is also the accepted standard variety of Urhobo used for both oral and written communication and for teaching purposes. At present, the language is taught at the primary, secondary and tertiary levels of education in Delta State. Agbarho clan is a community of fourteen villages located somewhere in the centre between the former Western and Eastern Urhobo Divisions. The clan headquarters is Orho-Agbarho, a town located half-way between Effurun and Ughelli on the Effurun-Patani road. The immediate neighbours of Agbarho are Okpe to the north, Ughievwen to the south, Ughelli to the east and Uvwię (Effurun) to the west.

The entire Urhobo nation is surrounded by the Işekiri to the west, Isoko to the south-east, Izon to the south, Ukwuani to the east and Edo to the north.

1.2 REVIEW OF PREVIOUS STUDIES ON URHOBO

1.2.1 LINGUISTIC CLASSIFICATION

Studies on Urhobo were quite scanty until very recently and most of them had to do with the linguistic classification of the language. Elugbe (1989a) traces these linguistic classifications by various linguists. They include: Koelle (1854) who classifies it as one of the five languages that make up the Niger-Delta Group B which he lists under 'VB' with the other members of the group as Bini, Ihewe, Egbele and Oloma; Cust (1883) and Thomas (1910) follow this classification; Westermann (1927) goes a bit further and classifies the Edo Group, to which Urhobo belongs, under Kwa languages Group (g); Talbot (1932), Greenberg (1955, 1963), Wolff (1959) Wescott (1962), Armstrong

(1964), Hoffmann (1973), Elugbe (1973, 1978), Bennett and Sterk (1977) as well as all the linguists who have worked on this language since then have all followed this classification of Urhobo as an Edoid language. The term 'Edoid' for the former Edo group of languages was coined by Elugbe (1978). Elugbe identifies Urhobo as a member of the south western branch of the Edoid family of languages (Elugbe 1989a:7). Williamson (1989) has reclassified the Edoid languages under the 'new' Benue-Congo, itself a sub-branch of the Niger-Congo languages. Fig. 1 is the linguistic classification of Urhobo in relation to other Edoid and 'new' Benue-Congo languages.

1.2.2 EARLIER STUDIES

Apart from linguistic classification, reports of research work on various aspects of the language are available although not very extensive. These will be further highlighted as they concern our work in the appropriate sections but for now we shall outline some main points in the major works on the language.

Kelly (1969a) is a preliminary study of the phonology of the language in which he describes the consonants, vowels, syllable structure and the tone and intonation patterns. His study is based on the Agbon dialect, the closest dialect to Agbarho.

Kelly (1969b) discusses vowel patterning in the noun and concludes that vowel harmony has broken down in the noun, so much so that it can no longer be spoken of. He claims that the phenomenon can only be applied to the verb phrase.

Welmers (1969, 1973), also working on the Agbon dialect, presents a ~~sketchy~~ outline of the phonemes of the language but discussions on its tone patterns and grammatical patterns are a lot more elaborate. Welmers (1969) says that Urhobo has two tones, high and low, and a downstep but that the phenomenon of 'terracing' or 'downstep' within a phrase is not found in that a nonlow tone lower than an immediately preceding nonlow is heard only in utterance final position (that is, before a pause).

Welmers (1973) analyses Urhobo as a language with three level tones: high, low and mid (the mid tone occurs only clause finally and only after a high tone, elsewhere it is low). He also says that there is no appreciable downdrift in the system.

Till date, Elugbe has done the largest amount of work on various aspects of Urhobo phonology along with the phonology of other Edoid languages. Elugbe (1973, 1977, 1983, 1989a and 1991) all contain discussions on Urhobo from the sound system, through the tone system to the orthographic representation of Urhobo sounds. His studies are based on the central Agbarho dialect.

Elugbe's (1973) analysis of the Urhobo tone system is similar in several respects to Welmers (1969).

Elugbe (1977) recognises a mid tone instead of a downstep for the language because, as he claims, after downstep it is possible to go back to high within the same tone phrase and because this is not a possibility normally permitted in a system with two tones and a downstep, it becomes natural to recognise the third level as a mid tone. In

addition, he identifies the presence of the phenomenon of final low tone raising in the language. By this he means that low tones in both the citation forms of nouns and in utterance final position are realised on a slightly higher level than low tones elsewhere.

Elugbe (1989a) concludes his analysis of the Urhobo tone system with these four 'uncontroverted' facts, namely:

- i) there is no downdrift;
- ii) there is downstep;
- iii) after low, there is no contrast between high and downstep; yet,
- iv) after downstep, it is possible to go back to high within the same tone phrase.

Apart from these, there are a few unpublished articles and projects here and there on aspects of Urhobo phonology and tone system.

One point that needs to be mentioned here is that till date, no major work that zeros in on analysing Urhobo on its own has been done. Apart from a few articles and research projects, most of the work done so far are part of a general treatise on the Edoid languages. Thus, data investigated in such works are usually limited in number and in the depth of treatment.

TABLE 1 CLASSIFICATION OF (NEW) BENUE - CONGO AND THE EDOID LANGUAGE FAMILY TREE (ADAPTED FROM WILLIAMSON (1989) AND ELUGBE (1989b))

(NEW) BENUE - CONGO

CHAPTER TWO

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 INTRODUCTION

The theoretical framework that we intend to follow in this study is the autosegmental model of phonetic (and consequently phonological) representation which arose out of a need for a more proper representation of the phonetic as well as the phonological content in language. The reason for our choice of the autosegmental framework is fairly obvious. Apart from the fact that it is one of the recent phonological models, it is also the one designed in the first place to handle problems created by such phenomena as tone which turned out to be problematic for the standard (linear) theory. We shall, in this work, present fresh evidence from Urhobo in support of the autosegmental model of phonological representations.

2.2 AUTOSEGMENTAL PHONOLOGY

The most fundamental characteristic of the autosegmental theory is that phonological representation is non-linear, that is, that a phonological representation is composed, not of a single sequence of entities but of several parallel sequences of entities arranged in two or more tiers, each of which is said to be independent of the others.

Within standard generative phonology, a phonological representation is conceived as a linear arrangement of segments and boundaries. Each segment consists of an

unordered set of features, with a feature specification, while the boundaries, interspersed between the segments, partition the string of segments into substrings that constitute domains for phonological generalisations (van der Hulst and Smith, 1982). In the SPE model of generative phonology (Chomsky and Halle, 1968), phonological representations are assumed to consist of segmental and suprasegmental representations. The segmental representations consist of consonant and vowel segments together with empty segments referred to as syllable, morpheme, word and phrase boundaries. The boundaries indicate the domain in which a particular phonological process takes place. In other words, phonological representations are linearly ordered with segments, some of which bear suprasegmental properties, for example, tone, arranged in a neat sequence but the relationship between the segmental and suprasegmental levels is not given any serious consideration within the theory.

However, the standard theory has been found to be inadequate in handling a number of phenomena such as tone and later, nasality, vowel harmony, etc. In fact, the motivating factors that gave rise to autosegmental phonology are outlined below:

- (i) the inability of the standard generative phonology to account for contour tones borne by single vowels and for complex segments like affricates and pre-nasalised and post-nasalised segments. The SPE could not effectively account for the fact that a single vowel could have two different tonal specifications in a sequence to indicate a rising or a falling contour tone. Autosegmental phonology is able to account for such phenomena

because it does not require that there should be an equal number of segments on each tier since each tier is independent of the other. It is thus possible within this model for a tone-bearing unit to be linked to two or more tones. A rising and a falling contour tone would be encoded as in 1(a) and 1(b) respectively:

1(a) Rising tone

1(b) Falling tone

The linear ordering on the tonal tier shows explicitly that in 1(a) a low tone precedes a high tone and by associating both tones with a single vowel segment, we indicate that the vowel is produced with a rising tone. In the same way, the vowel in 1(b) is produced with a falling tone. Similarly, affricates and pre-nasalised stops are adequately represented as in 2(a) and (b) respectively below:

2(a) Affricates (e.g. [ts]) (b) prenasalised stops (e.g. [mb])

ii) A second motivation for autosegmental theory is the inability of standard generative phonology to account for the stability of tone features as a result of its adoption of a linear representation. Within this theory, tone is considered as a feature of the vowel segment bearing it. This being the case, it is expected that when the vowel segment gets elided or becomes nonsyllabic and so loses its ability to bear tone as a result of some phonological processes, all the features of the vowel segment, including the tone, should be elided with it. However, it has become obvious that not all the features said to characterise some property of a segment are synchronised by the same temporal function. We frequently have situations in tone languages where a vowel is elided or becomes nonsyllabic but its tone survives and surfaces on an adjacent segment. Therefore Leben (1973: 135) asks; "why should one type of segmental feature be able to 'float' when no other segmental feature appears to have this property?" and demands an explanation for why this entity (tone) is capable of behaviour different from that of other segmental features. Evidence abounds in Urhobo to support this issue of the stability of tones.

In the Noun+Noun associative construction, for example, the vowel of the associative marker /rɛ/ bears a high tone. The vowel of this marker is usually elided but its high tone remains and manifests itself on the vowel prefix of the following noun. If this vowel prefix bears a high tone, no change in tone occurs, but if it bears a low tone, what we get is not a HL glide or a downstep but rather the high tone of the associative marker (AM) causes the following low tone borne by the prefix vowel of the second noun

to delink so that it is now realised on a high tone in surface structure. Let us illustrate with an example:

3(a) (i) Underlying Representation

ii) by Vowel Elision

iii) by Relinking of (H)

iv) by delinking of L

v) by deletion of delinked low tone (L → ∅)

(b) (i) Underlying Representation

ii) by vowel elision

iii) by Relinking of (H) (applies vacuously)

Notice that vowel elision causes the tone that was borne by the elided vowel segment to become automatically floating. Moreover, in constructions such as the ones above, and in fact in most constructions in Urhobo, the relinking of a floating high tone causes a following low tone to automatically delink. Consequently, unless otherwise stated, in subsequent examples, we shall collapse the two stages indicated in (iii) and (iv) of example 3(a) into one.

Another example comes from the Verb plus Noun construction in Urhobo. The final vowel of the verb stem is usually elided but its tone remains and manifests on the prefix vowel of the following noun. The examples below illustrate our point.

4(a)(i)	<table style="margin: auto;"> <tr><td style="text-align: center;">L</td><td></td><td style="text-align: center;">H</td><td></td><td style="text-align: center;">L</td><td style="text-align: center;">L</td></tr> <tr><td style="text-align: center;"> </td><td></td><td style="text-align: center;"> </td><td></td><td style="text-align: center;"> </td><td style="text-align: center;"> </td></tr> <tr><td style="text-align: center;">V</td><td style="text-align: center;">+</td><td style="text-align: center;">C</td><td style="text-align: center;">V</td><td style="text-align: center;">+</td><td style="text-align: center;">V C V</td></tr> <tr><td style="text-align: center;"> </td><td></td><td style="text-align: center;"> </td><td style="text-align: center;"> </td><td></td><td style="text-align: center;"> </td></tr> <tr><td style="text-align: center;">ɔ</td><td></td><td style="text-align: center;">d</td><td style="text-align: center;">ɛ</td><td></td><td style="text-align: center;">ɔ b e</td></tr> </table>	L		H		L	L							V	+	C	V	+	V C V							ɔ		d	ɛ		ɔ b e	Underlying Representation
L		H		L	L																											
V	+	C	V	+	V C V																											
ɔ		d	ɛ		ɔ b e																											

3rd pers

sing bought book

b)(i)

Underlying Representation

3rd pers. sing cooked soup

ii)

by Glide formation

iii)

by vowel elision

iv)

by (H) relinking and L delinking

v)

by deletion of floating tone..

[ò cèrò'yo'wó]

'he/she cooked soup'

(c)(i)

Underlying Representation

3rd pers.

sing wrote name

[^ˈo s^ˈjod^ˈɛ]

'he/she wrote name'

From the examples above, it is obvious that tone shows a kind of 'stability' which cannot be accounted for if it is assumed to be an integral part of the segment on which it appears in a phonetic representation. This lends credence to the autosegmental position that tones are themselves autosegments, independent in their own right.

iii) A third motivation for the autosegmental theory is the issue of 'floating' tones and toneless morphemes. Schachter and Fromkin (1968) using the standard theory represent a floating low tone in Akan with the matrix [-segment, +L] with no other segmental specifications and Leben (1973) criticizes this proposal as clearly ad hoc since no other segmental feature has been shown to be capable of this sort of representation. The autosegmental model predicts the existence of morphemes, lacking either the tone tier or the segmental tier since tone and segmental properties are encoded independently in the phonological representation. Morphemes lacking the tonal tier are regarded as 'toneless morphemes' while those lacking the segmental tier are referred to as 'floating' tones. In Urhobo, floating tones play a significant role in the phonetic representation of a number of grammatical configurations. Grammatical floating tones function as grammatical formatives and have been referred to as 'tomorphs', that is, tonal morphemes, by Elugbe (1985). In this language, most tense and aspectual information is signaled by tonal alternations. Moreover, questions are marked by a final (floating) low tone while

negation is marked by a final (floating) LH sequence. For now, let us consider the examples in 5(a) and (b) below:-

iii)

iv)

(v)

[ɔ dónɛ] 'did he/she buy yam?

5(b)(i)

[ɔ d ɔ n ɛ̃ ɛ̃ ɛ̃]

'he/she did not buy yam'

From the examples presented above, it is obvious that a number of floating tones get segmentalised on tone bearers. In fact, the segmentalisation of tomorphs is obligatory since they are specified in the grammar of the language. The segmentalisation of floating tones sometimes results in short vowels bearing contour tones as in 5a while it may result in the lengthening of the final vowel in order to accommodate excess tones as 5b shows. There are no significantly long vowels in this language. Moreover, all contour tones

found in Urhobo are a combination of the two basic tones High and Low, and an underlying sequence of non-identical tones can surface on the same tone bearing unit.

iv) Another issue which autosegmental theory accounts for easily because it is predicted in the framework is that of melody levels. Goldsmith (1976: 35) defines melody levels as 'significant levels in the grammar which refer to just one or two features in the utterance' and he illustrates with different tonal melodies which correspond to different tenses in the Tiv verbal system.

Urhobo verbal system also has melody levels which are significant in the grammar and are independent of the segments with which they are coarticulated in the phonetic representation. These melody levels are assigned to particular tenses. A particular verbal construction has its own melody which can simply be hummed without words or consonant and vowel segments and yet make sense. This is why verbs as well as monosyllabic pronouns in Urhobo have been analysed by linguists like Elugbe (1989a) as being underlyingly toneless and receive tone depending on the grammatical construction in which they appear. Members of these categories of items with the same syllable structure will surface with the same tone pattern(s) in similar grammatical constructions. In the citation form, they are all realised with the low tone but from tense to tense there is a corresponding tone pattern(s) which they bear. The tone patterns accompanying

monosyllabic subject pronouns and the verb stems in the three basic tenses in the language are summarised in 6 below:

6.	Tense	Subject Pronoun	Verb Stem	
			Monosyllabic	Disyllabic
a)	General Past	L	H	L H
b)	General Present	LH	L	L L
c)	Future	HL	H	H H

Consider the following examples

7.	a.	(i.)	sà	'shoot'
		(ii.)	kparè	'lift (up)'
	b.	(i.)	ᵛ sà-ré	'he shot (something)'
		(ii.)	ᵛ kparé-ré	'he lifted (something)'
	c.	(i.)	ᵛᵛ sà	'he is shooting'
		(ii.)	ᵛᵛ kparà	'he is lifting (something)'
	d.	(i.)	ᵛ cà sá	'he will shoot'
		(ii.)	ᵛ cà kparé	'he will lift (something)'

(v) Finally, the issue of bi-directional spreading in language which also posed a problem of analysis for the standard theory is resolved within the autosegmental framework. This is because the autosegmental theory recognises that there are natural languages in which spreading is bi-directional rather than simply unidirectional. Vowel

harmony in Urhobo is an example of a phenomenon that can spread both to the left and to the right and since vowel harmony is regarded not as a feature on the vowel but as an autosegment, bi-directional spreading is easily accounted for within this framework. In this language, the monosyllabic pronouns and the affixes accompanying verb stems usually occur in two phonological shapes. The particular shape that occurs in the surface form is determined by the [ATR] vowel harmony requirements of the verb stem vowel. If the verb stem vowel is [+ATR] it will select shapes that are phonologically different from those that a [-ATR] verb stem vowel will select to fill these positions. Thus, the [ATR] autosegment in Urhobo spreads both to the right and to the left of the verb stem vowel. We shall discuss details in the next chapter when we deal with **Vowel Harmony in Urhobo**; for now, the following are a few examples

8.	Verb stem	[ATR] status	Examples
a)	sì 'write'	[+ATR]	ò sí-rì 'he wrote'
b)	sè 'call'	[+ATR]	ò sé-rì 'he called'
c)	cò 'steal'	[+ATR]	ò có-rì 'he stole'
d)	sà 'shoot'	[-ATR]	ò sá-rè 'he shot'
e)	ʃɛ̀ 'sell'	[-ATR]	ò ʃé-rè 'he sold'
f)	kĩ́ 'plant'	[-ATR]	ò kĩ́-rè 'he planted'

Having discussed the motivations for the autosegmental framework, we now proceed to discuss the model itself.

Autosegmental phonology dates back to Leben (1971, 1973) and Williams (1971). In fact, Leben (1973) proposed a model of representation which later developed into what is today autosegmental phonology. His proposal is that given a lexical entry in a tonal language, there should be two separate sequences of feature matrices; the first represents a sequence of segments while the second represents a sequence of suprasegments (such as tone and nasality). In his proposal, a given tone has the same status with respect to a suprasegmental sequence as a given segment has with respect to a segmental sequence. The theory predicts, therefore, that where a language has inherently toneless morphemes, such morphemes are specified underlyingly with only sequences of segmental feature matrices, while 'floating' tones are specified with only the sequence of suprasegmental feature matrices. The phonetic matrix is to be derived by a set of mapping rules after the phonological, segmental and suprasegmental rules have been applied. However, only a single tiered representation is created in the surface structure at the end of the derivation.

Autosegmental phonology is, however, credited to Goldsmith (1976a) where it was first formalised. He claims that it is an attempt to supply a more adequate understanding of the phonetic side of the linguistic representation. He criticises the standard theory as being characterised by what he calls the 'absolute slicing principle' in which a phonological representation starts by being split up into neat 'slices' or segments, each linearly ordered and designed as having no ordered sub-parts. Goldsmith (1976a)

claims that autosegmental phonology is a proposal at the same logical level as the SPE idea that a phonological representation is a linear sequence of atomic units or segments and also that these segments are cross-classified by distinctive features. However, it differs from SPE by proposing that a phonetic representation comprises not a single tier but several parallel tiers of phonological segments; that is, the phonetic representation is split up into parallel sequences of segments each of which is represented on an independent tier or level. Elements of each tier are called autosegments and are sequentially ordered. Portions of the bundle of distinctive features earlier assigned to segments are extracted and arrayed on independent tiers and constitute segments in their own right and each of these independent tiers has autosegments which are related to the segmental tier by a set of conventions that preserve well-formedness throughout the course of phonological derivations. In other words, segments on different tiers are linked to each other by formal entities known as association lines which indicate how they are to be co-articulated. Elements of adjacent tiers are simultaneous if and only if they are linked by association lines. In addition, phonological rules may insert or delete elements of any tier and since each tier is independent, deletion of an element on one tier does not entail deletion of the element to which it is linked on another tier; however, at every stage, the output of such processes are subjected to conventions governing well-formedness. Thus, phonological rules have the new function of creating and modifying the patterns of association among elements of different tiers. In this model, all tiers

remain independent throughout derivations; at no time or point is, for example, the tonal tier merged with the segmental tier.

2.3 ASSOCIATION PRINCIPLES

Given a model of phonological representation which is **multitiered**, a natural question is to ask how the elements on the different tiers are synchronised or co-ordinated since ultimately the various tiers are actualised in a single acoustic signal. To be precise, how are the elements on the various tiers co-ordinated in order to obtain a well-formed phonological representation?

Leben (1973) proposes a Mapping Rule such that phonological representations are **multitiered** before the mapping but single-tiered (that is, linear) after the mapping. According to him, underlying tones are represented on a separate tier from the feature matrices representing vowel and consonant segments; they are subsequently merged with these matrices by Tone Mapping Rules that applied in the course of derivations but these create single-tiered representations in surface structure. From his mapping rule, it is therefore possible to distinguish two types of rules in terms of the ordering relation with the mapping rule, namely, rules that apply before the mapping and rules that apply after the mapping. However, since tones are merged with segments after mapping, the model did not adequately account for short vowels that bear contour tones.

To handle the situation, Goldsmith (1976) gives a different interpretation of the mapping relation and proposes that phonological representations are **multitiered at all**

levels. The result of the mapping operation is that we indicate how segments on different tiers are co-articulated and this is done formally by inserting association lines on different tiers. Goldsmith (1979) explains that association lines are not present in the underlying representation; they only serve to indicate the timing of units in an utterance and also reflect the relationship between the different autosegmental tiers. Since one segment follows another in an utterance, this sequence has to be reflected in λ^a representation.

Although all autosegmental phonologists are in general agreement that phonological representations are multitiered at all levels, there are divergent views on how the association of tiers or links between entities on different tiers are to be established or regulated. In other words, there are different approaches on the principles that govern the well-formedness of multitiered representations. Two main approaches are considered here.

The first approach is that put forward by Goldsmith (1976) in what is known as the well-formedness condition (WFC) as reproduced in 9 below:

9. Well-Formedness Condition (WFC)
 1. All vowels are associated with at least one tone;
 2. All tones are associated with at least one vowel;
 3. Association lines do not cross.

Goldsmith explains that the WFC functions to add or delete association lines in order to maximally meet its specification and obtain a well formed representation.

Goldsmith's WFC has been criticised as being both too weak and too strong. As pointed out by Clements and Ford (1979), it is too weak as an instruction to draw association lines because in some cases, there are several ways of satisfying it. For example, given 10a, we can have 10b, 10c or 10d as possibilities.

In addition, there is the problem of what to do with surplus tones or surplus tone bearing units. According to the WFC, the remaining tones should be (re) linked with the last tone bearer (cf Clause 1), or the remaining tone bearers should be linked with the last tone (cf Clause 2). Here, the WFC is considered to be too strong because the assignment^{ment} of two tones to one tone bearer cannot be a universal principle since there are languages that do not permit tone clustering on short vowels. Furthermore, Clause 2 as it stands leads to indeterminacy because an unassociated tone bearer which has a tone both to its right and to its left can have two options - to go to the right or to go to the left.

In order to handle these and other problems arising from WFC, Clements and Ford (1979) and Clements and Goldsmith (1984) have appended three additional principles as supplementary to the WFC. These are:

11. (i) associate free tones to free tone - bearing units in a one-to-one fashion going from left to right;

- (ii) the association of free (unassociated) segments takes precedence over that of already linked (associated) segments; furthermore, (a) give precedence to segments linked to unassociated elements, if there are any; (b) give precedence to segments on the left;
- (iii) add the minimal number of association lines required to undo the violation of the WFC.

However, while Clements and Ford (1979) agree with Goldsmith that a single tone can spread onto excess tone bearing units, the association conventions they propose are similar in several respects to the second approach outlined below. For example, they propose that the assignment of more than one tone to a tone bearing unit should not be automatic but should be created only by language specific rules.

The second approach on the principles that govern the well-formedness of multitered representations is that first suggested by Williams (1971) and developed by Clements and Ford (1979), Halle and Vergnaud (1982) and Pulleyblank (1986). In this model, tone linking is accompanied by a similar left-to-right rule but there is no recourse to the WFC in order to produce the correct output. Halle and Vergnaud (1982:67) outline Williams (1971) Tone Mapping Rule as in 12 below:

- 12(i) Map from left to right a sequence of tones onto a sequence of syllables;

- (ii) assign one tone per syllable, until it runs out of tones;
- (iii) assign the last tone that was specified to the remaining untuned syllables on the right, ...
- (iv) until you encounter the next syllable to the right belonging to a morpheme with specified tone.

Although this rule resembles Goldsmith's by accepting that the last tone is mapped or linked to several tone bearing units when the number of bearers exceeds the number of tones, the mapping of several tones to a single tone bearing unit cannot be a universal principle. Instead, this is determined by language specific rules. The position is made more explicit by Halle and Vergnaud (1982) with the additional provision:

- (v) If the procedure above runs out of vowels (syllabic elements or syllables), more than one tone may be assigned to the last vowel only if the grammar of the language includes a stipulation to that effect.

This means that the association of more than one tone with a single tone bearer is a marked phenomenon that requires an extra language specific rule if it occurs but if such a rule is absent from the grammar, only one tone per tone bearer will be permitted. It also means, as Clements and Ford (1979) have also argued, that any tone that remains unassociated after the left-to-right rule has applied or a tone that becomes dissociated when its original bearer is deleted or becomes non-syllabic should not be (re) - associated

as a matter of convention. When nothing is said in the grammar of the language, such unassociated tones remain unassociated and do not receive phonetic interpretation. Pulleyblank (1986a) suggests a further modification and argues that both the multiple $\overset{k}{\underset{\wedge}{\text{linings}}}$ of tones to a single bearer and the multiple $\overset{k}{\underset{\wedge}{\text{linings}}}$ of a single tone to more than one bearer should occur only as a result of language specific rules. He therefore proposes that the universal aspect of the Tone Mapping Rule is as stated in 13 below:

13. Association Conventions

Map a sequence of tones onto a sequence of tone-bearing units.

- (a) from left to right,
- (b) in a one-to-one relation.

while the universal aspect of WFC is as in 14:

14. Well-formedness Condition

Association lines do not cross

He explains that Halle and Vergnaud's (1982) proposal that Association Conventions apply only to floating tones follows automatically from his proposal in 13 above. Since tones are linked to tone-bearing units only in a strict one-to-one relation, a linked tone cannot be subject to further linking by convention.

To exemplify the position that tone clustering should be determined only by language specific rules and not by universal conventions let us consider the following

examples in Isoko (as reported by Donwa, 1982) and Urhobo, two closely related Edoid languages. First, we present the Isoko examples:

15. Underlying Representation (UR)	Phonetic Representation (PR)
a) /sì úfì/ ----->	[s j ǔ f ì] / [s j ú f ì]
L H L	L H L H L
pull rope	'pull a rope'
b) /dù íbì/ ----->	[d w ǐ b ì] / [d w í b ì]
L H L	L H L H L
pound seeds	'pound seeds'

In the first syllable of the phonetic forms, we can have two possibilities. The first is a LH contour tone which is the result of the juxtaposition of the low tone of the verb and the high tone of the noun prefix. Although the vowel of the verb stem has become a glide, its tone survives and is manifested on the vowel of the noun prefix. The second (phonetic) possibility, which is a logical step from the first, is that the LH contour undergoes a simplification to H. On the other hand, a similar situation in Urhobo is obligatorily simplified to H. Thus, we would have:

16.	UR	PR
(a)	/dɛ́ ɔ́k à/ ----->	[dɔ́kà]
	L H L	H L
	buy maize	'buy maize'
(a)	/kò éwũ / ----->	[kéwũ]
	L H L	H L
	sew dress	'sew a dress'

Language specific rules can reveal why similar inputs account for different outputs even in closely related languages.

Until recently, the third condition of Goldsmith's WFC "Association lines do not cross" had been accepted as the only universal aspect by most linguists who have worked with the autosegmental model.

Urua (1990) has however challenged this position and suggested that it should also be considered a language - specific requirement. Describing Ibibio morphology within the autosegmental framework, she contends that for a ~~correct~~ derivation of the surface forms of partial reversive reduplication in the language, association lines must cross. She illustrates her position with the verb /dép/ 'buy' which by -CV suffixation yields [dép-pé] 'not buying (Negative)'. The derivation is as follows: (Urua 1990: 23-24).

An alternative derivation is as follows:

If association lines are not allowed to cross the derivation would yield the following wrong output.

(These examples are Urua's examples 20, 21 and 19 respectively).

Elugbe (personal communication) has pointed out to me that Akinlabi and some other linguists have recently presented Urua's examples in a different way in which the association lines do not cross. As I have not been able to lay my hands on the article to read it, I cannot make comments on it. However, to my knowledge, the condition that association lines do not cross remains valid in the treatment of tone and in this work, they do not cross.

2.4 WHEN THE CONVENTIONS APPLY

Another issue that has been given attention relating to Association Conventions is when the conventions apply. Pulleyblank (1986a) outlines two approaches. The first, which is also the more dominant one in the literature, is that the conventions apply whenever possible throughout the derivation. This means, for example, that a rule of

vowel or tone deletion will automatically be followed by a reapplication of the Association Conventions so that, given a derivation such as 20a where a rule of vowel deletion applies to V_1 as in 20b, this theory will automatically derive 20c

The second approach which is held by Pulleyblank (1986a) is to assume that the Association Conventions apply only at the beginning of a derivation but not automatically elsewhere. Therefore, given the derivation in 20a above, this theory would leave the output of 20a unaffected as in 20b unless a relinking rule applies to yield 20c. This means that the ^klinings even of floating tones to free tone bearers would not be automatic; they would come about solely by stipulation if the relevant configuration has been derived by a rule.

The two approaches have been found to have quite different results in a number of cases and Pulleyblank suggests that the choice between the two alternatives should depend on empirical consideration.

However, evidence from Urhobo supports Pulleyblank's claim that relinking of delinked tones is not automatic. When a tone is set afloat as a result of a phonological process such as vowel elision or glide formation, relinking may or may not occur. Let us consider the following examples:

Underlying Representation (UR)

3rd Pers

sing. bought yam

by vowel elision

by (H) relinking and

L delinking

Surface representation (SR)

[ɔ̃ dɔ̃nɛ̃] 'he/she bought yam'

Underlying representation

by glide formation

(iii)

by $\textcircled{L}$ deletion

[sjewū] 'pull a dress'

c)(i)

Underlying representation

maize two

(ii)

by vowel elision

by Ⓛ relinking

Surface representation

[éki^ˈvε̃] 'two maize'

The examples above show that it is necessary for relinking to occur by rule in Urhobo otherwise we may derive the following wrong sequences *[ɔ̃d̃ɔ̃ñɛ̃], *[sjéw̃ũ] for 21(a) and (b) respectively. In 21(a) the delinked high tone relinks and results in automatic delinking of the following low tone whereas in 21(b) the delinked low tone does not relink. It is important to note that any tone that is not linked to a vowel segment in this language does not get a phonetic realisation in surface structure. In example 21(c) above, the delinked low tone relinks and results in a LH contour on the following vowel.

Our position therefore is to uphold the view that tone assignment rules should be language specific wherever necessary. As our examples 15 and 16 above also show,

different languages have different rules for assigning tones to tone bears^{er} while some tones may even remain unassigned.

2.5 LINKING OF TIERS

Autosegmental theory was originally devised to handle tonal phenomena but it has been extended to handle other phenomena such as vowel harmony (Clements 1976, Chumbo~~w~~ 1982), syllable structure (Clements 1976, Clements and Keyser 1983) and nasality (Hyman 1982). This leads to the question of the number of autosegmental tiers a particular language may have. This is entirely language specific.

Since in autosegmental phonology there *may be* several tiers in a phonological representation, the question arises as to which tiers a given tier can be linked to. For instance can a tone tier be linked directly to a segmental tier?

Goldsmith (1976, 1979) and Clements and Ford (1979) propose that autosegments are linked directly to the phonemic tier, that is, to the consonant and vowel segments that bear them. This proposal has however been criticised for not being able to show the actual independence of the tiers since the autosegments are shown to be properties of the units bearing them after the application of the association conventions.

The dominant view is that expressed by Halle and Vergnaud (1982), Clements and Keyser (1983) and Pulleyblank (1983, 1986a) that autosegments are indirectly linked via a structural CV skeleton which has a different status from the autosegmental tiers. The CV skeleton consists of C and V elements to which autosegments are linked and from

which they are linked to bearing units. The CV skeleton determines the timing relation of the autosegmental tiers and so sustains their independence. The major advantage of having a CV skeleton is that it enables a clear representation of different processes in language simultaneously as we have shown in a number of our derivations given above. It constitutes a separate autosegmental tier and forms the core of the representation and it is around it that vowels and consonants are articulated. Clements and Keyser (1983) propose that the skeleton is part of the universal phonological representation and serves multiple roles. These include:

- (i) forming the basis of syllabification rules which require that V elements on the skeletal tier dominate syllable peaks (vowels and syllabic consonants);
- (ii) forming the basis of phonological quantity such that long segments are represented as single phonemes which are linked to two units of the CV tier (long segments count as one unit from the point of view of their segmental quality but as two from the point of view of quantity) whereas complex segments such as affricates and prenasalised stops are represented as two phonemes linked to a single C slot on the CV tier (that is, they are two units from the point of view of their feature substance but as one from that of segmental quantity);
- iii) compensatory lengthening by which deletion of one segment is accompanied by the lengthening of another (usually adjacent) one is expressed as the spreading of a neighbouring phoneme onto the skeletal position left vacant by the deleted one.

Pulleyblank (1983, 1986a) in fact suggests the following constraint:

22. Autosegmental tiers can only link to slots in the skeletal tier.

Goldsmith (1990:53) re-echoes this constraint in what he refers to as the linkage condition reproduced in 23 below:

23. Linkage Condition

A segment will not be phonetically realised if it is not linked to a position in the skeletal tier.

Thus, the skeletal tier is an integral part of the phonological representation. Pulleyblank has argued that allowing autosegmental tiers, rather than the skeletal tier, to link to each other creates unfortunate configurations that can easily be avoided. He argues further that although the constraint in 22 produces a more restrictive multitiered theory, it helps to avoid situations where association lines are likely to cross. In addition, it allows tiers to radiate out from a central skeletal tier. It should be noted that only syllabic elements, and these usually occupy the V slot, can be mapped for tones.

Another issue that arises from an analysis in which autosegments are indirectly linked via a structural skeletal tier concerns the existence of a phonemic core. The question is asked

whether or not a feature can be represented simultaneously on both the phonemic tier and on an autosegmental tier. Halle and Vergnaud (1982) propose the possibility of representing a feature both

autosegmentally and on the phonemic core as a compromise position between Leben and William's model of Tone Mapping Rules and Goldsmith's WFC. They suggest that the autosegmental value takes precedence over the core value so that, for example, the core tonal value of a vowel will only surface if there is no tonal autosegment linked to it.

Pulleyblank (1986a) proposes that no special status should be assigned to a phonemic core because redundant tonal specifications are simply tonal autosegments supplied when a skeletal slot has not received any specification for tone. This means that all tonal specifications should be on a single tier since there is no formal difference in terms of tiers between segmental features and autosegmental features. Segmental behaviour results when each slot is linked to an autosegment prior to rule application while autosegmental behaviour results when rules create multiple $\overset{k}{\text{linings}}$ or when $\underset{\Delta}{\text{linings}}$ are incomplete prior to the application of rules or conventions. He argues that this proposal is borne out of a theory in which a CV-skeleton functions to co-ordinate the various tiers.

However, the CV-skeletal slot has been slightly modified in recent literature with the introduction of 'X' slots in favour of C - and V - slots to which autosegments may be linked indirectly. The 'X' slots are unspecified for syllabicity and so have the advantage of avoiding the sometimes clumsy and cumbersome explanation of how sometimes vowel features may spread to occupy the position of consonant slots or vice versa. Pulleyblank (1986b) employs the 'X' approach in his discussion of vowel harmony in Okpe. In

languages which have compensatory lengthening, the advantage of the 'X' approach is clearly illustrated. The following examples are taken from Urua (1990 : 158) which show that when certain CVC verb radicals are pluralised, the final C in the radical or verb root is deleted and in its place the preceding vowel is lengthened to occupy the position of the deleted consonant. The examples below are Urua's example 108

24. I (Sing. lexical forms)	II (CVC radicals/ roots devoid of -V & -CV suffixes)	III (Plural lexical forms)
i) dép 'buy'	dép -	dée-mé 'buy many things'
ii) kòkó 'remove object from mouth'	kòk -	kòò-ŋò 'remove objects from the mouth'
iii) sítte 'remove stopper'	sít -	síi-ŋé 'remove stoppers'

She explains that the final C of the CVC verb root is deleted leaving an empty slot which is then filled by spreading the root vowel. In such an analysis, the 'X' slot has the advantage of preventing the problem of accounting for how a vowel segment spreads onto a slot previously occupied by a consonant.

In Urhobo, a similar situation exists with the phenomenon of nasality and it provides further evidence for our adopting the CV-skeleton. Let us examine the forms in 25 and 26 below.

25. I Verb stem	II Past tense
a) sì 'write', 'pull'	sí-rì 'wrote', 'pulled'
b) cò 'steal'	có-rì 'stole'
c) sà 'shoot'	sá-rè 'shot'
d) kpɔ̃ 'be dry'	kpɔ́-rè 'dried up'

26. I	II
a) kǐ 'search round'	kǐ-rì 'searched round'
b) sě 'refuse'	sě-rě 'refused'
c) dǎvě 'taste'	dǎvě-rě 'tasted'
d) kɔ̃ 'plant'	kɔ́-rě 'planted'

The forms in I are the verb stems while those in II are the past tense forms. To derive the forms in II, a-CV suffix is added to the verb stem. This -CV suffix has the underlying form /rV/ which appears in two phonological shapes depending on whether the verb stem vowel is a nasal or an oral vowel.

If the verb stem vowel bears the feature [+ Nasal], the -CV suffix (both the consonant and the vowel segments) would appear with [+ Nasal] and if the verb stem vowel bears the feature [-Nasal], the -CV suffix would appear with [-Nasal]. This is the situation in 26 and 25 respectively. It means therefore that the feature of nasality spreads onto the -CV suffix. Using the CV-skeleton this can be derived as in 27 and 28 below:

27. (i)

[- Nasal]

shoot

Underlying representation

ii)

[- Nasal]

by suffixation

iii)

[sá rɛ̀]

Surface representation

Underlying representation

Surface Representation

iv) [+ Nasal]

[sẽrẽ] 'refused'

An alternative analysis is to use the 'X' - skeleton and derive the forms as in 29

and 30 below respectively:

29.(I) [- Nasal]

Underlying representation

ii) [- Nasal]

by suffixation

iii) [- Nasal]

by [Nasal] autosegmental spreading

iv) X X X X

Surface Representation

[s a r e] 'shot'

30 (i) [+ Nasal]

Underlying representation

(ii) [+ Nasal]

by suffixation

iii) [+ Nasal]

by [Nasal] autosegmental spreading

iv) [+ Nasal]

Surface representation

[s [˘]e [˘]r [˘]e] 'refused'

Although the 'X' - skeleton has its advantages, we intend in this work to use the CV-skeleton. This is because a CV-skeleton would enable people unfamiliar with the language to identify more easily whether we are dealing with a C or a V element. Urhobo has evidence to show that phenomena such as nasality, tone, and vowel harmony (notice that the vowels of the suffix in 25 and 26 appear in different shapes depending on the [ATR] vowel harmony requirements of the verb stem vowel) are autosegments on different tiers and the vowel slot bears a lot of load in the analyses of these various phenomena. The CV-skeleton would afford us an opportunity to present a clearer picture of a number of processes in Urhobo.

CHAPTER THREE

AN OVERVIEW OF URHOBO PHONOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

In this chapter, we present an outline of aspects of Urhobo phonology. We consider this discussion relevant to our work because there are a number of factors which affect sound segments as well as syllables and these in turn have implications for tones and tone patterns.

3.2 SEGMENTAL PHONOLOGY

This section deals with the segmental phonology, that is, with the consonant and vowel segments found in the language. While we highlight some previous analyses of these segments by notable linguists wherever necessary, our description would be based mainly on an auditory perception of the sound segments as perceived by this presenter.

We note here that there are two types of phonation that are linguistically significant in Urhobo; these are, the voiced and the voiceless. Whereas all vowels, nasals, and approximants are voiced, obstruents are either voiced or voiceless. Moreover, with the exception of the labial velar plosives /kp/ and /gb/ which are said on a combination of airstreams, namely, an ingressive velaric airstream and an egressive pulmonic airstream, all Urhobo speech sounds, are said on the pulmonic egressive airstream. For the labial-velar plosives, the implosion at the lips and the explosion at the velum are perceptually and articulatorily discernible.

3.2.1 CONSONANT SEGMENTS

To make our work easier and our discussion clearer, we shall, before going into full discussions, present three charts of Urhobo consonant segments as presented in the literature by Kelly (1969a), Welmers (1969) and Elugbe (1989a).

Table 2:

Kelly's Consonant Chart for Urhobo (Kelly 1969a:154)

	Bilabial	Labio dental	Alveolar	Palato alveolar	Palatal	Velar	Labial-Velar
Plosive	p b		t d		c ʃ	k g	kp gb
Fricative	ɸ β	f v	s z	ʃ ʒ		x ɣ	xm ɣw
Nasal	m		n		ɲ		ɲm
Trill/Tap			ɾ				
Flap			r				
Approximant					j		w

TABLE 3

Welmer's Consonant Chart (Welmers 1969:86)

Bilabial	Labiodental	Alveolar	Pre-Palatal	Velar	Labial-Velar
-	-	t	ty	k	kp
b	-	d	dy	g	gb
f	f	s	sy	h	-
v	v	z	zy	ɣ	-
w	-	r	ry	y	-
m	-	n	ny	-	ɲm

TABLE 4

Elugbe's Consonant Chart (Elugbe 1989a:71)

	m			n	ny						
p	b			t	d	c	ɟ	k	g	kp	gb
ɸ		f	v	r		'		h	ɣ		
				s	z	ʃ	ʒ				
					l						
					ɭ						
			ɥ				y				w

The three charts above reflect the differences in the number of consonant phonemes proposed for Urhobo. Kelly's chart has thirty consonant segments, Welmers' has twenty-seven while Elugbe's has twenty-eight. In the following sections, we discuss the groups of consonants beginning with the plosives.

3.2.1.1 PLOSIVES

Both Kelly and Elugbe each identify ten plosive segments for Urhobo namely /p, b, t, d, c, ɟ, k, g, kp, gb/, whereas Welmers identifies only nine; he does not include the voiceless bilabial plosive /p/ in his list of phonemes. However, there is evidence to show that the sound exists as a phoneme in the language, although we should quickly point out that the words bearing it are quite few. Let us consider the following examples:

- 31 (a) $\acute{u}p\bar{e}$ 'scar' (c) $p\grave{a}n\grave{e}$ 'peel lightly'
 (b) $\acute{u}b\bar{i}$ 'seed' (d) $b\grave{a}n\grave{e}$ 'sprinkle'

The examples in 31 above show clearly that there is a phonemic contrast between /p/ and /b/ in Urhobo and there does not appear to be any apparent reason not to recognise it as a phoneme. In this work, therefore, we follow Kelly and Elugbe and identify the ten plosive segments as phonemes in the language. Each of them is used in words as exemplified below:

/p/ voiceless bilabial plosive

/pene/--> [p $\grave{e}n\grave{e}$] 'hurry past'

/á-piápiá/--> [ápjápjá] 'a type of bird'

/b/ voiced bilabial plosive

/bene/ ---> [b $\grave{e}n\grave{e}$] 'cuddle'

/ò-bò/--> [òbò] 'hand'

/t/ voiceless alveolar plosive

/ta/ ---> [tá] 'speak, say'

/ò-tá / --> [òtá] 'word'

/d/ voiced alveolar plosive

/da/ ---> [dà] 'drink'

/ò-dà/ ---> [òdà] 'matchet, cutlass'

/c/	voiceless palatal plosive	
	/ca/ ---> [cà]	'support'
	/ò-cé / ---> [òcé]	'water pot'
/j/	voiced palatal plosive	
	/ja/ ---> [jà]	'be peppery'
	/ò-ja/ ---> [òjà]	'soap'
/k/	voiceless velar plosive	
	/ka/ --> [kà]	'stop (e.g. rain)'
	/s-ka/ ---> [s̀kà]	'maize'
/g/	voiced velar plosive	
	/ga/ --> [gà]	'serve'
	/h-ga/ --> [h̀gà]	'sickness'
/kp/	voiceless labial velar plosive	
	/kpa/ --> [kpà]	'vomit'
	/h-kpá/ ---> [h̀kpá]	'walking stick'
/gb/	voiced labial velar plosive	
	/gba/ ---> [gbà]	'tie up'
	/ò-gbá/ ---> [ògbā]	'fence'

We make the following observations:

- (a) each voiceless plosive is pronounced with a slight aspiration in syllable - initial position. This aspiration is, however, not significant;
- (b) each plosive segment in Urhobo is opaque to nasality that is, plosives are not affected by nasality when they occur in the environment of a nasal segment.

3.2.1.2 FRICATIVES

Kelly recognises twelve fricative segments for Urhobo as listed in his chart; Welmers has ten without Kelly's /xm, ɣw/ and Elugbe has nine without Kelly's /xm, ɣw, and β/. Both Welmers and Elugbe identify Kelly's /xm, ɣw/ as labialised allophones of the phonemes /h, ɣ/ respectively and we totally agree with them. Elugbe regards Kelly's voiced bilabial fricative /β/ (Welmers' /ʋ/) as a voiced labiodental approximant. In this work, we follow Elugbe and identify the sound as a voiced labiodental approximant rather than a voiced bilabial fricative because its manner of articulation is clearly in consonance with that of other approximants in the language and also because the contact between the lower lip and the upper front teeth is clearly perceptible during its production.

As for the voiceless velar fricative /x/ (Kelly 1969a) or /h/ (Welmers 1969, Elugbe 1989a) this is merely a matter of preference of a particular symbol as the descriptions of the sound by all three linguists are identical. However, because h is also the symbol used to represent the sound orthographically, we follow Welmers and Elugbe and choose to

symbolise this sound phonemically as /h/ and treat [x] as an allophone in free variation with [h].

In this work, therefore, we recognise nine fricative segments, namely / ϕ , f, v, s, z, $\int$, $\mathfrak{z}$, h, $\mathfrak{h}$ /. Each of these is used in words as exemplified below:

/ ϕ / voiceless bilabial fricative

/ ϕ o/ ---> [ϕ ò] 'jump'

/ù- ϕ ó/ ---> [ù ϕ ó] 'throat'

/f/ voiceless labiodental fricative

/fo/ ---> [f ò] 'fit (e.g. a dress)'

/ú-fí/ ---> [úfí] 'rope'

/v/ voiced labiodental fricative

/vo/ --> (vò) 'fetch (e.g. water)'

/ù-vò/ ---> [ùvò] 'sun'

/s/ voiceless alveolar fricative

/si/ --> [sì] 'write, pull'

/ù-sí/ --> [ùsí] 'starch'

/z/ voiced alveolar fricative

/ze / ---> [zè] 'appease'

/ú-zò/ ---> [úzò] 'antelope'

/ʃ/ voiceless palatal fricative

/ʃe/ ---> [ʃè] 'fall'

/èʃà/ ---> [èʃà] 'gray hair'

/ʒ/ voiced palatal fricative

/ʒẽ/ ---> [ʒẽ] 'like'

/u-ʒe/ ---> [ùʒè] 'twenty'

/ʒ/ voiced velar fricative

/ʒa/ ---> [ʒà] 'forbid'

/a-ʒá/ --> [aʒá] 'broom'

/h/ voiceless glottal fricative: it has two allophones, namely, [x] and [h]

[x] is a voiceless velar fricative

[h] is a voiceless glottal fricative. Both allophones are in free variation.

/hɔ/ ---> [hɔ̃]/[xɔ̃] 'bathe'

/ɔ'-hɔ'/ ---> [ɔ'hɔ̃]/[ɔ'xɔ̃] 'chicken'

In addition, the voiceless glottal fricative [h] can be nasalised when it immediately precedes a nasal vowel; all the other fricative segments listed above are not affected by nasality in the environment of nasal vowels. For example:

/h a ɾ ẽ/ --> [h̃ ã ɾ̃ ẽ̃] / [x̃ ã ɾ̃ ẽ̃] 'abuse'

/ò-hɔ̃r ẽ̃/ --> [òh̃ɔ̃r̃ ẽ̃] 'a fight'

3.2.1.3 NASALS

Both Kelly and Welmers identify four nasal consonants for Urhobo, namely /m, n, ɲ, ŋm/. Although in Elugbe (1989a) the labial-velar nasal /ŋm/ does not appear in his list of consonant segments, it does occur in his 1973 work and he has explained (personal communication) that its omission is a typographical error. Consequently, all the three linguists whose works we are considering recognise four nasal consonants for Urhobo, namely, /m, n, ɲ, ŋm/. In this work, we also recognise the four nasal consonants. Each of them, except /n/ has one allophone; /n/ has two, namely, [n] and [l] and the two of them are sometimes in free variation.

Elugbe (1973, 1989a) and a few other preliminary studies on Urhobo consonant segments have recognised /l/ as the underlying form while [n] is treated as an allophone of /l/: the [n] variant is found before a nasal vowel while [l] is found in an oral environment. In this work, we choose to regard the underlying form of the sound as /n/ and treat [l] as a variant which sometimes occurs in free variation with [n]. We advance the following reasons for our stand:

(a) Although in a number of items [l] and [n] occur as allophones in free variation, the [n] variant occurs more frequently than [l]. The following are some examples:

32. (a) /ɲ n é/ ---> [ɲ nɛ́] ~ [ɲlɛ́]

'yam'

(b) /ùnè/ ---> [ùnɛ̀] [ùlɛ̀]

'song'

(c) /ónán/ ---> [ónán̄] [ólál̄] 'grinding stone'

(b) Whereas [n] can be found where [l] also occurs, there are a number of items which permit only [n] but not [l] and there was never a case in my entire data in which only [l] was permitted. For example.

33 (a) /óní/ --> [óní̄] not *[ólí] 'mother'

(b) /ùnù/ ---> [ùnù̄] not *[ùlù] 'mouth'

We, therefore, propose that /n/ may sometimes lose its nasal quality in the speech patterns of certain speakers and when this happens, it is realised as [l] as the examples in 32 above show.

c) More importantly, when loan words enter into Urhobo, all cases of [l] in the original word are realised as either [n] or [r]. [l] is only heard in the speech patterns of the educated Urhobo who make a conscious effort to overcome the [l] ~ [n] alternation that Urhobo speakers are noted for. The following are some examples:

34. (a) look ---> [nuk]
 (b) Lagos ---> [negosu]
 (c) table ---> [iteboro]
 (d) school ---> [isikuru]

If [l] was the underlying form, it should be stable enough to be retained even in these words. For the reasons outlined above, we submit that there are four nasal consonant

segments in Urhobo namely /m, n, ɲ, ŋm/ and that the alveolar lateral [l] is not found in underlying representation.

It is also interesting to note that a distinction is made in this language between the palatal nasal /ɲ/ and the nasalised palatal approximant [ɲ̃]. The two sounds contrast in the following words.

- 35 (a) /oǰǎ/ → [oǰǎ] 'a walk'
 (b) /ɲá/ → [ɲ̃á] 'a prawn'
 (c) /ɲo/ → [ɲ̃o] 'hear'
 (d) /jã/ → [j̃ã] 'walk'

Each of the nasals is used in words as exemplified below:

/m/ voiced bilabial nasal

/mɔ/ → [m̃ɔ] 'come'

/ù - m̃i/ → [ùm̃i] 'local filter'

/n/ voiced alveolar nasal: it has two allophones, namely [l] and [n].

[l] is the voiced alveolar lateral, and

[n] is the voiced alveolar nasal.

Both allophones are sometimes in free variation but the environment for the free variation cannot be predicted.

/nɔ/ → [ñɔ] 'ask'

/ù-ñé/ → [ùñé] / [ùlé] 'song'

/ɲ/ voiced palatal nasal

/ɲo/ ---> [ɲõ]

‘hear’

/ɲ-pa/ ----> [ɲpã]

‘prawn’

/ɲm/ voiced labial velar nasal

/ɲma / ---> [ɲmã]

‘extract (e.g. oil from palm fruit)’.

/à-ɲmá/ ----> [à ɲ mǎ]

‘cloth’

3.2.1.4

THE RHOTICS

Urhobo has two rhotics:

/r/ is a voiceless alveolar trill. It is opaque to nasalisation, that is, it is not receptive to nasality when it occurs in a nasal environment.

/rã / ----> [rã]

‘untie, fly’

/u-ré/ ----> [uré]

‘wood, tree’

/ɾ/ is a voiced alveolar tap. It has two allophones:

[ɲ] is a tapped alveolar nasal which occurs in a nasal environment

/mɾa/ ----> [m ɲ ǎ]

‘be loud (of sound)’

/o-ɾi/ ---> [o ɲ i]

‘puss’

[ɾ] is a voiced alveolar tap found elsewhere.

/ɾe/ ----> [ɾe]

‘eat’

/è-ɾé/ ----> [èɾé]

‘mat’

For ease of presentation and typing, the voiced alveolar tap would be indicated everywhere in this work with the orthographic symbol r while the tapped alveolar nasal would be represented as $\tilde{r}$

3.2.1.5 APPROXIMANTS

These are sounds produced with an open approximation of the vocal organs and have no audible friction. We recognise three approximants for Urhobo, namely /v, j, w/ and each of them may be nasalised in the environment of a nasal vowel. Consequently, each of them has two allophonic variants as indicated below.

[$\tilde{v}$, $\tilde{j}$, $\tilde{w}$] before nasal vowels

[v, j, w] before oral vowels.

Each approximant is used in words as exemplified below:-

/v/ voiced labiodental approximant

/vo/ ---> [$v\grave{o}$] 'have'

/u^h-v^ho/ ---> [$u\tilde{v}\tilde{o}$] 'flesh'

/j/ voiced palatal approximant

/ja/ ---> [$j\grave{a}$] 'catch'

/u^h-j^hε/ ---> [$u\tilde{j}\tilde{\epsilon}$] 'a fly'

/w/ voiced labial-velar approximant

/wã/ ---> [$w\tilde{ã}$] 'pass (by)'

/o^h-w^he/ ---> [$o\tilde{w}\tilde{e}$] 'bush mango'

In Table 5

below we provide a maximally specified feature matrix for distinguishing Urhobo consonant segments.

TABLE 5: MAXIMALLY SPECIFIED DISTINCTIVE FEATURE MATRIX FOR URHOB CONSONANT SEGMENTS.

	p	b	t	d	c	ɟ	k	g	kp	gb	m	n	ɲ	ɲ ^m	ɸ	f	v	s	z	ʃ	ʒ	h	ɣ	ŋ	r	ɔ	j	w
CONSONANTAL	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-
SYLLABIC	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
SONORANT	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
CONTINUANT	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
ANTERIOR	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	-
CORONAL	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-
LABIAL	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	+
NASAL	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
HIGH	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+
BACK	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	+
VOICE	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	+	-	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+
GRAVE	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	-	+

3.2.2 VOWEL SEGMENTS

All the linguists who have studied Urhobo sounds have claimed that there are seven oral vowels, namely, /i, e, ε, a, ɔ, o, u/. They have all also recognised that each of these vowel segments can be both significantly and phonetically nasalised.

Our observation of the behaviour of the vowel segments in this language shows that although the seven oral vowels (and seven nasal/nasalised vowels) listed above exist at the phonetic level, we need to recognise nine oral (and nine nasal) vowels at the phonological level. (The seven phonetic vowels are also those used for writing the language). This is because the vowels e and o each patterns in two phonologically different ways when it occurs in a sequence.

Let us consider some examples briefly for now.

36. i) `ozé 'basin' ~ `izé 'basins'
 ii) `eɽu 'cap' ~ `iɽu 'caps'
 but
 iii) `otá 'word' ~ `etá 'words'
 iv) `erakṍ 'dog' ~ `erakṍ 'dogs'
37. i) se 'read, call ---> `esé 'to read, call'
 ii) do 'throw' ---> `edó 'to throw'

but

- iii) re 'eat' ~ `εrɪ́[è rjɔ́] 'to eat'
 iv) so 'sing' ~ `εsuɔ́[è swɔ́] 'to sing'

The examples in 36 and 37 above show clearly that e and o pattern differently in grammatical sequences.

Elugbe (1973, 1989a) has claimed that Urhobo, like some other Edoid languages, has a seven-vowel system which has been reduced from a ten-vowel system postulated for Proto-Edoid (PE). The ten vowels of PE fall into two harmony sets in their patterning behaviour, namely, (cf Elugbe 1989a:118):

38. Expanded Pharynx [+EXP]		Non-expanded Pharynx [-EXP]	
i	u	I	ɔ
e	o	ε	ɔ
	ɔ		a

Only Degema, a Delta Edoid (DE) language is known to have contrasts involving all ten vowels; generally, most Edoid languages have reduced the original system in one of three ways, namely (Elugbe 1989a:119).

39. (a) in the nine-vowel systems, there is no /ɔ/;
 (b) in the eight-vowel systems, there are no /ɔ, I/
 (c) in the seven-vowel systems, there are no /ɔ, I, ɔ/.

Urhobo provides evidence of the last possibility. In a seven-vowel system such as Urhobo has, PE*/ɔ/ is said to have merged with /ɛ/, */ɪ/ with /e/ and */ɔ/ with /o/. Thus, sometimes e and o occur as the original e and o, that is, the low vowels in the Expanded Set while at other times they are reflexes of *I and *ɔ, that is, the high vowels in the Non-expanded set respectively. Evidence that this is the case is further strengthened by the following examples:

40. a) úkɛ́ 'egg' ~ íkɛ́ 'eggs'
 b) útiɛ́ [úʔjɛ́] 'orange' ~ itiɛ́ [ítʔjɛ́] 'oranges'
 c) ̀sò 'hawk' ~ ̀esò ~ 'hawks'
 d) ̀odè 'name' ~ ̀edè ~ 'names'

In 40 a and b, we have a non-expanded vowel in the stem where an expanded vowel is expected, evidence of the merging of PE *ɔ with ɛ. In 40c and d, PE *ɔ merged with o in the stem and prefix positions respectively, in addition to the fact that the typical plural prefix of the non-expanded set *I has also merged with e. Thus, we have an original ten vowel system which has been reduced to seven with serious implications for the behaviour of vowels in the language. Although vowel reduction appears to be complete on the surface, the vowels still retain their original features at the phonological level and this is responsible for the differences in their patterning when they occur in grammatical sequences.

Elugbe (1989a) has also claimed that even in languages in which the vowels /ɔ, ɪ, ʊ/ occur, they are forbidden in the prefix position and this leads him to infer that it may be one of the ways in which vowel reduction may be initiated.

Donwa-Ifode (1989), discussing vowel reduction in the Edoid languages, makes a similar claim and postulates that when these languages reduce their vowels, the first one to go is /ɔ/, followed by /ɪ/ and lastly, by /ʊ/. (There are no Edoid languages with less than seven vowels). This may be why it is still possible to occasionally hear [ʊ] in the rendering of certain Urhobo words:

41. [ɔ̃ ṽ ʊ̃] 'one' }
 } as reported by Elugbe (1973)
- [ɔ̃ s̃ ʊ̃] 'hawk' }
 }
- [s̃ ʊ̃] 'sing' }
 } as recorded from an Agbon
- [ɔ̃ ṽ ʊ̃] 'one' } informant in the present work.

For the reasons stated above, we shall recognise seven vowels at the phonetic level but nine at the phonological level and following Elugbe (1991) we shall differentiate them with the lowered indices. The vowels are to be found in Table 6 below:

Table 6: Urhobo Vowel Segments

Phonetic/Orthographic	Phonological
i	/i/
e	/e ₁ /
	/e ₂ /
ε	/ε/
a	/a/
ɔ	/ɔ/
o	/o ₁ /
	/o ₂ /
u	/u/

/e₂/ and /o₂/ are high vowels along with /i/ and /u/ while /e₁/ and /o₁/ are non-high vowels.

Each of the nine phonological vowel segments may co-occur with the specification [+Nasal]; in other words, each of them may be inherently nasalised, that is, marked in underlying representation with the [Nasal] autosegment, or it may be phonetically nasalised, that is, have the [Nasal] autosegment spread to it from a preceding [+Nasal] consonant segment. Generally, we follow Amayo (1976) and use the term 'nasal vowels' to refer to those vowels that are significantly nasalised while we use the

term 'nasalised vowels' to refer to those vowels that become nasalised as a result of being in a nasal environment.

At the underlying level, Urhobo oral vowels would be indicated as follows:

/i, e₁, e₂, ε, a, ɔ, o₁, o₂, u/.

The nasal/nasalised vowels are indicated as follows:

ĩ, ě₁, ě₂, ě, ã, õ, õ₁, õ₂, ũ.

The morphemes below demonstrate the oral/nasal vowel contrasts in this language.

42. Oral Vowels /V/

/i/ : /ò-rí/ ---> [òrí] 'pomade'

/e₁/ : /se₁/ ---> [sè] 'call, read'

/e₂/ : /re₂/ ---> [rè] 'eat'

/ε/ : /sε/ ---> [sɛ] 'be efficacious'

/a/ : /ɣare₂/ ---> [ɣàrè] 'divide share out'

/ɔ/ : /gɔ/ ---> [gɔ̃] 'worship'

/o₁/ : /fo₁/ ---> [fò] 'fit'

/o₂/ : /so₂/ ---> [sò] 'sing'

/u/ : /ku/ ---> [kù] 'pour'

43. Nasal Vowels /Ṽ/

/ĩ/ : /ò-ĩ/ ---> [òĩ̃] 'puss'

/ě₁/ : /zě₁/ ---> [zě̃] 'like'

- /ē₂/ : /sē₂/ ----> [sē̃] 'refuse'
 /ē̃/ : /kpē̃/ ----> [kpē̃] 'peel'
 /ā/ : /ɣarē₂/ ----> [ɣarē̃] 'be expensive'
 /ɔ/ : /vɔ̃/ ----> [vɔ̃] 'be full'
 /o₁/ : /jō₁ no₁/ ----> [jōnō̃] 'learn'
 /o₂/ : /fō₂/ ----> [fō̃] 'be clean'
 /ū/ : /vū/ ----> [vū̃] 'uproot'

Nasalised vowels are exemplified in 44 below:

44. Nasalised vowels [ṽ]

- /è₂rákō̃₂/ ----> [ẽrákō̃] 'dog'
 /ũwè₁ṽ/ ----> [ũwè̃ṽ] 'house'
 /àɣmá/ ----> [ãɣmá] 'cloth'
 /óní/ ----> [óní̃] 'mother'

A distributional restriction exists on vowel segments that are marked [+ Nasal] in the underlying representation: they do not occur as prefix vowels.

In addition, Elugbe's (1973) claim that the vowel segments that are inherently [+ Nasal] are lower in terms of tongue height than their [- Nasal] counterparts is confirmed by this writer.

A point worth noting here, although we shall deal with it more fully under Vowel Sequences, is that [+ High] vowels, namely, /i, u, e₂, o₂/ (as well as their nasal

counterparts) may each be realised as non-syllabic glides - /i/ and /e₂/ may each be realised as the palatal approximant [j] while /u/ and /o₂/ may each surface as the labial-velar approximant [w] when they occur as the first vowel in a sequence within or across morpheme boundaries.

Consider the following examples:

45. /i/ : /òvìè/ ---> [òvjè] 'king'
 /fì + íyó/ ---> [fj íyó] 'throw money'
 /u/ : /ùbue₁/ ---> 'ubwè 'dust'
 : /ku + ame₂/ ---> [kwamè] 'pour water'
 /è₂/ : /sè₂ + òtá/ ---> [sjòtá] 'refute a word'
 /o₂/ : /sò₂ + ùnè₁/ ---> [swunè] 'sing a song'

Notice that only /i/ and /u/ occur as the first member of a vowel sequence within morpheme boundaries, /e₂/ and /o₂/ are not found; and this may be evidence of a further merging of /e₂/ and /o₂/ with /i/ and /u/ respectively in this position. We shall examine how vowels pattern again under Vowel Sequences and Vowel Harmony.

In Table 7 below, we provide a maximally specified matrix for Urhobo vowel segments.

TABLE 7: MAXIMALLY SPECIFIED MATRIX FOR URHOBOW VOWEL

PHONEMES

	i	e ₁	e ₂	ɛ	a	ɔ	o ₁	o ₂	u
High	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	+
Back	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
Low	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
Round	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+
ATR	+	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	+

Phonological processes which affect vowel segments and which are of interest to us are: vowel elision, glide formation, vowel lengthening, vowel harmony and nasality in vowels and each of these will be discussed later in this chapter.

3.3 VOWEL SEQUENCES

Vowel sequences are highly attested within stems and across morpheme and word boundaries in this language. The morphology of Urhobo is such that nouns as well as qualifiers (adjectives, quantifiers, demonstratives and possessive pronouns) begin with a prefix of some sort and end with a vowel. The prefixes attached to nouns and qualifiers function as concord markers which express number concord with their head nouns. Verbs, adverbs as well as auxiliaries begin with consonants but also end with vowels. Thus, all Urhobo lexical items end with vowels while quite a number of them also begin with vowels. This means that whenever two lexical items are in sequence, they almost always make vowels available at their boundaries. There are also a number of lexical items which have sequences of vowels in their stems. At morpheme boundaries, there are

no restrictions as to the type of vowels that may occur in a particular position, either before the boundary or after the boundary. The following are a few examples:

46. (a) fí + íǵó₁

throw money

(b) kù + ùdí

pour a drink

(c) sè₁ + ǵgbá

call hero

(d) kǵrǵ + emámǵ

pluck fruit

(e) kò₁ + àǵmá

sew cloth

(f) dè + ǵfètǵ₂

buy comb

(g) sà + òhúó

shoot person

However, within morpheme stems, restrictions exist as to how vowels may occur in a sequence. The first vowel in the sequence must be a [+ High] vowel; it must be either /i/ or /u/ and the second vowel must be a non-identical vowel. We shall return

to this issue when we deal with glide formation in 3.4.2. For now, the following are some examples:

47. (a) ɔ̌₁-vié̌₁ 'king'
 (b) ɔ̌₂-víé̌ 'a cry'
 (c) ɔ̌ - siá 'bush dog'
 (d) ɔ̌₁-sió₁ 'rain'
 (e) ɸǐɔ̌ 'be straight'
 (f) ǔ-búé₁ 'dust'
 (g) ɔ̌₂-vué 'message'
 (h) ú̌-suó₁ 'administration'
 (i) gǔɔ̌ň 'look for'
 (j) kúǎ 'pack, gather together'

There are no vowel sequences *ii, *iu, *ui, or *uu within morpheme stems.

The syllable structure of Urhobo prohibits vowel sequences from occurring at the phonetic level. Therefore, when vowel sequences occur in the underlying representation, they obligatorily undergo some systematic phonological processes to arrive at the acceptable phonetic realisations. The two common processes are vowel elision and glide formation.

3.4 PHONOLOGICAL PROCESSES

Three phonological processes which affect vowels will be considered in this section, these are: vowel elision, glide formation and vowel lengthening. As mentioned in the preceding section, when vowel sequences occur either within or across morpheme boundaries in the underlying representation in Urhobo, they undergo phonological processes in order to arrive at acceptable phonetic forms because vowel sequences are usually prohibited in surface structure. Two of the three phonological processes that we are considering, namely, vowel elision and glide formation, are boundary eliminating processes which turn two syllables in underlying representation into one in the phonetic realisation. This means that in a fairly long utterance, a number of vowels may be affected by either of these processes. However, adequate provision is made for the listener to facilitate his interpretation of the phonetic string. What implications do these processes have for the tone system of Urhobo? In this language, every vowel bears a tone in underlying representation. When such a vowel undergoes either of these processes, its tone is automatically set afloat and one of two things may happen to it. (i) it may remain floating and consequently receives no phonetic realisation, or (ii) it may relink with the following vowel segment. This second option leads to the creation of two other situations, namely, (a) the relinking of a floating tone may result in automatic delinking of the inherent tone borne by the vowel or (b) it may result in the creation of

contour tones. The three situations mentioned above are illustrated in the examples below. More examples will be given in the appropriate sections.

48. The floating tone does not relink and so gets deleted from the phonetic string.

a) $d\grave{e} + \acute{z}ka \rightarrow d^{\circ} \acute{z}ka \rightarrow [d\acute{z}ka]$
 buy maize (vowel elision) 'buy maize'

b) $f\ddot{u} + \acute{u}rukpe \rightarrow f\ddot{u}^{\circ} \acute{u}rukpe \rightarrow [f\ddot{u}^{\circ} \acute{u}rukpe]$
 extinguish light (glide formation) 'put out a light'

49. The floating tone relinks and causes automatic delinking of the inherent tone of the vowel.

a) $d\acute{e} + a\grave{z}ma \rightarrow d^{\circ} a\grave{z}ma \rightarrow [d^{\circ} a\grave{z}ma]$
 bought cloth (vowel elision) 'bought cloth'

b) $s\acute{u} + \grave{e}u\acute{e}_2 \rightarrow s\acute{u}^{\circ} \grave{e}u\acute{e} \rightarrow [s\acute{u}^{\circ} \grave{e}u\acute{e}]$

lead goat (glide formation) 'lead a goat'

50. The floating tone relinks and causes the creation of contour tone.

a) $\acute{e}_2ka + \acute{iv}\grave{e} \rightarrow \acute{e}k^{\circ} \acute{iv}\grave{e} \rightarrow [\acute{e}k^{\circ} \acute{iv}\grave{e}]$

maize two (vowel elision) 'two maize'

b) $\acute{ik}p\grave{u} + \acute{e}n\grave{e}_2 \rightarrow \acute{ik}p\grave{u}^{\circ} \acute{e}n\grave{e} \rightarrow [\acute{ik}p\grave{u}^{\circ} \acute{e}n\grave{e}]$

bags four (glide formation) 'four bags'

In the case of vowel lengthening, a vowel may be lengthened in order that a tomorph may be given phonetic realisation. This is what happens for example, with the negative tomorph in Urhobo.

We shall proceed now to examine each of these processes in some more detail.

3.4.1 VOWEL ELISION

Vowel elision is a common phonological process in Edoid languages. It applies in both slow deliberate speech and in normal conversational speech. It is a boundary eliminating process which fuses lexical sequences by deleting either of two vowels occurring across a morpheme boundary that existed between the two lexical sequences. Although a number of vowels may be elided from an utterance, it is done in a systematic way so that communication is usually sustained. This is an indication that vowel elision is a process that is represented in the grammar of the language. In a sequence such as $CV_1 \# V_2$, where V_1 represents the vowel before the boundary and V_2 represents the vowel after the boundary, vowel elision sometimes affects V_1 and sometimes V_2 depending on certain conditions. Let us first consider some examples.

51. V_1 Elision

- a) $d\acute{e} + \acute{u}k\acute{o} \rightarrow d\acute{u}k\acute{o} \rightarrow [d\acute{u}k\acute{o}]$
 buy cup 'buy a cup'
- b) $c\grave{e}_1r\grave{e}_1 + \grave{c}n\acute{e} \rightarrow c\grave{e}r\acute{n}\acute{e} \rightarrow [c\grave{e}r\acute{n}\acute{e}]$
 cook yam 'cook yam'

- c) $\text{ɔ́mɔ̀tɛ} + \text{ójòjò}_1\text{vɛ̀} \text{ ---} \rightarrow \text{ɔ́mɔ̀tɔ́jòjòvɛ̀} \rightarrow [\text{mɔ̀tɔ́jòjòvɛ̀}]$
 girl beautiful 'beautiful girl'
- d) `aɣmá} + \text{ɔ́fúáfò}_2 \text{ ---} \rightarrow \text{`aɣmɔ́fwafò $[\text{aɣmɔ́fwafò}]$
 cloth white 'a white cloth'
- e) $\text{íkó}_1 + \text{ívè} \text{ ---} \rightarrow \text{íkɔ́ívè} \text{ ---} \rightarrow$ $[\text{íkívè}]$
 cups two 'two cups'
- f) $\text{é}_2\text{mɔ́} + \text{é}_2\text{rã} \text{ ---} \rightarrow \text{émɔ́erã} \text{ ---} \rightarrow$ $[\text{émérã}]$
 children three 'three children'
- g) $\text{`ajè}_2 + \text{r é} + \text{ò}_1\text{viè}_1 \text{ ---} \rightarrow \text{`ajè rɔ́vjè} \text{ ---} \rightarrow$ $[\text{ajèrɔ́vjè}]$
 woman AM king 'king's wife'
- h) $\text{`evé}_2 + \text{rɛ́} + \text{ɔ́s é} \text{ ---} \rightarrow \text{`evé rɔ́sɛ̀} \text{ ---} \rightarrow$ $[\text{evé rɔ́sɛ̀}]$
 goat AM father 'father's goat'
- i) $\text{ɔ́nàná} + \text{ɔ́mɔ́tɛ̀} \text{ ---} \rightarrow \text{ɔ́nánɔ́mɔ́tɛ̀} \text{ ---} \rightarrow$ $[\text{nánɔ́mɔ́tɛ̀}]$
 this one girl 'this is a girl'
- j) $\text{ɔ́jè}_2\text{nà} + \text{ɔ́bè}_2 + \text{ɔ́mɛ̀} \text{ ---} \rightarrow \text{ɔ́jènbè mɛ̀} \text{ ---} \rightarrow$ $[\text{ɔ́jè nbè mɛ̀}]$
 that one goat mine 'that is my goat'

The examples above show that V_1 elision takes places in the following *grammatical* sequences.

52. (a) Verb + Noun (as in 51 a and b above)

(b) Noun + Adjective (as in 51 c and d)

- (c) Noun + Numeral (as in 51 e and f)
 (d) Noun + Noun Construction (as in 51 g and h)
 (e) Demonstrative + Noun Construction (as in 51 i and j).

In the next set of examples below, elision affects V_2 , not V_1 .

53. V_2 Elision

- (a) $\acute{u}k\acute{o}_1 + \grave{a}n\grave{a}n\grave{a} \rightarrow \acute{u}k\acute{o} n\grave{a}n\grave{a} \rightarrow [\acute{u}k\acute{o}n\grave{a}n\grave{a}]$
 cup this one 'this cup'
- (b) $\grave{i}m\acute{e}z\grave{e} + \grave{a}n\grave{a} \rightarrow \grave{i}m\acute{e}z\grave{e} n\grave{a} \rightarrow [\grave{i}m\acute{e}z\grave{e} n\grave{a}]$
 table the 'the table'
- (c) $\acute{e}_1 w\ddot{u} + \grave{a}m\acute{e} \rightarrow \acute{e}w\ddot{u} m\acute{e} \rightarrow [\acute{e}w\ddot{u} m\acute{e}]$
 dress mine 'my dress'
- (d) $\acute{u}k\acute{o}_1 + \grave{a}w\acute{e} \rightarrow \acute{u}k\acute{o} w\acute{e} \rightarrow [\acute{u}k\acute{o} w\acute{e}]$
 cup yours 'you cup'

The examples in 53 above show that V_2 elision takes place in the sequences:

54. (a) Noun + Demonstrative (as in 53 a and b)
 (b) Noun + Possessive pronoun (as in 53 c and d).

A close examination of 51 - 54 above indicates that the choice of the eliding vowel is determined by the morphosyntactic relations occurring between the lexical items that bear the vowels. A grammatically functional vowel, such as a noun prefix that indicates number alternations, is usually retained in preference to a grammatically

vacuous vowel such as a verb stem vowel or the prefix vowel of a demonstrative whose function is vacuous in the phonetic string. Thus, as the examples in (51) show, the final vowels of verbs, nouns, the associative marker and demonstratives are elided when they occur in such a sequence. However, the examples in (53) show that this principle is overridden depending on the morphosyntactic relations between the two lexical items juxtaposed. The redundant vowel is then elided. In (53), the demonstrative and possessive pronoun prefixes which mark concord become redundant when they occur immediately preceded by their headnoun and so they are elided. Note that in the examples in (55) below, ^{the} associative marker /rɛ / is introduced between the headnoun and the qualifier.

55. (a) úkó₁ + rɛ́ + ɔ̀jě̀₂ ---> [úkó rɔ̀jě̀]
 cup AM his 'his cup'
- (b) é₁ wṹ + rɛ́ + àvǎ̀rě̀₂ ---> [éwṹ rávǎ̀rě̀]
 dress AM ours 'our dress'
- (c) íkó₁ + rɛ́ + ɔ̀₂wǎ̀vǎ̀₃ ---> [íkó rówǎ̀vǎ̀]
 cups AM yours (pl) 'your cups'
- (e) ìmɛ́ɔ̀ + rɛ́ + ǎ̀jě̀₂ ---> [ìmɛ́ɔ̀ rájě̀]
 table AM theirs 'their table'

However, vowel elision is usually blocked when V₁ is a close vowel. In that case, V₁ obligatorily undergoes glide formation. We shall consider this in the next section.

We have chosen vowel elision to account for the process outlined above instead of assimilation and contraction (since there are no long vowels in Urhobo) for two main reasons:

- (a) There is no intermediate assimilatory stage that is acceptable as an alternative pronunciation even in slow deliberate speech.
- (b) There is no perceivable increase in length in the vowels that result after vowel elision.

This situation in Urhobo is different from Isoko (Donwa, 1982) and Emai (Egbokhare, 1990) where a number of similar sequences may be accounted for by assimilation and contraction.

3.4.2 GLIDE FORMATION

Glide formation and vowel elision are complementary processes. Glide formation may occur within a morpheme/word boundary or across a morpheme/word boundary, provided certain conditions are satisfied.

- i) Within a morpheme/word boundary, the following conditions must be met:
 - (a) The first vowel in the sequence, V_1 , must be a close vowel, front or back, while the second vowel, V_2 , must be a non-identical vowel. (Only the vowels /i/ and /u/ are permitted in such sequences).
 - (b) The vowel sequence must be preceded by a consonant, that is, the close vowel occurs between a consonant and a non-identical vowel, in the frame C - V.

The following are some examples:

- 56 (a) $\text{òvìé}_1 \implies [\text{òvǰé}]$ 'king'
 (b) $\text{èvié} \implies [\text{èvǰé}]$ 'slave, servant'
 (c) $\text{ùbùé}_1 \implies [\text{ùbǰé}]$ 'dust'
 (d) $\text{áχuá} \implies [\text{áχwá}]$ 'bush'

ii) Across a morpheme/word boundary, the following conditions apply

- (a) The vowel before the boundary, V_1 , is a [+High] vowel; that is /i, u, e₂, o₂/, while the vowel across the boundary V_2 may be any vowel in the language. In some languages, for instance Emai (Egbokhare 1990), it is obligatory that V_1 and V_2 must be non-identical vowels but in Urhobo, this restriction does not apply. In Urhobo, the only restriction in this regard is on V_1 which must be a [+High] vowel; any vowel may follow V_1 sequence as the following examples show:

57. (a) $\text{sí} + \text{úfí} \implies [\text{sjúfí}]$
 pull rope 'pull a rope'
 (b) $\text{fí} + \text{íyó}_1 \implies [\text{fjíyó}]$
 throw 'throw money'
 (c) $\text{bí} + \text{o}_2\text{kó} \implies [\text{bjókó}]$
 push canoe, boat 'paddle a boat'

- (d) $\text{̀sì} + \text{̀} \text{̀be}_2 \implies [\text{̀sɔ̀be}]$
 write book 'write a book'
- (e) $\text{̀kù} + \text{̀} \text{̀dí} \implies [\text{̀kwùdí}]$
 pour drink 'pour (a) drink'
- (f) $\text{̀mù} + \text{̀} \text{̀kpè}_1 \implies [\text{̀mwíkpè}]$
 carry beds 'carry beds'
- (g) $\text{̀kù} + \text{̀} \text{̀vri} \implies [\text{̀kwèvri}]$
 pour oil 'pour oil'
- (h) $\text{̀gù} + \text{̀} \text{̀já} \implies [\text{̀gṽjá}]$
 judge case 'judge a case'
- (i) $\text{̀fù} + \text{̀} \text{̀ame}_2 \implies [\text{̀fṽámě}]$
 stop water 'stop water (running)'
- (j) $\text{̀re}_2 + \text{̀} \text{̀ká} \implies [\text{̀rjóká}]$
 eat maize 'eat maize'
- (k) $\text{̀sě}_2 + \text{̀} \text{̀sè}_2 \implies [\text{̀sṽjése}]$
 refuse gift 'refuse a gift'
- (l) $\text{̀so}_2 + \text{̀} \text{̀unè} \implies [\text{̀swunè}]$
 sing song 'sing a song'
- (m) $\text{̀tō}_2 + \text{̀} \text{̀atō}_2 \implies [\text{̀tṽātó}]$
 chew chewing stick 'chew a chewing stick'

The examples in 57 above show that V_2 may be any vowel, not necessarily a non-identical vowel with V_1 . Thus, there is a slight difference between what occurs in an across morpheme/word boundary sequence and what occurs in a within-morpheme/word-boundary sequence. Whereas in the latter, V_2 is required to be a non-identical vowel with V_1 , no such requirement is necessary across morpheme/word boundaries. However, that V_1 must be a [+High] vowel is an obligatory part of the rule.

(b) A second condition is that the word bearing the [+High] vowel, that is the word bearing V_1 , is required to have the minimal structure of its lexical category. The minimal structure for nouns and nominals is disyllabic while that for verbs is monosyllabic.

Let us compare the following examples:

- 58 (a) $m\grave{u} + \grave{i}r\acute{i}b\acute{o}$ $\implies$ $[m\grave{w}i\acute{r}i\acute{b}\acute{o}]$
 carry pepper 'carry pepper'
- (b) $d\grave{u}v\grave{u} + \grave{i}r\acute{i}b\acute{o}$ $\implies$ $[d\grave{u}v\grave{i}r\acute{i}b\acute{o}]$
 pound pepper 'pound pepper'
- (c) $br\grave{u} + \grave{i}r\acute{i}b\acute{o}$ $\implies$ $[br\grave{i}r\acute{i}b\acute{o}]$
 cut pepper 'cut pepper'
- (d) $k\grave{u} + \grave{e}_1v\grave{r}\acute{i}$ $\implies$ $[k\grave{w}e\grave{v}r\acute{i}]$
 pour oil 'pour oil'
- (e) $h\grave{u}h\grave{u} + \acute{e}c\acute{e}$ $\implies$ $[h\grave{u}h\acute{e}c\acute{e}]$
 close door 'close a door'

- (f) $\text{bru} + \text{ɔnɛ} \implies [\text{br}\text{ɔn}\text{ɛ}]$
 cut yam 'cut yam'
- (g) $\text{si} + \text{ɛt}\check{\text{o}}_2 \implies [\text{sj}\text{ɛt}\check{\text{o}}]$
 pull hair 'pull hair'
- (h) $\text{v}\check{\text{u}}\check{\text{r}}\check{\text{i}} + \text{o}_2\text{b}\check{\text{o}} \implies [\text{v}\check{\text{u}}\check{\text{r}}\check{\text{o}}\text{b}\check{\text{o}}]$
 break hand 'break a hand'
- (i) $\text{kri} + \text{o}_1\text{b}\acute{\text{u}}\text{k}\acute{\text{o}}_1 \implies [\text{kr}\text{o}\text{b}\acute{\text{u}}\text{k}\text{o}]$
 late back 'be late'
- (j) $\acute{\text{u}}\text{b}\acute{\text{i}} + \text{ɛr}\text{o}_2 \implies [\acute{\text{u}}\text{b}\acute{\text{j}}\text{ɛr}\text{o}]$
 seed eye 'pupil'
- (k) $\text{ɛt}\check{\text{o}}_2 + \text{ɛ}\acute{\text{g}}\text{b}\acute{\text{a}} \implies [\text{ɛt}\text{w}\acute{\text{e}}\text{g}\text{b}\check{\text{a}}]$
 hair jaw 'beard'

In the examples in 58 above, verbs with a CVCV or a CrV structure undergo ^{also} vowel elision rather than glide formation, even though their final vowels are a_λ [+High]. We note here that monosyllabic verbs with a CrV structure behave in this regard as disyllabic verbs since those whose vowel segments are [+High] do not condition glide formation. This may be an indication that a CrV syllable structure is a derived one from an underlying $\text{C}_1\text{V}_1\text{C}_2\text{V}_2$ structure in which V_1 has been elided (Elugbe, 1973, 1989a). We shall return to this point later in 3.7 when we discuss syllable structure.

There are, however, a few trisyllabic nouns with [+High] final vowels which may also undergo glide

formation when they occur as V_1 in a vowel sequence. Below are the ones found in my data:

- 59 (a) $úkirì + \text{fúáfò}_2 \implies [ukirj\text{f}\acute{w}\acute{a}f\grave{o}]$
 drum white 'a white drum'
- (b) $\text{éwé} \acute{n} + \text{vò}_2 \implies [éw\acute{e}rj\text{v}\grave{o}]$
 monkey one 'one monkey'
- (c) $\text{áarè}_2 + \text{ójó} \acute{j}\acute{o}_1 \text{v}\acute{í} \implies [á\text{r}\acute{e}j\acute{o}j\acute{o}j\acute{o}v\acute{i}]$
 man fine 'a handsome man'

(c) A third condition is that the vowel occurring across the boundary, that is, V_2 is not grammatically vacuous. We mentioned earlier, while discussing vowel elision, that some vowels get elided because they are grammatically vacuous. Therefore, even though conditions (a) and (b) of glide formation may be met, the process may not take place if V_2 is grammatically vacuous. In such a case, the vowel is usually elided before V_1 has a chance of forming a glide.

Compare 60 (a) and (b) as well as (c) and (d) below.

60. (a) $\text{é}_1 \text{v}\acute{u} + \text{vò}_2 \implies [é\text{v}\acute{u}\text{v}\grave{o}]$
 stomach one 'oneness'

- (b) $e_1v\ddot{u} + \grave{m}\acute{\xi} \implies [e\ddot{v}\ddot{u}m\acute{\xi}]$
 stomach mine 'my stomach'
- (c) $\acute{i}b\acute{i} + \acute{e}_2r\grave{a} \implies [\acute{i}bj\acute{e}r\grave{a}]$
 seeds three 'three seeds'
- (d) $\acute{i}b\acute{i} + \acute{e}_2n\grave{a}n\grave{a} \implies [\acute{i}b\acute{i}m\grave{a}n\grave{a}]$
 seeds these ones 'these seeds'

From the conditions stated above, it is obvious that morpheme structure as well as grammatical function have a role to play in the application of glide formation rules.

In accounting for glide formation within our chosen framework, we shall allow a change of an original V slot on the CV tier which dominated V_1 in the sequence to change to a C slot as in the following derivation.

61. (a) Underlying Representation

(b) By glide formation

(where V1 refers to the first vowel and V2 to the second vowel in the sequence). Elugbe (personal communication) has suggested an alternative representation in which we allow

the initial C slot to branch out and dominate both the original consonant segment and the glide. This analysis has been adopted by Anderson (1993) in the description of vowel quality alternation in Dinka. [ovje] would thus be represented as in 62 below.

62. (a) Underlying Representation

[ovje]

'a king'

(b) By glide formation

However, within the CV framework (cf Clements and Keyser 1983:34) elements of the CV tier should correspond to the timing units of speech production at the subsyllabic level. A single C represents a single unit of timing while a sequence CC represents a double timing unit. Thus, the representation in 62 would be appropriate if the result of the application of glide formation rules is the creation of a complex segment such as an affricate or a diphthong, as one finds in Dinka. In Urhobo, on the other hand, we notice that the glide still behaves as a separate segment from the

preceding consonant segment. Let us consider the string $(f\ddot{u} + e_2\grave{r}\grave{a}\grave{r}\grave{e}_2) \dashrightarrow [f\grave{w}\grave{e}\grave{r}\grave{a}\grave{r}\grave{e}]$ 'put out/extinguish fire' in 63 below.

([N] represents the nasal autosegment.)

63. (a) Underlying representation

extinguish fire

(b) By glide formation

(c) by [N] relinking

(d) By [N] spreading

(e) surface representation

[f w ẽ r̥ ã r̥ ẽ]

'put out / extinguish fire'

However, the derived surface form in 63(e) is not the correct phonetic realisation of the string. The glide [w] which is derived from /u/ by the application of glide formation rules retains its nasality in the phonetic form. /f/ is not a nasalisable segment in this language and so is unaffected by the phenomenon. Consequently, the two segments dominated by the same C slot in 63 behave differently, which should not be the case. Moreover, the double timing unit of the sequence is *auditorily* perceived. Since it is uneconomical to represent glides in different ways depending on the phonological phenomenon we are dealing with, we would, everywhere in this work, represent a glide with a separate C slot; in other words, we would change an underlying V slot dominating the segment into a C slot following the application of glide formation rules. The string in 63 and other similar strings would, therefore, be represented as in 64 below:

64. (a) Underlying representation

(b) By glide formation

(c) by [N] spreading

(d) Surface representation

[fw̃er̥āre] 'put out/extinguish fire'

3.4.3 VOWEL LENGTHENING

Vowel lengthening is a process that occurs within certain grammatical configurations in Urhobo; one of the most obvious ones being verbal constructions in the negative. In this language, there are no significantly long vowels and yet, only vowels may bear tones. On the other hand, there are a number of tomorphs which are not linked to any segments in the underlying representation. Let us consider, as an example, the negative tomorph which is simply a LH tone sequence in the underlying representation.

This tomorph is supposed to be mapped onto the final vowel in the phonetic realisation. However, in the phonetic realisation, one notices that the final vowel in the configuration is lengthened, as can be verified from the instrumental tracings in Figures 1 and 2 for the sentences in 65(a) and (b) respectively.

65. (a) /é[́]sè₂ dɛ[́] ʒka/ -----> [é[́]sè dɔkà]
 HL H HL HL HL
 name of bought maize 'Ese bought maize' (Fig. 1)
 person
- (b) /é[́]sè₂ dɛ[́] ʒkà ' ' / -----> [é[́]sè dɔkààà]
 HL H HL (LH) HL HLLH
 name bought maize negative tomorph 'Ese did not buy maize' (Fig. 2)

(Note that each figure contains two tracings of the same sentence; the sentences were repeated for cross-checking purposes only).

A comparison of the length of the final [a] vowel segment in the two sentences shows that the duration of the sound in fig. 2 is about thrice its duration in fig. 1, even though, in this case, the positive form ends with a low tone. This indicates that the segmentalisation of the LH sequence is provided for in terms of vowel length.

Following autosegmental tradition (cf Goldsmith 1990:48 ff) vowel length would be indicated by additional V slots on the CV tier but the V slots would dominate only one vowel segment on the segmental tier. Consequently, we interpret the duration of [a]

noticeable in fig. 2 as an indication to create two extra V slots to accommodate the floating LH sequence which marks the negative. Our derivation is set out in 66 below:

Another example is presented in 67 below.

Vowel lengthening does not occur if the configuration is a question. The question tomorph is a floating low tone which is also realised on the final vowel of the utterance. If the statement already ends on a low tone, the addition of the question tomorph does not result in a further lowering of the final low tone, as happens in some Edoid languages such as Ghotuo (Elugbe, 1985). In fact, there is no difference in the pitch level between the final low tone of a statement and that of a question and so the effect of the

segmentalisation of the tomorph in this case is vacuous. Instead, what happens here is that the high tone immediately preceding the final low tone is upstepped probably in anticipation of this segmentalisation and is realised on a level slightly higher than a preceding high tone. Let us compare figs 1 and 2 with fig. 3 which traces a sentence in the question form:

68.	é s e ₂ d é	ɔ k a	---->	[é s e d á k a]
	HL H	H L (L)		HL H ^R L
	name bought maize	question		'Did Ese buy maize?' (Fig. 3)

(where H^R indicates a raised high pitch).

We find that there is no final vowel lengthening neither is there any difference in the pitch of the final low tone of the statement (Fig. 1) and the question (Fig. 3).

However, if the statement ends on a high tone, the segmentalisation of the question tomorph results in the creation of a HL contour but with no vowel lengthening. Thus, we would have:

69.	ɔ d é	ɔ n é	----->	[ɔ d ó n é]
	L H	L H (L)		L H HL
	3rd pers bought yam	question		'Did he buy yam'
	singular	tomorph		

3.5 VOWEL HARMONY IN URHOBO

We cannot discuss Urhobo vowel segments without examining the phenomena of vowel harmony and nasality in vowels. Our discussion is necessitated by the fact that they have some significant implications for the understanding of a number of items which we shall come across in our discussion of the tone system. We shall begin by examining the phenomenon of vowel harmony.

Vowel harmony can be defined as a process whereby the vowels of a given language can be divided into two mutually exclusive sets such that the vowels of a given morpheme, word or verbal phrase are selected from any one of the two sets. The vowels in each set can cooccur with themselves to the exclusion of the vowels of the other set. The phenomenon has been attested in many West African languages and in the Edoid languages, the vowels are grouped into the following sets.

Set 1: i, e, ə, o, u

Set 2: I, ε, a, ɔ, ɔ̃

In Urhobo, two seemingly identical morphemes may behave differently when they appear in certain constructions due to the operation of vowel harmony. Consider the examples in 70 and 71 below:

70. (a) se₁ ----> [sɛ̃] 'call, read'
 (b) do₁ ----> [dɔ̃] 'throw'
 (c) wẽ₁ ----> [wẽ̃] 'thread (v)'

71. (a) re_2 ----> [rè] 'eat'
 (b) so_2 ----> [sò] 'sing'
 (c) $s\check{e}_2$ ----> [sě] 'refuse'

In the infinitive form, these verbs pattern is as in 72 and 73 respectively.

72. (a) $\grave{e}se$ ----> [èsé] 'to call, read'
 (b) $\grave{e}dó$ ----> [èdó] 'to throw'
 (c) $\grave{e}w\acute{e}$ ----> [èwé] 'to thread'
73. (a) $\grave{e}ri\acute{o}$ ----> [ɛrjɔ́] 'to eat'
 (b) $\grave{e}su\acute{o}$ ----> [ɛswɔ́] 'to sing'
 (c) $\grave{e}s\check{i}\acute{o}$ ----> [ɛsjɔ́] 'to refuse'

In the Verb + Noun construction they behave as in 74 and 75 respectively.

74. (a) $se_1 + \acute{o}b\grave{e}$ ---> [sòbè] 'read a book'
 (b) $dò_1 + \acute{a}j\acute{m}\acute{a}$ ---> [dàj\acute{m}\acute{a}] 'throw a cloth'
 (c) $w\check{e}_1 + \acute{o}rú\acute{r}\acute{u}$ ---> [wǒrú\acute{r}\acute{u}] 'thread a needle'
75. (a) $re_2 + \acute{o}n\acute{e}$ ---> [rjò\acute{n}\acute{e}] 'eat yam'
 (b) $sò_2 + \grave{u}n\grave{e}$ ---> [swùn\grave{e}] 'sing a song'
 (c) $s\check{e}_2 + \acute{o}t\acute{a}$ ---> [sjò\acute{t}\acute{a}] 'refuse an utterance'

In this language, the phenomenon exists in varying degrees in the noun and verbal constructions. In 3.2.3 above, we mentioned that although Urhobo has a seven (oral)

vowel system on the surface, the behaviour of the vowels indicates that the system has been reduced from a ten vowel system and as a result, we have recognised nine vowels at the phonological level with e and o sometimes behaving as [+High] and at other times as [-High] vowels.

In describing vowel harmony systems, the terms 'Advanced Tongue Root' [ATR] and Expanded [EXP] are the common labels used for West African languages. Following Ehugbe (1991) we shall divide Urhobo vowels into two sets using lowered indices and the label [+ATR]. The two sets are

Set 1	Set 2
[+ ATR]	[-ATR]
i u	e ₂ o ₂
e ₁ o ₁	ɛ ɔ
	ɔ

The vowels in each set co-occur with themselves in the following words:

76. Set 1 [+ATR]	Set 2 [-ATR]	
í kú 'crayfish'	é ₂ gbá	'jaw'
é ₁ bò ₁ 'sack'	ò ₂ dɛ	'name'
ú ₁ fí 'rope'	è d è	'day'
ó ₁ dó ₁ 'mortar'	ɔ kà	'maize'
	ayá	'broom'

The vowels /i, u, e₂, o₂/ are the [+High] vowels in the two sets and they behave alike in constructions as we shall show later.

Urhobo is a language with a root controlled [ATR] vowel harmony system. Stem vowels are either [+ATR] or [-ATR] while affixes are generally unspecified for the feature [ATR], receiving their [ATR] specification from the stem. In autosegmental framework, this means that [ATR] harmony is the result of the spreading of an underlying [ATR] autosegment onto unspecified [ATR]-bearing units to its left or to its right, since vowel harmony is also bi-directional. This position is schematised by Pulleyblank (1986:130) as follows:

77. [ATR] Harmony

[+ATR]

Conditions: 1 x = rhyme

2 mirror image

He explains that the first condition which specifies that slots relevant to the rule must be rhyme slots and not onsets encodes the fact that ATR Harmony affects only vowels, not consonants. The second condition serves to specify the bi-directional nature of [ATR] spreading; in other words, a [+ATR] autosegment spreads to a free rhyme slot on either its right or left.

In Urhobo, nasal vowels pattern exactly like their oral counterparts with respect to vowel harmony and so they would not be given separate treatments. We shall now turn to the effect of vowel harmony in various constructions. Although we shall mention briefly vowel harmony in nouns and nominal, more attention would be on affix harmony in the verbal system as that has more implications for our main work.

3.5.1 VOWEL HARMONY IN NOUNS AND NOMINALS

A noun in Urhobo is generally made up of a prefix vowel and a stem which consists of at least a consonant and one or two vowel segments. Whereas the majority of nouns in the language pattern as in (76) above, there are a number of exceptions. The following are some of them:

78. (a) [íṣ̄] 'faeces' e) [ɛ̀bò] 'charm'
 (b) [úk̄] 'trouble' f) [ɔ̀bò] 'doctor'
 (c) [ɛ̀fá] 'divination' g) [ásé] 'acquittal'
 (d) [òdè] 'name'

Items such as in (78) above give the impression that there is no vowel harmony in the noun, a fact which probably led Kelly (1969^b) to conclude that vowel harmony has broken down completely in the Urhobo noun.

However, a look at the way nouns form their plurals indicates that the phenomenon still exists to some extent in the noun. Urhobo nouns form their plural by alternating the prefix vowel of the singular noun with another vowel and, generally, it is

the stem vowel that determines this alternation. If the stem vowel is a Set 1 vowel, the typical plural prefix would be /i/ and if it is a Set 2 vowel, the typical plural prefix would be /e/. The following are some examples:

79. Set 1 Vowels.

- a) ỳé₁ré₁ 'road' - ỳé₁ré 'roads'
- b) ỳdì 'drink' - ỳdì 'drinks'
- c) é₁bò₁ 'sack' - íbò 'sacks'
- d) ó₁dó₁ 'mortal' - ídó 'mortars'
- e) ỳnè₁ 'song' - ỳnè 'songs'
- f) ỳnmù 'drug' - ỳnmù 'drugs'
- Set 2 Vowels
- g) è₂rákò₂ 'dog' - è₂rákò 'dogs'
- h) ò₂dè 'name' - èdè 'names'
- i) é₂cé 'door' - é₂cé 'doors'
- j) ỳbò₂ 'doctor' - èbò 'doctors'
- k) àyá 'broom' - èyá 'brooms'

There is also a group of nouns which Elugbe (1973) refers to as 'paired body parts'. These form their plural by alternating the singular prefix vowel with /a/ instead of /i/ or /e/ as indicated above. The following are some examples:

80. a) ò₂wò 'leg' - àwò 'legs'
- b) ò₂bò 'hand' - àbò 'hands'

- c) `akõ<sub>2</sub> 'tooth' - `akõ₂ 'teeth'
 d) `ɛrõ<sub>2</sub> 'eye' - `arõ₂ 'eyes'

As for the nominals, there are some nominals derived from Verb + Noun sequences; they signal agentive meaning. Since all verbs begin with a consonant and all nouns begin with a vowel, a prefix must be added to the verb stem in order to nominalise the verb. This prefix vowel attached to the verb stem is selected according to the harmonic category of the verb stem vowel. The two vowels which alternate in the prefix position are /o/ and /ɔ/, the former co-occurring with Set 1 vowels and the latter with Set 2 vowels. Below are some examples:

81. (a) sũ - ɔsũ
 lead - 'leader'
 (b) fã + ɛtõ₂ - ɔfẽ tõ₂
 flog hair - 'comb'
 (c) gbè₁ + usí - ò₁gbùsì
 mix starch - 'native frying pan'
 (d) sì + ɔbè₂ - ò₁sùbè [òsùbè]
 write book - 'secretary'
 (e) jɔrẽ₂ + íyó₁ - ɔjɔríyò₁
 hold money - 'treasurer'

(f) t̃a + 0₂t̃a' - ɔ̃t̃0₂t̃a

Speak word - 'spokesman'

Note that all the nominals derived from this process are low-toned irrespective of the inherent tones of the items from which they are derived. We shall return to this in Chapter five when we deal with tones in nominals.

3.5.2 AFFIX HARMONY IN THE VERBAL SYSTEM

In the verbal system of this language, the vowels of affixes which accompany verb stems, such as, subject pronouns, concord markers, tense/aspect markers, are required to agree in harmony with the verb stem vowel(s). In this section, we shall examine some of them.

3.5.2.1 THE INFINITIVE (AND GERUND)

(Infinitives and gerunds are homonyms and their formation involves the same processes in Urhobo and so no separate treatment would be given to gerunds).

In an earlier work (Aziza, 1994), we claimed that deriving the infinitive form of the verb involves the addition of a prefix vowel to the verb stem in all cases but that a suffix is added only if the verb stem vowel is [+High]. In this work, based on a better exposure to relevant data, Urhobo provides evidence to support Elugbe's (1989a) claim that PE employed a discontinuous morpheme *U...(A) mhi as its infinitive/gerund - marking morpheme. This morpheme, according to him, was realised as *u...(ə) mhi if the

verb stem had [+ATR] vowels and as *ɔ... (a) mɪl if the vowels of the verb stem were [-ATR]. The optional (A) (ɛɔ~a) was deleted if the preceding stem vowel was not a close front or back vowel.

The infinitive-marking morpheme in Urhobo may be represented as:

E...O

and it bears the tones L ...H. The prefix E has two realisations: e- if the verb stem vowel is a Set 1 vowel and ɛ- if it is a Set 2 vowel. Similarly, the suffix O is realised as -o if the verb stem vowel is a Set 1 vowel and as -ɔ if it is a Set 2 vowel. However, the suffix is deleted if the verb stem vowel is [-High] and when this happens, the high tone of the suffix is realised on the verb stem vowel. If the verb stem vowel is [+High], the realisation of the suffix conditions glide formation so that the verb stem vowel surfaces as [j] for [-Back] vowels and as [w] for [+Back] vowels. We illustrate our point with the examples in 82 and the sample derivation in 83 below. (The tones will be discussed in Chapter Four)

82. (a) si 'write, pull' - e₁sió₁ [ɛsjo₁] 'to write, pull'
 (b) se₁ 'call, read' - e₁se₁, 'to call, read'
 (c) do₁ 'throw' - e₁do₁ 'to throw'
 (d) ku 'pour' - e₁kuó₁ [ɛkwó] 'to pour'
 (e) re₂ 'eat' - ɛri₂ [ɛrj₂] 'to eat'
 (f) ʃɛ 'sell' - ɛʃɛ 'to sell'

(g) da 'drink' - ἔδα 'to drink'

(h) kpɔ 'dry up' - ἔkpɔ 'to dry up'

(i) so₂ 'sing' - ἔsuɔ [ɛswɔ] 'to sing'

83. Sample derivation

a) (i) Vowel Harmony tier

[+ATR] (Underlying Representation)

CV tier

C V

Segmental tier

s i

'write, pull'

(ii)

[+ATR]

(by affixation)

(iii)

[+ATR]

(by [ATR] spreading)

(iv) [+ATR] (by glide formation)

[esjo] 'to write, to pull'

b)(i) Vowel Harmony tier [-ATR] (Underlying Representation)

(ii) [-ATR] (by affixation)

(by [ATR] spreading)

(by glide formation)

[ɛ̀ sw ɔ́] 'to sing'

c) (i) Vowel Harmony tier

[+ATR]

(Underling Representation)

CV tier

C V

Segmental tier

s e₁

'to read, call'

(by affixation)

(by [ATR] spreading)

(by deletion of suffix)

[e'se] 'to read, to call'

d) (i) [-ATR]

(Underlying Representation)

'drink'

(ii) [-ATR]

(by affixation)

(iii) [-ATR]

(by [ATR] spreading)

(iv) [-ATR]

(by deletion of suffix)

[ɛ̣ d á] 'to drink'

3.5.2.2 THE PAST TENSE

The past tense is marked by a suffix -ri which is attached to the verb stem and is realised in two shapes, -ri ~ -re, depending on the harmony requirements of the verb stem vowel. If the verb stem vowel is [+ATR], it selects -ri and if it is a [-ATR] vowel, it selects -re. Below are some examples:

84. Set 1 [+ATR] verbs

- a) si ~ siri - mì sírì
 'write' - 'wrote' 'I wrote'
- b) se₁ ~ seri mì sérì
 read - 'read' 'I read'
- c) do₁ ~ dori - mì dórì
 throw 'threw' 'I threw'

Set 2 [-ATR] Verbs

- d) re₂ ~ rere - mè rère
 'eat' 'ate' 'I ate'

- e) da ~ dare - mè dàrè
 'drink' 'drank' 'I drank'
- f) kɔ̃ ~ kɔ̃re - mè kɔ̃rè
 'plant' 'planted' 'I planted'

In our sample derivations in 85 below, we indicate the vowels of the first person singular subject pronoun and the past tense marker respectively with I before harmony takes place.

85. Sample derivations.

b) (i) Vowel Harmony tier

[-ATR]

(Underlying Representation)

C V tier

Segmental tier

(ii)

[-ATR]

(by [ATR] spreading)

It should be pointed out that if the verb phrase includes an object (which also always comes after the verb) the past tense marker is deleted, as in the following examples.

86. a) mĩ se₁ we₁ 'I called you'b) mẽ₂ dá u₂di 'I drank wine'

It should also be noted that if the verb stem vowel is both [+High] and [+Back], that is, /u/ or /o₂/, [ATR] harmony occurs coupled with an assimilation process which copies the features of the verb stem vowel

onto the suffix vowel. Below are

a few examples.

87. a) ku 'pour' - kúru 'poured'
 b) duwu 'pierce' - duwuru 'pierced'
 c) so₂ 'sing' - so₂ro₂ 'sang'
 d) ro₂ro₂ 'be hot' - ro₂ro₂ro₂ 'became hot'

The examples in 87 above indicate that the spreading of autosegments may sometimes be blocked in certain contexts so that here, as with the tones that we shall examine later, automatic spreading of autosegments is a language - specific principle, rather than a universal one. We shall not dwell more on this here.

3.5.2.3 SUBJECT AND OBJECT PRONOUNS

Each monosyllabic subject or object pronoun in this language is realised in two phonetic shapes to agree with the harmonic category of the very stem vowel. The pronouns are listed in 88 and 89 below:

88. Subject Pronouns

Singular	Plural
1. mi ~ me 'I'	àvare/ me ~ ma 'we'
2. wo ~ wɔ 'you (sg)'	òwawá/ we ~ wa 'you (p)'
3. o ~ ɔ 'he/she/it'	aje 'they'

89. Object Pronouns

Singular	Plural
1. ve ~ vɛ 'me'	àvare 'us'
2. we ~ wɛ 'you'	òwawá 'you'
3. ro ~ rɔ 'him/her/it'	aje 'them'

The use of these pronouns is illustrated in examples 90 and 91 below:

90. Subject Pronouns.

(i) [+ ATR] verbs

mì sírì	'I pulled'
wò, sírì	'you pulled'
ò, sírì	'he/she pulled'
àwàré/mè sírì	'we pulled'
òwà wá/wè sírì	'you pulled'
ájě sírì	'they pulled'

(ii) [- ATR] verbs

mè, dárè	'I drank'
wò dárè	'you drank'
ò dárè	'he/she drank'
àwàré/mà dárè	'we drank'
òwà wá/wà dárè	'you drank'
ájě dárè	'they drank'

91. Object Pronouns.

(i) [+ ATR] verbs

wò, sí vé	'you pulled me'
ò, sí wé	'he pulled you'

mì sí ró₁

'I pulled him/her/it'

wò sí ávarè₂, -[wò sjaúáǎǎ]

'you pulled us'

ò sí òwau á -[ò sjoúwáúá]

'he pulled you'

mì sí ajè₂ -[mì sjaǎǎ]

'I pulled them'

(ii) [-ATR] verbs

wò fá vé

'you flogged me'

ò fá wé

'he flogged you'

mè fá rò

'I flogged him/her/it'

wò fá ávarè₂, -[wò fáúáǎǎ]

'you flogged us'

ò fá ò₂ wau á -[ò fówá úá]

'he flogged you'

mè fá ajè₂ -[mè fáǎǎ]

'I flogged them'

A point must be made here about the third person singular object pronoun. In this position, there is an additional constraint on the [ATR] vowel harmony in the sense discussed so far. If the verb stem vowel is both [-High]) and [-Back], that is, /e/ or /ɛ/ [ATR] harmony occurs together with assimilation. In this case the features of the verb stem vowel are also copied onto the vowel of the third person singular object pronoun. Thus instead of the forms in 92, we have the forms in 93 as the correct ones.

92 a) * mì sé ró

b) * wò té ró

c) * wò sɛ ró

- d) * ɔ̀ tɔ̀ré rɔ̀
- 93 a) mɪ̀ sé, ré, `I called him'
 b) wò, té, ré, `you got there'
 c) wɔ̀ sé ré `you sold it'
 d) ɔ̀ tɔ̀ré ré `he burnt it'

3.5.3.4 COMPLEX VERBS

Complex verbs are formed from Verb + Noun Sequences. The process involves the deletion of the verb stem vowel but its vowel harmony features remain and surface on neighbouring segments when the complex verb is used in constructions. Consider the following example:

94. mɪ̀révũ derived from mɪ̀ɛ + é, vũ
 be pregnant see stomach

It patterns as follows:

95. a) [mɛ̀ mɪ̀révũ] 'I am pregnant'
 b) [wɔ̀ mɪ̀révũ] 'you are pregnant'
 c) [ɔ̀ mɪ̀révũ] 'she is pregnant'

The subject pronouns harmonise with the deleted vowel /ɛ/ of the verb stem and not with the Set 1 vowels of the noun. This is an indication that vowel harmony is ordered before any deletion takes place. A string like [ɔ̀ mɪ̀révũ] 'she is pregnant' is

derived as in 96 below. The third person singular subject pronoun is indicated underlyingly as O. (For now we shall regard the CCV syllable structure as underlying).

96. Sample derivation.

i) Vowel Harmony tier [-ATR] [+ATR] (Underlying Representation)

ii) Vowel Harmony tier [-ATR] [+ATR] (by [ATR] spreading)

iii) Vowel Harmony tier [-ATR] [+ATR] (by Vowel Elision)

3.5.3.5 THE FUTURE TENSE

The future tense marker is an independent morpheme which precedes the verb stem and is realised in two phonological shapes according to the [ATR] harmony requirements of the verb stem vowel. The two shapes of the future tense morpheme are: /cẽ/ with Set 1 verb stems and /ca/ with Set 2 verb stems. The following are a few examples.

97. Set 1 verbs

- a) mí cè: sí 'I will write, pull'
- b) mí cè: kó₁ 'I will sew'
- c) ó cè: bú 'It will be plentiful'
- d) àṽar̃é cè cé₁r̃é₁ 'we will cook'

98. Set 2 verbs

- a) mé₂cà tá 'I will tell, say'
- b) w̃á cà ʃé 'you will sell'
- c) òwàṽá cà só₂ 'you (pl) will sing'

d) `ajé cà fɔ́ɔ́

'they will wash'

Notice that the first and the third person plural subject pronouns which in the citation form end with the low tone become high because of the construction in which they are used. We shall return to this point in our discussion of tone in Chapter Six.

3.5.3 CONCLUSION

To conclude this section, we submit that Urhobo operates a root controlled [ATR] vowel harmony system. In addition, affix alternation in both the noun and the verb may form a basis for reconstructing merged vowels. Elugbe (personal communication) has suggested that the situation in Urhobo may be likened to that in Nupe and that Hyman's suggestion that Nupe phonology can be made more abstract if an absolute neutralisation rule is recognised may also be applicable to Urhobo. The rule in Urhobo would then be that *I, *ɔ have become e₂, o₂ respectively. Although there is a lot of merit in this suggestion, making a case for such a rule is beyond the scope of this work. For now, we include /e₂/ and /o₂/ as members of the vowel segments of Urhobo in underlying representation only, based on their behaviour.

3.6 NASALITY IN URHOBO

A comprehensive discussion of nasality in Urhobo is beyond the scope of this work. However, it does have a special status in the language which can most insightfully be captured within the framework of autosegmental phonology. It provides further evidence for the segmentalisation of the feature [Nasal] onto a separate autosegmental

tier independent of other segmental features. We begin by briefly describing the behaviour of sound segments with respect to nasality.

We mentioned in 3.2.2 and 3.2.3 above that Urhobo has both nasal consonants and vowels. All [+sonorant] segments can be nasalised when they occur in a nasal environment. In this regard, the glottal fricative /h/ behaves as a [+sonorant] segment although there is friction in its production. Thus, all vowels and the consonants /m,n,ɲ, ^ŋɾ,h,ʋ,j,w/ are receptive while all other segments are opaque to it.

3.6.1 ALTERNATIONS IN NASALITY

We showed, while discussing vowel harmony in 3.5 above, that the process of forming certain constructions in Urhobo, such as, the infinitive, the past tense and even the verb + object pronoun construction, involve the addition of a suffix to the verb stem. (For the purposes of this discussion, we would regard the object pronoun as a suffix attached to the verb). We showed that these suffixes have to agree with the [ATR] requirements of the verb stem vowel. In addition, they also have to agree in nasality with the verb stem vowel. (Nasal vowels do not occur as prefix vowels in this language). If the verb stem vowel is [+ Nasal], the suffix must be realised as [+ Nasal]. Conversely, if the verb stem vowel is [- Nasal], the suffix must surface as [- Nasal]. If the suffix is made up of both a consonant segment (which is usually a [+ sonorant] and a vowel segment, both segments are affected by the nasality phenomenon. Let us examine the examples in 99, 100 and 101 below:

The starred forms are the unacceptable forms:

99. The Infinitive forms

	Verb Stem		Derived Forms
a)	sè ₁ 'call'	-->	[èsé] 'to call' * ese
b)	sàré ₂ 'sprinkle'	--->	[ɛsàré] 'to sprinkle' * ɛsarɔ
c)	sě ₂ 'refuse'	--->	[ɛsǝ] 'to refuse' * ɛsɔ
d)	síw ₁ 'save'	--->	[esíwò] 'to save' * esiwò

100. Past tense forms

a)	tà 'say'	--->	[tárè] 'said' * tare
b)	huòrè 'wash'	--->	[xwòrè] 'washed' * xwor re
c)	kɔ̃ 'plant'	--->	[kɔ̃rè] 'planted' * kɔ̃re
d)	fàríɛ 'be wayward'	-->	[fàrjèrè] 'was wayward' * fàrjère

101. Verb + Object Pronoun construction

a)	fá + vɛ 'flogged me'	-->	[fávɛ]
b)	ɣàré ₂ + rɔ 'divided it'	--->	[ɣàréɔ]
c)	fá + vɛ 'exposed me'	--->	[fávɛ]
d)	kǎrě ₂ + rɔ 'locked it'	--->	[kǎrěɔ]

In a Verb + Noun Object construction, nasality survives even when the vowel segment which bore the [+ Nasal] specification gets elided or becomes nonsyllabic. Let us consider the example in 102 below:

102. Verb + Noun Object Construction.

- | | | | |
|----|--|------|--|
| a) | $k\overset{\sim}{\sigma} + \overset{\sim}{\sigma}ka$ | ---> | $[k\overset{\sim}{\sigma}ka]$ |
| | plant maize | | 'plant maize' |
| b) | $s\tilde{e}_2 + \overset{\sim}{\sigma}ta$ | ---> | $[s\tilde{j}\tilde{o}ta]$ |
| | refuse word | | 'refute a word' |
| c) | $gb\tilde{e} + \tilde{j}e_1r\tilde{e}_1$ | ---> | $[gb\tilde{j}e_1r\tilde{e}_1]$ |
| | clear road | | 'clear a road' |

3.6.2 AUTOSEGMENTAL ANALYSIS

Hyman (1982) proposes that we regard nasality as an autosegment capable of being mapped onto a lexical morpheme or stem. Within the autosegmental framework, the occurrence of a particular feature on one tier does not preclude it from occurring on another tier (cf van der Hulst and Vergnaud, 1982). A particular phenomenon may occur on different tiers within a phonological representation and since the tiers are independent of one another, what affects the phenomenon on one tier may not affect it on another tier. It is for this reason that we may differentiate two types of nasality, namely, nasality as a distinctive feature and nasality as an autosegment. As a distinctive feature, it is part and parcel of the segmental make-up of the sounds on which it is found and so occurs on the segmental tier. The only consonant segments that possess it as a segmental feature in Urhobo are the four nasal consonants, /m, n, ɲ, ŋm/.

On the other hand, nasality may be regarded as an autosegment and so occurs on an autosegmental tier. As an autosegment, Hyman (1982) has suggested that nasality be mapped onto lexical morphemes or stems. In other words, a lexical morpheme is either marked positive for nasality or it has no underlying nasal specification. Just like the vowel harmony autosegment considered in 3.5 above, and the tonal autosegment to be considered later, within a lexical morpheme both the nasality bearing unit (NBU) and the domain within which the phenomenon can be realised must be specified for each language. Nasality is, thus, linked to a segment in the phonological representation only by association; it is independent of that segment. Consequently, it is stable, that is, it can feature even in the absence of the segment to which it has been linked; it can float, and it can spread onto neighbouring segments which are receptive to it. We would be concerned in this section only with nasality as an autosegment.

One way of accounting for the nasal autosegment in Urhobo is to propose that the nasality bearing unit (NBU) for the nasal autosegment in the underlying representation is the only or final vowel segment within a stem. This means that the autosegment is mapped onto only a V slot on the CV tier in the underlying representation and so nasal consonants are not NBUs. The domain within which the phenomenon is realised is all [+ sonorant] segments within the stem. Thus, apart from the NBU, all other nasalised segments within a stem are derived from the spreading of the nasal auto segment but its

that is, from right to left. (Note that this spread is blocked by the boundary that exists between the prefix vowel and the stem so that the prefix vowel in a phonological word is not affected by the nasality within the stem. We indicate this boundary with " - ".) Let us consider some examples:

103. a) $\overset{\cdot}{u}$ -w $\overset{\cdot}{e}$ v $\overset{\cdot}{i}$ ---> [u $\tilde{w}$ $\tilde{e}$ $\tilde{v}$ i] 'a house'
- b) a-v $\overset{\cdot}{a}$ r $\overset{\cdot}{e}$ $\overset{\cdot}{e}$ $\overset{\cdot}{e}$ $\overset{\cdot}{e}$ ---> [a $\tilde{v}$ $\tilde{a}$ r $\tilde{e}$ $\tilde{e}$ $\tilde{e}$ $\tilde{e}$] 'we, us'
- c) s $\tilde{e}$ $\overset{\cdot}{e}$ $\overset{\cdot}{e}$ ---> [s $\tilde{e}$] 'refuse'
- d) mr $\overset{\cdot}{e}$ ---> [m $\tilde{r}$ $\tilde{e}$] 'see'

We illustrate with some sample derivations in 104 below. ([N] stands for the nasal autosegment)

ii)

by [N] spreading

iii)

Surface representation

[uwevi] 'house'

b)

i) Nasality tier

C V tier

Segmental tier

Underlying Representation

'we', 'us'

ii)

by [N] spreading

[avare]

Another way of accounting for the nasal autosegment, and our position in this work, is to propose that the NBU may be the final vowel or the first nasal consonant within a stem. Thus, although it is also mapped onto only one slot on the CV tier, that slot may be a C1, if it is a nasal consonant, or the final V slot within the stem. Our proposal is schematised as in 105 below:

105. (a)

(b)

(where ∞ means any vowel segment).

If the nasal autosegment is mapped onto a C slot, it means that the consonant segment must be one of $/m, n, \eta, \hat{\eta}m/$ since these are the only consonant segments that have nasality also as a distinctive feature. If it is mapped onto a V slot, since all the nine phonological vowels can bear nasality, it must be the final vowel of the stem. The domain of nasality remains all [+sonorant] segments within the stem.

The spreading of nasality is bi-directional depending on the type of NBU and also the type of grammatical string. Within a stem, if the NBU is a C, spreading is from left to right but if it is a V, spreading is from right to left. As usual, prefix vowels are not affected by nasality within the stem. The following are some examples:

106. (a) mrɛ ----> [mrɛ̃] 'see'
- (b) ó-ní ----> [ónĩ] 'mother'
- (c) à-ŋmá ----> [aŋmá] 'cloth'
- (d) k ǒ ----> [k ǒ̃] 'plant'
- (e) duvũ ----> [dúvũ̃] 'pierce'
- (f) u-we₁vĩ ----> [uwe₁vĩ̃] 'house'
- (g) ɛ-re₂rè₂ ----> [ɛrè₂rè₂] 'eight'

We present some sample derivations below:

عآ

133

by [N] spreading

(iii)

Surface representation

[mr̥ε] 'see'

(b) (i) Nasality tier

[N]

Underlying Representation

CV tier

V-C V

Segmental tier

a-ʃm̥ a 'cloth'

(ii)

[N]

by [N] spreading

V-C V

a-ʃm̥ a

(iii)

Surface Representation

[aŋmá] 'a cloth'

(c) (i) Nasality tier

Underlying Representation

C V tier

Segmental tier

(ii)

by [N] spreading

(iii)

The examples above show that where [N] is mapped onto C₁, spreading is to the right and includes, where there is one, an immediately following consonant (which is usually [+sonorant] and the vowel segment. Where, on the other hand, it is mapped onto the V, it spreads onto all the preceding nasalisable consonant and vowel segments. Thus, all the segments within a morpheme stem agree on the feature of nasality.

Across morpheme boundary, spreading is always from left to right. In this case, the vowel before the boundary is either a nasal or nasalised vowel and when it gets elided or becomes non-syllabic due to some phonological processes, the nasality phenomenon survives on the vowel across the boundary which then becomes the nucleus of that syllable. Let us consider some examples:

108. (a) $k\check{\text{ɔ}} + \acute{\text{u}}\text{-}\acute{\text{r}}\acute{\text{e}}_1 \quad \text{--->} \quad [\acute{\text{k}}\acute{\text{u}}\acute{\text{r}}\acute{\text{e}}]$
 plant tree 'plant a tree'
- (b) $g\check{\text{b}}\check{\text{e}} + \acute{\text{a}}\text{-}\acute{\text{ɔ}}\acute{\text{u}}\acute{\text{a}} \quad \text{--->} \quad [g\check{\text{b}}\acute{\text{ɔ}}\acute{\text{w}}\acute{\text{a}}]$
 clear bush 'clear bush'
- (c) $\acute{\text{s}}\check{\text{e}}_2 + \acute{\text{a}}_2\text{-}\acute{\text{t}}\acute{\text{a}} \quad \text{--->} \quad [\acute{\text{s}}\check{\text{ɔ}}\acute{\text{t}}\acute{\text{a}}]$
 refute word 'refute a word'

- (d) $s\check{u} + \underset{1}{q}\text{-huo}' \quad \dashrightarrow \quad [s\check{w}\check{o}xw\acute{o}]$
 lead person 'lead a person'
- (e) $m\grave{a} + \underset{2}{o}'\underset{3}{t}' \quad \dashrightarrow \quad [m\acute{o}t\grave{o}]$
 measure land 'measure land'
- (f) $\underset{1}{\eta}\varepsilon + \underset{2}{\eta}'\underset{1}{kpe}\underset{1}{ti} \quad \dashrightarrow \quad [\eta\acute{e}kpe\underset{1}{ti}]$
 press box 'press a box'

We present some sample derivations below:

(iii)

(iv)

(b) (i) Nasality tier

CV tier

Segmental tier

(ii)

(iii)

(iv)

(c) (i) Nasality tier

CV tier

Segmental tier

(ii)

by vowel elision

(iii)

by [N] spreading

(iv)

Surface Representation

[mɔ̃tɔ̃] 'measure land'

The examples in 108 above also demonstrate the stability of the nasal autosegment. We find that where a nasal vowel gets elided or becomes a nonsyllabic glide, the nasality phenomenon is not deleted along with the vowel. Rather, it relinks on the vowel segment that becomes the nucleus of that syllable. If it was a segmental

feature, it should have been deleted along with the other segmental features of the vowel, for instance, its backness.

Thus, the fact that nasality can spread, can be set afloat and it is stable all show that it is an autosegment, independent of the segment that bears it in the phonetic representation.

3.7 URHOB0 SYLLABLE STRUCTURE

3.7.1 INTRODUCTION

Unlike early generative phonology, recent models of autosegmental phonology recognise the syllable as being at the heart of phonological representations and that through it a number of phonological systems are organised. Urhobo tone system presents further evidence for regarding the syllable as a phonological unit since the syllable is the tone bearing unit and a number of phonological processes which affect syllable structure also affect tone and vice versa. As the examples in 3.4 above show, a number of tones get affected when phonological processes necessitate resyllabification, while the segmentalisation of the negative tomorph necessitates the creation of new syllables to bear the tones so as to arrive at well-formed configurations.

In dealing with the syllable in Urhobo, we adopt the CV model of phonology developed by Clements and Keyser (1983). The main reason for this choice, apart from the fact that the CV model of syllable structure is conceptually easier and more systematic in dealing with syllables, is the fact that our theoretical framework for this study includes

a skeletal CV tier which mediates between the various autosegmental tiers and through which a number of phonological processes are organised. Clements and Keyser (1983) assume a three-tiered structure of the syllable, namely:

- a) a syllable node 'σ';
- b) a CV-tier whose C and V elements dominate consonantal and vowel segments;
- c) a segmental tier which consists of bundles of distinctive feature matrices which represent consonant and vowel segments.

Thus, between the syllable node and the segmental tier is the CV tier which is non-branching and lacks internal constituent structure. The C element in the CV model is linked to [+ consonant] segments and represents what in some other models, such as Selkirk's (1982) model, is referred to as the syllable onset or syllable coda, while the V element is linked to [- consonant] segments and represents the syllable nucleus which is the obligatory constituent of the rhyme in Selkirk's model; it is the peak of sonority in the syllable. Any segment dominated by a C element of the CV tier is nonsyllabic while any segment dominated by a V element is syllabic. The V element is the obligatory constituent of the syllable. It is possible to find a well-formed syllable that contains no C element but it is not possible for a syllable to exist without a V element. Each V element defines a syllable and as such, the number of V elements in a string coincides with the number of syllables in the string. As mentioned above, the V element defines the peak of

sonority within the syllable so that when there appears to be a sequence of vowel segments, such as we have in a diphthong, the V element dominates only the most sonorant segment in the sequence. The number of C elements within a syllable is determined by language-specific rules and these rules also specify the collocational restrictions on the combinations of C elements allowed. The principles of resyllabification carry out operations on an underlying representation and modify it in specific ways in order to derive a well formed surface structure. Rules add or delete C elements as required by the specific language.

3.7.2 URHOB0 SYLLABLES

In Urhobo, there exists an ultimate relationship between word structure and syllable structure such that one expects to find identical constraints on the beginnings and ends of both the syllable and the word irrespective of whether we are dealing with an initial, medial or final position. Following Clements and Keyser's classification of syllable types, Urhobo has Type 2 syllables. The classification is as follows: (Clements and Keyser 1983:29)

- | | | |
|------|---------|----------------|
| 110. | Type 1: | CV |
| | Type 2: | CV, V |
| | Type 3: | CV, CVC |
| | Type 4: | CV, V, CVC, VC |

At the phonological level, Urhobo syllable structure can be summarised as follows:

where 'σ' stands for the syllable, '(C)' for the optional C element and 'V' for the obligatory V element. σ dominates C and V elements; C dominates a consonantal segment along with its other distinctive features represented by [F] and V dominates a nonconsonantal segment along with its other distinctive features. The brackets around C captures the fact that C is an optional element, in other words, a syllable may or may not begin with a consonant. All segments dominated by V are vowels; there are no syllabic consonants in this language. Urhobo operates a rule of syllabification that inserts a syllable boundary after each vowel segment. We thus have a situation where all the syllables in the language are open ones. We mentioned earlier that the syllable is the tone bearing unit. However, it is the V element within the syllable that bears the tone. Whenever an original V element loses its syllabicity due to, say, glide formation, it also loses its ability to bear tone and the tone becomes floating and it either surfaces on an adjacent vowel segment or it remains floating and so gets no phonetic realisation.

Thus, the following syllable structures are possible in Urhobo.

112. (a) V
 (b) CV
 (c) CCV

3.7.2.1 THE V SYLLABLE

The V syllable consists of a vowel as the only segment. It is the nucleus of the syllable and bears the tone. The V syllable is the minimum syllable type in the language. It can occur as a word, or initially in the phonological word as a prefix of some sort in nouns, adjectives, demonstratives, as well as in the formation of the gerundive and the infinitive forms from verbs. The following are some examples:

113 (a) /e/	V	interjection	'Used to denote a positive response'
(b) /o ₁ / ~ /ɔ /	V	pronoun	'third person singular pronoun he/she/it as in examples (c) (d) below
(c) /ò ₁ firì/	V - CV - CV		'he/she/it threw' (for instance, money)
(d) /ɔ̀ dare ₂ /	V - CV - CV		'he/she/it drank'
(e) /ɔ̀ - nɛ́/	V - CV	noun	'yam'
(f) /ú - kpe ₁ /	V - CV	noun	'bed'
(g) /ɔ̀ - gá - gǎ /	V - CV - CV	adjective	'strong'
(h) /ó ₁ - jí - jí - rǒ/	V - CV - CV - CV	adjective	'cold'
(i) /ɔ̀ - nà - nà/	V - CV - CV	demonstrative	'this (one)'
(j) /ɔ̀ - jè ₂ - nà /	V - CV - CV	demonstrative	'that (one)'

(k)	/da/	'drink' --->	/ɛ̣ - da/ 'drinking' / 'to drink'
	CV	verb	V - CV gerundive / infinitive
(l)	/ko ₁ /	'sew' --->	/ẹ ₁ - ko ₁ / 'sewing' / to sew'
	CV	verb	V - CV
(m)	/ce ₁ re ₁ /	'cook' --->	/ẹ ₁ - ce ₁ re ₁ / 'cooking' / 'to cook'
	CV - CV	verb	V - C V C V
(n)	/to ₂ rẹ/	'burn' --->	/ɛ̣ - to ₂ rẹ/ ;burning' / 'to burn
	CVCV		V - CVCV

3.7.2.2 THE CV SYLLABLE

The CV syllable consists of a consonant element C and the nucleus V. It is the predominant syllable structure in the language. It can occur as a word or in the initial, medial or final position in the phonological word. All verbs in the language begin with at least a consonant and end with a vowel. This syllable type is, therefore, very commonly found as the only syllable or, at least, the initial syllable in verbs. In addition, most V syllables are followed by CV syllables. Examples include the following:-

114. (a) /sa/ CV 'shoot'
- (b) /gbe₁/ CV 'dance'
- (c) /co₁/ CV 'steal'
- (d) /ɣa-re₂/ CV-CV 'share out, divide'
- (e) /kpo₁-kpo₁/ CV-CV 'worry'

- (f) /ɔ̣- mɔ́/ V-CV 'child'
 (g) /ạ-jɛ́/ V-CV 'woman'

3.7.2.3 THE CCV SYLLABLE

This syllable structure consists of two marginal consonant elements, C₁ and C₂, and the obligatory V element. As with the other syllable types, it can occur as a word or in any position in a word. However, there are collocational restrictions on the types of consonant segments found in this syllable type. The first consonant segment dominated by C₁ must be a [+cons, +grave] segment while the second consonant segment dominated by C₂ must be the voiced alveolar tap /r/. Consider the following examples.

115. a) bru CCV verb 'cut'
 b) kri CCV verb 'be late'
 c) mɾɛ CCV verb 'see'
 d) hra CCV verb 'scatter'
 e) ʋɾɛ CCV verb 'severe'
 f) à-φrɔ́ V-CCV noun 'argument'
 g) è₁-gbrù V-CCV noun 'male garments'
 h) é₁-brì V-CCV noun 'darkness'
 i) í-bre₁-he₁ V-CCV-CV noun 'mud'

Elugbe (1973) claims that this syllable type is actually underlyingly $C_1 V_1 C_2 V_2$ structure where V_1 and V_2 are of the same quality. He substantiates his claim by pointing out that it is possible to hear the full forms in the speech of some speakers. Thus, both of these forms are possible:

116. a) e_1bri VCCV and e_1biri VCVCV 'darkness'
 b) e_1kru VCCV and e_1kuru VCVCV 'family'
 c) e_1vri VCCV and e_1viri VCVCV 'oil'

He concludes that the fact that the CCV structure is predictable in that C_1 is always a [+grave] consonant and C_2 is always the alveolar tap [r] along with the fact that it is possible to hear the fuller forms of $C_1 V_1 C_2 V_2$, a recognition of a CCV structure for Urhobo would be uneconomical.

Olomukoro (1980) makes a similar claim but points out that a CCV structure is fast gaining ground and may soon be regarded as a phonemic syllable structure since the alternate forms in which a vowel is inserted between the two consonant segments is very infrequently heard.

One other point we find germane to the argument above is the behaviour of the CCV syllable when it occurs in a sequence. As mentioned in 3.4.2 above in our discussion of glide formation processes where two vowels occur in a sequence whether within or across morpheme boundaries such that V_1 is a [+High] vowel / $_{1,u,e_2,o_2}$ / and V_2 is any vowel, identical or nonidentical, V_1 usually undergoes glide formation to [j] in the

case of /i, e₂/ or [w] in the case of /u, o₂/. However, this rule is blocked if the [+High]vowel is preceded by the alveolar tap in a CCV syllable so that instead of glide formation we have vowel elision taking place with the [+High] vowel undergoing elision.

Compare the examples in 117 with those in 118 and 119 below:

- 117 a) bru + a₂ɲmá ---> [brəɲmá]
cut cloth 'cut a cloth'
- b) fru + íyó₁ ---> [fríyó]
snatch money 'snatch money'
- c) kri + úkó₁ ---> [krúkó]
be late back 'behind schedule'
- 118 a) fũ + amé₂ ---> [fũwámé] 'stop the flow of water
stop (example tap water)
extinguish water
- b) ru + írúó₁ ---> [rúwíró]
do work 'perform a job'
- c) sí + ɔ̀be₂ ---> [sɪ̀be]
write book 'write a book'
119. a) duvũ + o₂bɔ ---> [dúvóbɔ]
pierce hand 'pierce a hand'
- b) sívĩ + úré₁ ---> [sívúré]
drag wood 'argue about wood'

c) $\text{viri} + \text{ka}$ $\longrightarrow$ $[\text{viri}ka]$
 break maize 'break maize'

The verbs in 117 above which have a CCV structure behave like those in 119 which have a CVCV structure in that the vowels before the boundary are elided, even though they are high vowels and identical with those in 118 which undergo glide formation. This further attests to the fact that this CCV structure is suspect and may have been derived from a $C_1 V_1 C_2 V_2$ structure following the elision of V_1 .

Nevertheless, we propose that the time has now come to recognise a phonemic CCV syllable for Urhobo in which C_1 is a [+Cons, + Grave] segment while C_2 is the voiced alveolar tap $/r/$. This is because in no part of my present data were the alternate forms of $C_1 V_1 C_2 V_2$ heard or attested as possible forms by any of my informants. They were said to be unacceptable forms. A few very old people interviewed remember that the forms were in use when they were quite young but that no one used them these days. Since this is a synchronic study, we think that it would be worthwhile at this stage to set up a phonemic CCV structure for Urhobo to cater easily for a whole body of data with this type of syllable structure.

In addition, some other closely related Edoid languages with the same sequences have the CCV structure recognised in underlying representation in their systems. Donwa (1982) working on Isoko, also a Southwestern Edoid language in which similar sequences

along with similar restrictions exist, analyses them as CCV. The examples she cites in Isoko include the following:

- | | | | | |
|-----|----|--------|-------|----------------|
| 120 | a) | u-bro | V-CCV | 'half' |
| | b) | bru | CCV | 'cut' |
| | c) | o-gbru | V-CCV | 'male garment' |

Elugbe (1989a) in his analysis of Okpe and Uvwie, also two very closely related Southwestern Edoid languages recognises the CCV structure for similar sequences in similar environments as well. In addition, Omamor (1993) also recognises the CCV structure for similar sequences in her analysis of Okpe syllables. Her examples include:

- | | | | |
|-----|----|---------|--------------------------------------|
| 121 | a) | /bru/ | 'cut/go out to meet' |
| | b) | /e-krũ/ | 'family/relations' |
| | c) | /krũ/ | 'appear (of moon) survive (of baby)' |
| | d) | /hra/ | 'scatter around' |

All these examples taken from Isoko and Okpe are similarly rendered in Urhobo and there seems to be no point in analysing them as CCV in Isoko, Okpe and Uvwie and as CVCV in Urhobo. We therefore adopt a CCV syllable structure for all such sequences with two consonant segments following each other.

However, apart from the phonemic CCV syllable discussed above, there is also a phonetic [CCV] syllable which is derived from the application of glide formation rules followed by resyllabification. Usually, phonological processes such as vowel elision and

glide formation destroy existing syllables and this necessitates the application of resyllabification rules in order to create new well formed syllables. The application of glide formation rules create phonetic CCV syllables in which C_1 is any consonant segment and C_2 is one of the glides [j] or [w]. When the conditions for glide formation as stipulated in 3.4.2 above are satisfied, the vowel of the first syllable, V_1 , which is one of /i, u, e₂, o₂/ is realised as a glide such that /i, e₂/ are realised as the palatal approximant [j] and /u, o₂/ as the labial velar approximant [w]. Since all syllables in Urhobo must end with a vowel, the principle of resyllabification obligatorily applies. The second syllable which consists of only a vowel segment ceases to be a syllable and is annexed to the first syllable in order to provide the obligatory nucleus to make the syllable complete. Therefore, what is underlyingly a sequence of two syllables, CV-V, becomes realised as a single syllable with a consonant cluster [CCV] in which C_2 is either [j] or [w]. The following are a few more examples in addition to those given in 3.4.2 above.

122	a) mié ₁	CV-V	--->	[mjé]	CCV	'take'
	b) o ₁ -sió ₁	V-CV-V	--->	[ósjò]	V-CCV	'rain'
	c) ú-tié	V-CV-V	--->	[útjé]	V-CCV	'orange'
	d) gua	CV-V	--->	[gwa]	CCV	'drive'
	e) ɔ-rwè	V-CV-V	--->	[ɔrwè]	V-CCV	'mad person'
	f) é ₁ -muó ₁	V-CV-V	--->	[émwó]	V-CCV	'to carry'
	g) sí + ɔ be ₂	CV+V-CV	--->	[sjbè]	CCVCV	'write a book'

- h) $\text{s}\acute{\text{e}}_2 + \text{é}\acute{\text{e}}_2$ CV+V-CV $\rightarrow$ $[\text{s}\acute{\text{j}}\acute{\text{e}}\text{é}]$ CCVCV 'refuse a gift'
- i) $\text{k}\grave{\text{u}} + \text{é}_1\text{v}\grave{\text{r}}\text{i}$ CV+V-CCV $\rightarrow$ $[\text{kwe}\text{v}\text{r}\text{i}]$ CCVCCV 'pour oil'
- j) $\text{s}\grave{\text{o}}_2 + \text{ù}\acute{\text{e}}_1$ CV+V-CV $\rightarrow$ $[\text{sw}\grave{\text{ù}}\acute{\text{e}}]$ CCVCV 'sing a song'

The derivation of the phonetic CCV syllable may be summarised as in 123 below:

b)

In 123 above, the syllable node that dominated V_2 delinks after glide formation has applied and the V element reassociates with the first syllable as the nucleus of that syllable. In the case of vowel elision which affects V_1 , since the remaining C element dominated by that syllable node is not a well formed syllable, V_2 replaces the empty V_1 slot and this automatically results in the delinking of the syllable node dominating V_2 so that the two syllables in underlying representation also become one syllable. We illustrate with the derivations in 124(a) and (b) below:-

124 a) **Glide formation**

(i) **Underlying**

(ii) **by glide formation**

(iii) **by resyllabification and**

(iv) **Surface**

b) Vowel Elision

(I) Underlying

Representation

(ii) by Vowel Elision

(iii) by resyllabification and

delinking of syllable node

(iv) Surface

representation

[dɔ^ˈka^ˋ] 'buy maize'

Since the process of resyllabification is a predictable and obligatory occurrence, we shall not enter it as one of the stages in our derivations in subsequent sections of this work; it is taken for granted.

We shall now proceed to deal with tone in Urhobo. In the sections that follow, we shall only derive the tonal autosegment in our analyses. Wherever necessary, we shall

present morphemes in the underlying representation with their [ATR] vowel harmony and nasality status taken for granted.

CHAPTER FOUR

URHOBOTONE SYSTEM

4.1 INTRODUCTION

Pike (1948: 3) defines a tone language as one with 'lexically significant, contrastive but relative pitch on each syllable'. This definition has been criticised as being too wide by Welmers since in associating pitch with every syllable, Pike does not cater for tone languages in which the tone of a syllable may be conditioned by grammatical considerations. In addition, there are some tone languages that contain what has been referred to as 'toneless syllables' the pitch of which is conditioned by the preceding tone.

In an attempt to cater for the flaws in Pike's definition, Welmers (1959: 2) regards a tone language as one in which 'both pitch phonemes and segmental phonemes enter into the composition of at least some morphemes'. This definition emphasises the distinctive characteristics of a tone language as one in which some (of its) morphemes contain both segmental and pitch phonemes.

In general terms, however, tone refers to pitch differences usually at the level of the syllable and it is used to differentiate word meanings or to convey or signal grammatical distinction. It is a relative affair, that is, it is not something to be measured in absolute terms.

Two typologies of tone systems are recognised in the literature, namely, the register tone system and the contour tone system. According to Pike (1948), in a pure

register tone system, tonal contrasts consist of different levels of steady pitch heights which neither rise nor fall in their production. On the other hand, in a pure contour tone system, there are tones which are not level but either rise, fall, or rise and fall in their production. Most African languages are said to be register systems.

Welmers distinguishes between the discrete type and the terraced type of register tone systems. He says that in a discrete level tone system, each level tone is restricted to a relatively narrow range of absolute pitch (for a given speaker under given conditions) such that, for instance, a high tone near the end of the utterance or tone phrase is virtually the same absolute pitch as a high tone at the beginning of the phrase and it is higher than any mid tone in the phrase. Examples of languages with the discrete tone system include Yoruba and Isoko.

In a terraced level tone system, on the other hand, a high tone at the end of a tone phrase is on a lower pitch level than one at the beginning of the phrase. In this system, any non-initial low tone has a lowering effect on the following nonlow tone. What is significant in this system is not the absolute pitch of a syllable in a phrase, as one finds in a discrete level tone system but the pitches of nonlow syllables relative to preceding nonlow syllables. From the above statement, it follows that the first nonlow pitch in the phrase is the highest after which there may be successively lower nonlow pitches but never a return from a lower pitch to the same level as a preceding nonlow. This successive lowering of nonlow after a low is what is referred to as downstep. The main difference, therefore,

between a discrete level system and a terraced level system lies in the operation of downstep in the latter which creates a pitch terrace by lowering successive tone units in steps. A classical example of a terraced level tone system is said to be one in which there are two basic tones, high and low, and downstep (here refers to both downdrift and downstep). We shall now turn our attention to the Urhobo tone system.

4.2 PREVIOUS ANALYSES

Three notable linguists have done significant work on the Urhobo tone system. They are: Kelly (1969a), Welmers (1969, 1973) and Elugbe (1973, 1977, 1989a). We shall present the main points of their works while raising questions wherever necessary.

In discussing the typology of the Urhobo tone system, all three linguists agree that Urhobo is a terraced level tone system with two basic tones, namely, the low tone and the high tone, as well as two gliding tones, namely, high - low (falling) and low - high (rising) which are usually derived from the level tones. They all also recognise a third pitch which is found only after the high tone and the status of this third pitch is one of the main points of disagreement between them. While Kelly (1969a), Welmers (1969) and Elugbe (1973, 1989a) recognise this third level as a non-automatic downstep, Welmers (1973) and Elugbe (1977) regard it as a mid tone. In what follows, we shall show that it is a downstep and not a mid tone.

The second point of disagreement is a follow-up from the first and it concerns whether or not the phenomenon of 'terracing' or downstepping of high tones within a

phrase in statements is found. Kelly (1969a) claims that it is found such that after a sequence of 'high - low', a succeeding high tone is lower in pitch than the original high tone while after 'high - downstep plus high' a succeeding high is realised on the same pitch as the downstep plus high syllable. However, both Welmers and Elugbe state clearly that the phenomenon is not found. According to Welmers (1969: 88), a nonlow tone lower than an immediately preceding nonlow is heard only in utterance final position (that is, before a pause), not within a phrase. In a similar vein, Elugbe (1989a:73) states that after a downstep, it is possible to go back to high within the same tone phrase. In this work, we shall show that terracing within a phrase is what occurs in Urhobo, making it a typical terraced level type of tone system.

A third phenomenon that will be examined more closely is that of final (low) tone raising said to occur in statements. Elugbe (1973, 1977, 1989a) attests to the phenomenon and claims that a final low tone immediately preceded by a high tone is raised. According to him (1973: 150) 'this is predictable and ... in disyllabic nouns has the effect of blurring the distinction between high - low and high - downstep nouns,. In this work, we claim that the phenomenon is attested only in statements that end with a verb.

4.3 THE PRESENT STUDY

4.3.1 METHODOLOGY

Data was collected orally from a total of thirteen Informants. There was one informant each for eight of the ten dialects studied; these are - Agbarha, Avwaka, Idjerhe, Olomu, Orogun, Udu, Ughelli and Ughievwen. In the case of the other two, there were two informants for Agbõn while there were three for Agbarho including this writer/investigator who is herself a native speaker of Agbarho. The reason for the increase in the number of informants in Agbõn and Agbarho dialects is that Agbrho is our focus dialect for this work and also the one that has been studied by Elugbe while both Kelly and Welmers have based their work on the Agbõn dialect. Agbõn is also the closest to the central Agbarho dialect. It was necessary to have more idiolects in order to verify some claims that have been made by the various researchers.

The instruments used for collecting the data were a cassette player/recorder to which audio cassettes were fitted. These were used to record the pronunciation of various items of data.

Data for this work included the Ibadan 400 - Wordlist, 300 randomly selected additional words from the language, 200 varied syntactic patterns and five short stories.

For processing our data the following instruments were utilised:

- i) a computer to which were fitted a microphone and a tone box. The raw data was transmitted via the microphone to the tone box which analysed

the tone levels and the computer produced instrumental tracings of the tokens presented as Figures 7 - 11, 15, 17 - 19.

ii) a Computerised Speech Laboratory (CSL) model 4300B Software version

5x. The facilities used in this model include:

- a) a loudspeaker
- b) a microphone
- c) a keyboard with a monitor
- d) a video copy processor
- e) a photocopier.

In this system, the host computer receives the raw data and shows it on the monitor; the Computerised Speech Laboratory gives whatever programme is required, for instance, spectrogram, pitch, frequency, etc. The video copy processor copies whatever is monitored and processed by the CSL on the screen while the photocopier produces a copy of the instrumentally processed data. The tracings are attached as Figures 1 - 5, 12 - 14 and 16.

Since our study is based on tone, our selection of programmes was limited to only those relevant to our work. The tone levels are measured in hertz based on frequency readings by the cursor. Thus, when we have a reading of 185, we mean 185Hertz. It should be pointed out that since the instruments are extremely sensitive and the human speech act is subject to a number of conditioning factors such as the pitch of the

individual speaker, physical as well as emotional factors surrounding the speech event, we cannot set a definite pitch range for particular tones. Rather, we consider each utterance individually and set the pitch level of the initial tone, be it a low tone or a high tone, as the reference point for that particular tone phrase with which we compare following pitch levels. Thus, as we shall see from the figures attached, a low tone may begin at 165Hertz in some cases while the same low tone may begin at 220 Hertz in some other cases. The native speaker recognises both as the low tone. The high tone also varies from as low as 207 Hertz to 330 Hertz. What is important is the pitch of a particular tone relative to others within the same tone phrase. There are no absolute pitch levels for any tone. However, within a tone phrase, we regard a variation of 10 Hertz between identical tones in a sequence as non-significant and therefore on the same pitch because pitches within this range were not differentiated by the ordinary ear.

In what follows, we shall deal more with statements which we consider to be the basic utterance. Other structures such as questions or exclamations would be clearly specified whenever they are used.

Below is a distinctive feature matrix for Urhobo level tones:

125.

	/	\
HI	+	-
LO	-	+

The downstep and contour tones are not represented in 125 above. A [+HI] level tone is redundantly [-LO] while a [+LO] level tone is redundantly [-HI]. Tones would be mapped onto tone bearing units in the autosegmental fashion thus:

In all cases, tones are mapped onto the V slots on the CV tier from which they are linked onto the segments dominated by the V slot. Only segments dominated by the V slot (that is, vowel segments) bear tone in this language. There are no syllabic consonants. It should be noted here that when a tone is delinked due to some phonological processes such as vowel elision or glide formation, it is delinked from the V

slot and is assumed to float and unless it relinks, it does not get any phonetic realisation. As a result, in our derivations later, we may not reflect the stage at which a delinked tone floats.

4.3.2 SUMMARY OF THE TYPOLOGY OF URHOBO TONE SYSTEM

We make the following claims about the Urhobo tone system based on our findings.

- (a) there are two basic tones, namely, high (H) and low (L) and two gliding tones, low-high (LH) and high-low (HL) which are actually sequences of the two basic tones: there are no phonemic contour tones;
- (b) there is a phonemic (non-automatic) downstep which is found only after the high tone and is not synchronically traceable to a lost low tone;
- (c) the non-automatic downstep sets a pitch ceiling within the tone phrase so that no other tone can significantly go higher than its pitch level;
- (d) there is automatic downstep so that a high tone which is preceded by a nonhigh tone (that is, a low or a downstep) is realised a step lower than a preceding high tone.

We shall present our arguments in support of these claims in the following sections.

4.4 THE BASIC TONES

4.4.1 INTRODUCTION

The basic tones in Urhobo are the low tone and the high tone. As will become obvious from the instrumentally processed data, Urhobo tones are generally realised on a relatively high pitch which tends to give a wrong perception of the tones at a casual glance; the true position is clearer only with a more attentive perception. If we compare the high and low tones of Urhobo and Ghotuṣ (Elugbe 1985) as produced instrumentally, we find that whereas an initial low tone in Urhobo is realised on a pitch of between 180 Hertz and 220 Hertz, a low tone in Ghotuṣ is realised on a pitch of between 90 Hertz and 100 Hertz. Similarly, an initial high tone in Urhobo is realised on a pitch of between 210 and 330 Hertz whereas in Ghotuṣ it is from about 120 Hertz. Let us briefly here present some examples from both languages:

127. Urhobo examples.

a) ̀̀ d́́ ̀̀ń́ ---> [̀̀ d́́ ̀̀ń́] 'he bought yam'

L H L H L H H

he bought yarm 190 225 225 (Fig. 4)

b) é́́wǔ́́ ré́́ àjè̀̀ ---> [é́́wǔ́́ rá́́ jè̀̀] 'a woman's dress'

H L H L L H L H L

dress AM woman 280 198 235 172 (Fig. 5)

128 Ghotuo examples (taken from Elugbe 1985: 10) as Figs 2a and 2b).

a) [ə̀sə́ sómà̀] 'a cricket from Oma'

90 110 125 115

(Fig. 6a)

b) [sɔ́ kpà̀] 'about a cock'

132 80

(Fig. 6b)

The two basic tones mentioned above can be found in any position in an utterance - initially, medially or finally.

4.4.2 THE LOW TONE

We make the following claims about the low tone based on our findings:

- (i) the low tone may be followed by another low or a nonlow tone. In the following examples, the low tone is shown in the citation form of some nouns and in different positions in statements:

129. a) ɔ̀kɔ̀ --> [òkɔ̀] 'a boat, canoe'

L L [- -]

b) ò₁dìbò₁ --> [òdìbò] 'a slave, servant'

L L L [- - -]

c) ìrìbó₁ --> [ìrìbó] 'pepper'

L H H [- - -]

d) ɛ̀rākō̃₂ --> [ɛ̀rākō̃] 'dog'

L H L [- - -]

e) `e₁gbè₁dé₁ --> [ègbèdè] 'needle'
 L L H [- - -]

f) ó₁nó₁gbò₁ --> [ónógbò] 'pussy cat'
 H H L [- - -]

g) ó₁dìbó₁ --> [ódìbò] 'banana'
 H L H [- - -]

h) `ò<sub>2</sub>b`ò ré `a<sub>1</sub>má ré `òvìè₁ r é `aje₂ --->
 LL H LH H LLL H LL
 hand AM cloth AM king AM woman

[`òb`ò rá₁má róv₁jè rājè]

 L L H H L H L

'tail-end of the queen's wrapper'

- ii) Within a tone phrase, the pitch of the low tone is highest in utterance initial position. From our instrumental recordings the low tone in its realisation varies between 180 Hz and 220 Hz. in this position and is higher than any other low tone within the same tone phrase. Let us consider the following examples:

- 130 a) $\text{'o}_2\text{b}^{\text{c}}$ ----> $[\text{'o b}^{\text{c}}]$ 'hand'
 L L 185 180 (Fig. 7)
- b) $\text{'o}_2\text{k}^{\text{c}}$ ----> $[\text{'o k}^{\text{c}}]$ 'boat, canoe'
 L L 180 180 (Fig. 8)
- c) $\text{'o}_1\text{dib}^{\text{c}}$ ----> $[\text{'o d i b}^{\text{c}}]$ 'slave, servant'
 L L L 170 170 170 (Fig. 9)
- d) $\text{'usi}^{\text{c}}\text{na}$ ----> $[\text{'u si n a}^{\text{c}}]$ 'the fame'
 L L L L 170 170 170 (Fig. 10)
- e) $\text{c}^{\text{b}}\text{o}_2\text{c}^{\text{b}}\text{na} \text{ d}^{\text{e}} \text{o}'_2\text{t}^{\text{c}} \text{c}^{\text{b}}\text{na}$ ----> $[\text{c}^{\text{b}}\text{o} \text{n}^{\text{a}} \text{d}^{\text{o}}\text{t}^{\text{c}}\text{n}^{\text{a}}]$
 LL LLH H!H L L 185 190 185 208 185 147
 doctor the bought land the (Fig. 11)
 'the doctor bought the (parcel of) land'
- f) $\text{c}^{\text{b}} \text{d}^{\text{e}} \text{c}^{\text{b}} \text{n}^{\text{e}}$ ----> $[\text{c}^{\text{b}}\text{d}^{\text{e}}\text{c}^{\text{b}}\text{n}^{\text{e}}]$ 'he bought yam'
 L H L H 190 225 230 (Fig 4)
 he bought yam.
- g) $\text{'o}_2\text{c}^{\text{e}} \text{r}^{\text{e}} \text{a}^{\text{m}}\text{e}_2$ --> $[\text{'o c}^{\text{e}} \text{r}^{\text{a}} \text{m}^{\text{e}}]$
 L H H L L 200 230 230 170
 pot AM water 'water pot' (Fig. 12)

h) `òbò ré `aḡmá ré `òviè ré `ájè₂ --->

LL H L H H LLL H LL

hand AM cloth AM king AM woman

[`òbò r`aḡmá r`óvjè r`ájè]

220 215 245 240 245 185 210 165

'tail-end of the queen's wrapper'

(Fig. 13)

The variation in the pitch of the initial low tone in each case can only be attributable to the speech process itself. This is because a consideration of the type of consonant following the low tone or the length of the utterance does not lead to any useful generalizations. We find that the pitch of the low tone surrounding both voiced and voiceless consonants may be the same as examples 130 (c) and (d) show. Moreover, whereas 130(e) which begins at 185Hz has six syllables (phonetic realisation only), 130 (g) with only four syllables begins the low tone at 200 Hz. It should have been expected that the longer the tone phrase the higher the realisation of the pitch of the low tone. We must point out here though that these variations mentioned are not distinguished by the ordinary ear neither are they noticeable outside instrumental analysis. This is more the reason why we have to handle tone groups individually and deal with tones relative to one another within a tone phrase. The variations have no phonological relevance.

- iii) Consecutive low tones are realised on about the same pitch as the examples above show clearly irrespective of whether they are within the same word boundary or not.
- iv) A low tone in a H - L - H sequence has a lowering effect on the pitch of the second high tone. Consider the following example:

131. $\acute{e}_1 \text{ w}\ddot{u} \text{ r}\acute{e} \text{ } \grave{a}\text{j}\grave{e}_2 \text{---> } [\acute{e}\ddot{w}\ddot{u} \text{ } \bar{r}\acute{a}\text{j}\grave{e}]$
 H L H L L 280 198 135 172 (Fig.5)
 dress AM woman 'a woman's dress'

We shall return to this when we deal with downdrift in section 4.5.

- (v) As would have become obvious from the examples in 130 e, f, g, h and from 131 above, the low tone is also progressively lowered as the statement progresses. We shall also return to this point when we deal with downdrift.
- (vi) Quite often, a low tone which occurs in underlying representation in the environment of a nonlow tone may not survive to surface structure if the nonlow is set afloat as a result of some phonological processes. The relinking of a floating nonlow almost always means automatic delinking for the low and instead of resulting in downstep or downglide for the nonlow, the delinked low tone has no phonetic effect on the surviving nonlow. Let us consider a few examples:

132 a) $\overset{\text{H}}{\text{ɔ}} \overset{\text{H}}{\text{dɛ}} \overset{\text{L}}{\text{ɔ}} \overset{\text{H}}{\text{nɛ}}$ --> $[\overset{\text{H}}{\text{ɔ}} \overset{\text{H}}{\text{dɔ}} \overset{\text{H}}{\text{nɛ}}]$
 L H L H L H H
 he bought yam
 [_ - -]
 190 225 230
 'he bought yam'

(Fig. 4)

b) $\overset{\text{H}}{\text{úkpe}}_1 \overset{\text{H}}{\text{ré}} \overset{\text{L}}{\text{ò}}_1 \overset{\text{H}}{\text{huó}}_1$ --> $[\overset{\text{H}}{\text{úkpe}} \overset{\text{L}}{\text{róxwò}}$
 HL H LHH H L H H
 bed AM person
 'a persons bed'

c) $\overset{\text{H}}{\text{í}} \overset{\text{H}}{\text{ò}}_1 \overset{\text{H}}{\text{ré}} \overset{\text{L}}{\text{ùdì}}$ --> $[\overset{\text{H}}{\text{í}} \overset{\text{DS}}{\text{ò}} \overset{\text{H}}{\text{rùdì}}]$
 H !H H LL H DS H L
 'money AM drink'
 'money for drink'

We derive 132(a) within the autosegmental framework in 133 below:

ii)

iii)

iv)

The examples above show that the coalescing of a high tone and a low tone following the elision of a vowel and the boundary that existed between them does not produce a downstep as one would find in tone systems such as Edo (Amayo 1976), Ghotuo (Elugbe, 1985), Emai (Egbokhare, 1990) which are Edoid languages as well. Instead, the relinking of the high tone results in automatic delinking for the low tone

When we compare the string in 131 with those in 132 and 134, we find that the low tone has a lowering effect on a following high tone only if the low tone is present in surface structure. Thus, whereas the second high tone in each string in 131(a) and 132(b) is realised on a lower pitch than the preceding high tone because there is a low tone in surface structure, in 132(a) and (c) as well as those in 134 where the low tone is not phonetically realised, it does not affect the pitch of the surviving high tone. It shows, from the examples, that downdrift in this language applies very late in the grammar, possibly to only surface forms. We shall return to this under downdrift.

- vii) Just as a delinked low tone does not have an effect on a following high, it also does not have an effect on a following low tone. This means that a low tone which follows a lost low tone is realised on about the same pitch as a low tone which is not preceded by a lost low. Let us consider the following examples:

136.	(a)	ḡdɛ́	ḡkà	ḡnà	---	>	[ḡdɔ́kà nǎ́]	
		L	H	H	L	L	210 265 175 172	
		she bought maize the					'she bought maize'	
	(b)	é ₁ wǔ	rɛ́	àjè ₂	---	>	[éwǔ rājè]	
		H	L	H	L	L	270 195 230 175	
		dress AM woman					'a woman's dress' (Fig. 5)	

In 136(a) above, the last two low tones are realised on the same pitch although a low tone that existed between them has been elided. In the tone systems of Ghotuo and Emai, such a lost low tone would have caused a following low tone to downstep. Compare the examples above with those in 137(a) and (b) below taken from Elugbe (1985:7) (They are Elugbe's examples 5a and 5c respectively).

137.	(a)	sɛ́	ɔkpa	---	>	sɔkpa	
		H	L	L		H !L	
		of cock					'of/about a cock'

(b)	sẹ ọ sẹ	ṣ ọ sẹ
	H L M	H M
	of cricket	'of/about a cricket'

In the Ghotuo examples, the downstepped low and the downstepped mid are clearly traceable to the lost low tone. This is not the case in Urhobo where the low tone must be present in the surface structure to cause automatic downstep. We return to this in section 4.5.

4.4.3 THE ISSUE OF FINAL LOW (TONE) RAISING

Our discussion so far would tend to give the impression that there is no final low (tone) raising in Urhobo as has been claimed to occur by Welmers (1969) and Elugbe (1973, 1977, 1989a). According to Elugbe (1973:150) 'a final low tone immediately preceded by a high tone is upstepped', a statement re-echoed in Elugbe (1989a:74) 'final low tones are raised in statements'. However, based on our data, although there is evidence of final low tone raising in statements, it is not a general principle. Two conditions must be met, namely:

- (i) the preceding high tone is a tense tomorph, and
- (ii) the final low tone is not part of an object.

If either or both of these conditions fails to apply, final low tone raising is blocked. In the examples in 138 below, the final low tones borne by the past tense suffix (138 a and b) and the verb stem (138 c and d) are raised to about mid level in the phonetic realisation:

138. (a) $\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{ɔ}} \text{ d}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{ɛ}} \text{ r}\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{e}}_2$ ---> [$\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{ɔ}} \text{ d}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{ɛ}} \text{ r}\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{e}}$]
 L H L
 he bought suffix

- (b) $\text{m}\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{e}}_2 \text{ f}\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{ɔ}}_1 \overset{\text{́}}{\text{ɔ}} \text{ r}\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{e}}_2$ ---> [$\text{m}\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{e}} \text{ f}\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{ɔ}}_1 \overset{\text{́}}{\text{ɔ}} \text{ r}\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{e}}$]
 L L H L
 I washed suffix

- (c) $\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{ɔ}} \overset{\text{́}}{\text{ɔ}} \text{ d}\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{e}}$ ---> [$\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{ɔ}} \overset{\text{́}}{\text{ɔ}} \text{ d}\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{e}}$]
 L H L
 he present buy

- (d) $\text{m}\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{e}}_2 \text{ e}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{e}}_2 \text{ f}\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{ɔ}}_1 \overset{\text{́}}{\text{ɔ}}$ ---> [$\text{m}\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{e}} \text{ e}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{e}} \text{ f}\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{ɔ}}_1 \overset{\text{́}}{\text{ɔ}}$]
 L H L L
 I present wash

However, in the examples in 139 below, low tone raising is blocked because the final low tone is part of the object.

139. (a) $\text{m}\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{e}}_2 \text{ d}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{ɛ}} \text{ e}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{e}}_1 \text{ w}\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{u}}$ ---> [$\text{m}\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{e}} \text{ d}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{ɛ}} \text{ e}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{e}}_1 \text{ w}\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{u}}$]
 L H H L
 I bought dress

 L H L 'I bought a dress'
- (b) $\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{ɔ}} \text{ f}\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{ɔ}}_1 \overset{\text{́}}{\text{ɔ}} \text{ e}_1 \text{ gbru}$ ---> [$\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{ɔ}} \text{ f}\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{ɔ}}_1 \overset{\text{́}}{\text{ɔ}} \text{ e}_1 \text{ gbru}$]
 L L H L L
 he washed garments

 L L H L

(c) ̀̀ ̀́ ̀̀ ̀̀ ̀̀ ̀̀ ̀̀ ̀̀ ̀̀ ̀̀
 L H L L L
 she present buy drink

→ [̀̀ ̀́ ̀̀ ̀̀ ̀̀ ̀̀]
 [- - - -]

The instrumental tracings presented in Figs. 1, 11 and 14 also show that the final low tone borne by nouns is not raised in statements. The situation in Urhobo is different from that in Isoko, a closely related Southwestern Edoid language with a discrete level type of tone system (Elugbe 1977, 1989a; Donwa 1982). In Isoko, the phenomenon of final low raising is evident in the citation forms of nouns and in virtually all statements irrespective of whether they end with objects or not, a situation also confirmed by this researcher. Compare the examples in 140 with those in 141 below.

140. Isoko examples

(a) ̀̀ ̀́ ̀́ ̀̀ ̀̀ ̀̀ ̀̀ ̀̀ ̀̀ ̀̀
 L H H L
 he bought maize

→ [̀̀ ̀́ ̀́ ̀̀ ̀̀ ̀̀ ̀̀ ̀̀]
 [- - - -]
 (final low raised to mid)

(b) ̀̀ ̀́ ̀́
 L H
 he bought

→ [̀̀ ̀́ ̀́]
 [- -]
 (No suffix attached to the verb)

141. Urhobo realisations:

(a) ɔ́ dɛ́ ɔ́ kà

L H H L

he bought maize

-->

[ɔ́ dɔ́ kà]

[- -]

(No final low raising)

(b) ɔ́ dɛ́ rɛ̀

L H L

he bought suffix

-->

[ɔ́ dɛ́ rɛ̀]

[- -]

(Final low (of suffix) raised).

4.4.4 THE HIGH TONE

We make the following claims about the high tone in Urhobo based on our data:

- (i) The high tone may be followed in a sequence by a low or a nonlow. The nonlow tone may be another high tone on the same pitch or one which is a little lower than the first and which we recognise as a non-automatic downstep as would be explained later. In the following examples, the high tone is shown in the citation form of some nouns and in different positions in some statements.

142. (a) ɔ́ kà

--->

[ɔ́ kà] 'maizè'

H L

[- -]

(b) ɔ́ nɔ́ gbò

--->

[ɔ́ nɔ́ gbò] 'pussy cat'

H H L

[- - -]

(c) $\acute{o}'s\acute{e}$ $\rightarrow$ [$\acute{o}s\bar{e}$] 'father'
 H ! H [- -]

(d) $\acute{a}g\acute{o}_2g\acute{o}_2$ $\rightarrow$ [$\acute{a}g\acute{o}g\acute{o}$] 'bell'
 H H H [- - -]

(e) $\acute{o}_1r\acute{e}_1r\acute{e}_1r\acute{e}\acute{e}_2n\acute{e}$ $\rightarrow$ [$\acute{o}r\acute{e}r\acute{e}r\acute{e}n\bar{e}$]
 H H ! H H L H [- - - -]
 town AM yams H H M M M

'a town of yams'

(f) $\acute{a}g\acute{o}_2g\acute{o}_2v\acute{e}\acute{i}r\acute{i}b\acute{o}_1r\acute{e}r\acute{g}b\acute{a}$ $\rightarrow$ [$\acute{a}g\acute{o}g\acute{o}v\acute{i}r\acute{i}b\acute{o}r\acute{g}b\acute{a}$]
 H H H H L H H H H H [- - - - -]
 bell and pepper AM hero H H H H H H H H

'a hero's bell and pepper'

(g) $w\acute{o}f\acute{a}\acute{e}v\acute{e}_2$ $\rightarrow$ [$w\acute{o}f\acute{e}v\acute{e}$]
 L H L H [- - -]
 you flogged goat L H H

'you flogged a goat'

(ii) Within a tone phrase, an initial high tone is realised on a higher level than elsewhere in a statement. Consider the instrumental evidence for the following examples:

143. (a) $\acute{u}r\acute{e}_1 \ r\acute{e} \ \grave{c}b\grave{o}_2 \ \grave{c}n\grave{a} \ \acute{v}\acute{o}_1 \ \acute{c}\acute{r}\acute{c} \ \dashrightarrow \ [\acute{u}r\acute{e} \ r\acute{c}b\grave{o} \ n\grave{a} \ \acute{v}\acute{c}\acute{r}\acute{c}]$
 HH H L L L L H H !H 215 220 215 150 160 190 175
 tree AM doctor the has honey
 'the doctor's tree has honey'

(Fig. 15)

(b) $\acute{i}\acute{y}\acute{o}_1 \ r\acute{e} \ \acute{u}r\acute{e}_1 \ r\acute{e} \ \acute{c}\acute{g}\acute{c} \ r\acute{e} \ \grave{a}j\grave{e}_2 \ \grave{c}n\grave{a} \ \dashrightarrow$
 H !H H H H H !H H L L L L
 money AM wood AM in-law AM woman the
 [$\acute{i}\acute{y}\acute{o} \ r\acute{u}r\acute{e} \ r\acute{c}g\acute{c} \ r\acute{a}j\grave{e} \ n\grave{a}]$
 260 220 220 218 220 185 185 150 150 (Fig. 16)
 'money for the wood of the woman's in-law'

(c) $\acute{e}_1w\grave{u} \ r\acute{e} \ \grave{a}j\grave{e}_2 \ \dashrightarrow \ [\acute{e}w\grave{u} \ r\acute{a}j\grave{e}]$
 H L H L L 270 195 230 175
 dress AM woman
 'a woman's dress'

(Fig. 5)

iii) As the examples in 143 above show clearly, after a low tone or a non-automatic downstep, a following high pitch is realised on a lower pitch than a preceding high tone and a terracing effect is thus created. After a High-Low sequence, a succeeding high tone is lower than a preceding high while after a High -Downstep

sequence, a succeeding high tone is realised on the same pitch as the downstep level. Besides, the first downstep in the tone group sets a ceiling for all other tones such that no other tone rises beyond its level. This is further evidence for our recognising this 'lower than high' pitch as a downstep and not a mid tone (cf example 143b (Fig. 16))

- (iv) As we mentioned earlier during our discussion of the low tone, a low tone which exists in underlying representation but gets deleted from the surface representation due to some phonological reasons, such as vowel elision or glide formation, has no effect on the pitch of the following high tone. Example 127(a) is reproduced here as 144 (a) for easy reference followed by a few more examples.

144.	(a)	ò dé ò né	---	[ò dóné]	
		L H L H		L H H	
		he bought yam			
		'he bought yam'		190 225 230	(Fig. 4)
	(b)	úkpè ré òhuó	---	[úkpè róxwó]	
		H L H L H H		H L H H	
		bed AM person			
				'a person's bed'	

- (c) $fí$ $úko_1$ ---> [f j $ú$ k $ó$]
 L H H
 throw cup
 'throw a cup'

 (Imperative sentence)
- (d) $fí$ $á$ $má$ ---> [f j $á$ m $á$]
 H L H
 throw cloth
 'threw a cloth'

In example 144(a) the two final high tones in the surface form are realised on the same pitch even though in the underlying structure there was a low tone intervening between them that became lost due to vowel elision. Although it was the high tone that was initially set afloat, its relinking resulted in the delinking of the intervening low tone. All the other examples in 144 show the same occurrence.

- (v) Consecutive high tones are realised on the same pitch with no significant raising or lowering. Again, the examples in 143(a) and (b) show this clearly. In 143(a) there are ^{three} initial high tones while in 143(b) three high tones follow the first downstep. In each case, the first pitch in the sequence is maintained by the others that follow it.

- (vi) The high tone may be upstepped by the presence of a question tomorph in an utterance. The question tomorph is a floating low tone which gets segmentalised on the final vowel segment of the statement form. If the statement ends on a high tone, the result is the creation of a HL contour but if the statement ends on a low tone, we do not get a downglide as one would expect and as happens in Emai (Egbokhare, 1990). Rather, the effect of the segmentalisation of this tomorph onto a statement that already ends on a low tone is that the immediately preceding high tone is upstepped, leaving the pitch of the final low tone unaffected. We can verify our claim by comparing Figs. 1 and 3 which we reproduce as 145(a) and (b) respectively.

145.	(a)	é̂sɛ̀₂ dɛ́	ɔ́kà	---	[é̂sɛ̀ d̄ɔ́kà]
		H L H H L			H L H L
		Name bought maize			325 200 270 165
		'Ese bought maize'			(Fig. 1) (statement)
	(b)	é̂sɛ̀₂ dɛ́	ɔ́kà ʼ	---	[é̂sɛ̀ d̄ɔ́kà]
		H L H H L	Ⓛ		H L H L
		Name bought maize Question			295 200 325 160
		'did Ese buy maize?'			(Fig. 3) (Question)

In 145(b) the pitch of the tone preceding the final low tone is significantly higher than an initial high tone or even the same high tone in an identical position in 145(a). We

believe that this is an intonational factor employed to differentiate a statement that ends on a low tone from its corresponding question form. Since the final low tone of the object merges with the low question tomorph, the immediately preceding high tone is upstepped so that the final low tone can start dropping from this elevated height. This way, the auditorily perceived downglide is maintained, even though the final low tone does not go lower in pitch than in the statement form. The upstepped high pitch is, however not a significant level in this language.

4.4.5 CONTOUR TONES

Two types of contour tones are found in this language, namely the rising tone, LH, and the falling tone, HL. As has been mentioned earlier, they are derived from sequences of the two basic tones borne by a single vowel segment. They usually result from the segmentalisation of floating tones onto vowel segments that already bear non-identical tones. Consider the following examples:

146. (a) $\overset{\text{L}}{\text{a}}\overset{\text{L}}{\text{b}}\overset{\text{H}}{\text{é}}\overset{\text{L}}{\text{nè}}$ $\rightarrow$ [$\overset{\text{L}}{\text{a}}\overset{\text{H}}{\text{é}}\overset{\text{L}}{\text{nè}}$]
 L L H L [$\text{— } \text{J } \text{—}$]
 hands four L L H L 'four hands'
- (b) $\overset{\text{H}}{\text{é}}\overset{\text{L}}{\text{kà}}\overset{\text{H}}{\text{í}}\overset{\text{L}}{\text{vè}}$ $\rightarrow$ [$\overset{\text{H}}{\text{é}}\overset{\text{L}}{\text{kí}}\overset{\text{L}}{\text{vè}}$]
 H L H L [$\text{— } \text{J } \text{—}$]
 maize two H LHL 'two maize'

(c) $\acute{\text{c}}\grave{\text{a}} \text{ d}\acute{\text{e}} \text{ a} \grave{\text{g}} \text{ m}\acute{\text{a}}$ $\rightarrow$ [$\hat{\text{c}} \text{ d}\acute{\text{a}}\text{g}\text{m}\acute{\text{a}}$]
 H L H L H $\left[\begin{array}{c} \backslash \quad - \quad - \\ \hline \end{array} \right]$
 he future buy cloth 'he must buy a cloth'

(d) $\grave{\text{c}} \text{ d}\acute{\text{e}} \text{ \textcircled{g}} \text{ n}\acute{\text{e}}$ $\rightarrow$ [$\grave{\text{c}} \text{ d}\acute{\text{e}} \text{ n}\hat{\text{e}}$]
 L H L H (L) $\left[\begin{array}{c} - \quad \backslash \\ \hline \end{array} \right]$
 he bought yam Question 'Did he buy yam?'

In 146 (a) and (b) above, the final low tone of the noun, which is set afloat following the elision of the vowel segment that bore it, is relinked onto the adjacent vowel of the numeral which already bears a high tone, creating a LH sequence. In 146 (c), the future morpheme gets deleted but its low tone survives and is relinked on the vowel of the subject pronoun which already bears a high tone, resulting in a HL sequence. As mentioned in 4.4.4 above, the low question tomorph gets segmentalised on the final vowel segment of the statement form resulting in a HL sequence if the statement already ends with a high tone, as in 146 (d) above.

4.5 DOWNSTEP

Downstep is a term usually used to refer to both the automatic downstep (downdrift) and the non-automatic downstep (phonemic downstep). We shall consider them in some detail in the following sections.

c) ɔ̀₂ b̀ r̄ é ʔ́ ɔ́ m̄ á r̄ é ɔ̀₁ v̄ ī ē₁ r̄ é ʔ́ ā j̄ ē₂ →

LL H L H H LLL H L L

hand AM cloth AM king AM woman

220 215 245 240 245 185 210 165 (Fig. 13)

'tail-end of the queen's wrapper'

d) ú r̄ é₁ r̄ é ʔ́ b̀ ò₂ ò n̄ à v̄ ó₁ ʔ́ ʔ́ ʔ́ →

HH H L L L L H H !H

tree AM doctor the bas honey

215 220 215 160 160 190 175 (Fig. 15)

H H H L L H DS

e) é s̄ ē₂ d̄ é é₁ b̄ o₁ r̄ é ʔ́ k̄ a →

HL HH L H HL

Name bought sack AM maize

'Ese bought a sack of maize'

f) ʔ́ s̄ á ɔ̀₂ b̀ ʔ́ r̄ é ú z̄ o₁ →

L H L L H HL

he shot hand AM antelope'

'he shot an antelope's hand'

In addition, in a language that has both the automatic and the non-automatic downstep, the presence of the non-automatic downstep in a phonological string also creates a terracing effect because the downstep sets a ceiling on the pitch of the following high tone which is then realised on the same pitch as the non-automatic downstep. Thus, in a sequence with a number of non-automatic downsteps, the high tones are progressively lowered to reflect the pitch of the immediately preceding downstep. Let us consider an example:

149. ɔ́:ɡɔ́ ɔ̀nà dá ɔ̀tɔ́ rɛ́ ɔ́:ɲɔ́ ɔ̀nà --->
 H!H LL H H!H H H!H LL

in-law the drank bottom AM honey the

280 240 190 240 210 210 180 160

(fig. 18)

'the in-law drank the dregs of the honey'

We shall return to this in the next section.

In Urhobo, automatic downstep is blocked if the intervening low tone or the non-automatic downstep is deleted from the phonetic string. Below are some examples:

150. a) ɔ́ dɛ́ ɔ̀nɛ́ --->
 L H L H

[ɔ́ dɔ́nɛ́]

he bought yam

'he bought yam'

- b) $m\grave{e}_2 f\grave{o} r\grave{o} a\grave{h}m\acute{a}$ → [$m\grave{e} f\grave{o} r\grave{o} a\grave{h}m\acute{a}$]
 L L H L H [- - -]
 I wahsed cloth 'I washed a cloth'
- c) $\acute{o}g\acute{o} + \acute{o}_1 b\acute{i}e_1 b\grave{i}$ → [$\acute{o}g\acute{o}b\acute{j}e\grave{b}\grave{i}$]
 H! H H H H L [- - -]
 in-law black H H H L
 'a black in-law'
- d) $\acute{o}s\acute{e} + \acute{o}v\grave{a}v\grave{a}r\grave{e}$ → [$\acute{o}s\acute{o}v\grave{a}v\grave{a}r\grave{e}$]
 H! H H H L L [- - -]
 father red H H H L L
 'a light-complexioned father'

In 150 (a) and (b) above, the low tone of the noun prefix is deleted following the relinking of the high tone of the verb whose vowel segment has been elided. With the deletion of the low tone, we notice that the high tone of the verb which is relinked on the prefix of the noun is realised on the same pitch as the high tone of the noun stem, as if there was never an intervening low tone. Similarly, in 150 (c) and (d), the non-automatic downstep which was borne by the vowel of the noun stem is deleted along with the vowel that bore it and the result is that the high tone of the noun prefix and the initial high tones of the attributive modifier are realised on the same pitch as though there was no non-automatic downstep between them in the underlying representation. Thus, in this

language, a low tone and a phonemic downstep can have a lowering effect on a following high tone (that is, cause automatic downstep) if they are present in the phonetic string. When they are delinked and are not relinked, downdrift is blocked. This shows that downdrift is a very late rule in the grammar of this language, applying possibly only to surface tones. More will be said on this in the next section.

A question often raised about tone systems that have downdrift is whether highs and lows downdrift and if they do, whether it is at the same rate. While in some tone systems it has been reported that both highs and lows downdrift at the same rate (see for example, Williamson, 1970; Amayo, 1976; Elimelech, 1978), in the Urh^obo tone system, although both high tones and low tones are subject to downdrift, the high tones downdrift faster than the low tones. From the measurements given for 148(a) - (c) above, we find that the rate of downdrift between two high tones separated by a low tone is almost twice as that between two low tones. Thus in 148(a) we have a difference of 55Hz between the two high tones in the string while between the two low tones there is only 35 Hz. A similar situation occurs in 148 (b) and (c). In (b) there is a difference of 40 Hz between the two high tones but 20 Hz between the two low tones. In (c) we are interested in the four tones in the final position of the string since high and low tones alternate in that position and so provide us with a better opportunity to compare their behaviour. Here, there is a difference of 35 Hz between the two high tones and 20 Hz between the two low tones. It should be noted, though, that where two low tones are separated by a sequence

of high tones, the interval between them becomes slightly higher. In 151 below, the difference between the two lows is 30 Hz.

151. ̀o₂cé r é àmé₂ ---->

 L H H L L

 'water pot'

[̀océ rámẽ]

200 230 225 170 (Fig. 10)

 L H H L

A second question concerns whether consecutive highs and lows downdrift. As has been mentioned earlier in our discussion of basic tones (4.4) neither consecutive highs nor lows downdrift in this language. In a language like Ghotuo (Elugbe, 1985) although consecutive tones do not generally downdrift consecutive lows downdrift when they are preceded by a high or a mid tone.

4.5.2 THE NON-AUTOMATIC/PHONEMIC DOWNSTEP

4.5.2.1 INTRODUCTION

The non-automatic or phonemic or, simply, downstep, also involves the lowering of a high tone but in the absence of an obvious preceding low tone in the phonetic representation. Thus, one finds two nonlow tones in a sequence but the second is realised on a lower pitch than the immediately preceding one for no apparent reason. Many African languages exhibit this tonal phenomenon. A downstep may appear in the lexical tone contour of a word as in the following Urhobo nouns, where the final tones are lower

than the immediately preceding high tones although no obvious low tone can be said to be responsible for the lowering:

152. a) $\acute{o}g\acute{o}$ ---> $[\acute{o}g\bar{o}]$ 'in-law'
 H! H $\left[\begin{array}{cc} - & - \end{array} \right]$
- b) $\acute{i}\gamma\acute{o}_1$ ---> $[\acute{i}\gamma\bar{o}]$ 'money'
 H! H $\left[\begin{array}{cc} - & - \end{array} \right]$
- c) $\acute{o}_1 r\acute{e}_1 r\acute{e}_1$ ---> $[\acute{o}r\acute{e}\bar{r}\acute{e}]$ 'town'
 H H H $\left[\begin{array}{ccc} - & - & - \end{array} \right]$
- d) $\acute{o}\gamma\acute{o}$ ---> $[\acute{o}\gamma\bar{o}]$ 'honey'
 H! H $\left[\begin{array}{cc} - & - \end{array} \right]$

Downstep may also serve as the marker of a grammatical or syntactic construction. In Igbo, for example, several syntactic constructions, including the associative construction, are characterised by the appearance of a downstep. It is used to mark the second constituent of the associative construction as in the following examples (cf Clark 1980: 103):

153. a) $\acute{i}\acute{s}\acute{i} + \acute{e}\gamma\acute{u}$ ---> $\acute{i}\acute{s}\acute{i}\acute{e}\gamma\acute{u}$
 H H H H
 head goat 'the head of a goat'

b)	í s í + j í	--->	í s í j í
	H H H		H H [!] H
	head yam		'the top of the yam'

In Kikuyu (cf Clements and Ford, 1979) a downstep serves as a grammatical marker and appears after any member of a certain lexical class referred to as Class I words. Clark (1980: 102) has the following examples:

154. a)	/mòá γ áhíjǎ/-	abáire moáyahíjǎ njata
		HLH . L HL H :!HH
		he-gave weakling star
		'he gave the weakling a star'

b)	/mòanèkì/-	moaneki ɔ̀nìrɛ
		LLL !LH H
		'Mwaniki saw'

Winston (1960) is said to be the first to recognise the phenomenon of downstep and to distinguish it from the mid tone within a terraced level tone system (cf Elugbe 1985). According to Winston, downstep is not a toneme itself; it is rather something that conditions the actual pitch of the following high toneme. The feature downstep accounts for any nonlow tone being slightly lower than an immediately preceding nonlow. In his study of the Efik tone system, Winston distinguishes downstep from the mid tone and claims that in a terraced level system, it is possible to have an indefinite number of

downsteps within the same tone phrase. He says further that each downstep sets a new level for the rest of the tone phrase such that no tone within that tone phrase may rise above the new level. The series of steps that can result from the repeated occurrences of downstep form the basis for the terracing. However, Winston sees the downstep as an intersyllabic feature which occurs arbitrarily and helps to distinguish some particular meaning or syntactic relationships or both. There is no attempt to trace downstep to lost low tones.

Attempts to account for the downstep feature have led Stewart (1965) to suggest the derivation of the downstep from a floating low tone preceding a high tone and this low tone may be irrecoverably lost. According to his analysis, a low tone in a H - L - H sequence lowered the second H and then dropped out. The result is that the second H becomes downstepped (!H).

Fromkin (1972) suggests the need for the recognition of a phonemic downstep. According to this argument, establishing a low tone which would always be deleted and which serves only to account for downstep is an adhoc device and is unwarranted. However, Stewart's analysis above has remained the favoured one among linguists ever since.

Hyman and Schuh (1974: 92) describe downstep as follows: 'If downdrift occurs on the second H of a H - L - H sequence, then downstep is what results if the conditioning low tone is lost or assimilated to the level of the preceding high tone'. This

analysis suggests that for downstep to occur in a language, downdrift must also occur but with the availability of more data, it has been shown clearly that there are systems with downstep but no downdrift, for example Dschang - Bamileke (Hyman 1979) while some others have downdrift but no downstep, for example Hausa (Welmers 1973).

Hyman (1979) proposes that we treat downstep as deriving from contour simplification rules, such that, from a H-L-H sequence, the following processes may take place:

$$HLH \rightarrow HLH \rightarrow \hat{H}LH \rightarrow H!H$$

Clements (1979) suggests the insertion of the downstep. According to his analysis, the disappearing low tone and the downstep are viewed as a sequence such that a downstep is inserted before a low tone which may then drop out. A number of linguists have adopted this approach. For example, Elugbe (1985) in his analysis of the downstep in Ghotuo follows this approach but with a slight modification: he inserts the downstep after, not before, the disappearing low tone.

Clements and Ford (1979) view downstep as the result of having a floating low tone in the phonological representation. This floating low tone appears on the tonal tier but it is not linked to any vowel segment and, as a consequence, is not pronounced although it triggers downstep.

Clark (1980) accounts for downstep in Igbo as an instance of a pitch-drop marker, the sole phonological realisation of a grammatical formative whose non-tonal

segments have dropped out. This grammatical formative which she represents as [↓] is inserted at the constituent boundary of an associative phrase by means of a rule which cliticizes it to the second noun in the construction.

Pulleyblank (1986a) suggests that downstep is simply the result of a floating low tone which is not pronounced and so there is no need to create a special downstep feature. According to him, the existence of a phonetic downstep may be attributable to tense factors, syntactic factors, lexical factors, and so on and such factors can condition the existence of a floating tone in a phonological representation. The downstep that ultimately occurs in the phonetic form is the indirect result of such factors.

It is obvious from the foregoing that the popular approach to the treatment of downstep is to derive it from a lost or floating low tone. However, as we shall show later in this section, downstep in Urhobo does not result from floating or lost low tones. When a low tone present in the underlying representation is set afloat due to some phonological processes such as vowel elision the floating low tone is often irrecoverably lost and has no effect whatsoever on the pitch of the following high tone. A low tone has a lowering effect on a following high tone only if such a low tone is present in surface structure otherwise, it has no effect.

4.5.2.2. **THE DOWNSTEP IN URHOBO**

We have said earlier that we are regarding the third pitch found in this language as a non-automatic downstep and not a mid tone, and our reasons are stated below:

i) In a typical three level tone language, all three tones may be found in different positions in a word and so may follow or be followed by the same tone or any of the other two tones. In Urhobo, only the high and low tones are not restricted to any position in a word; the third level has a co-occurrence restriction attached to it, namely, it is found only after a high tone. Consequently, it is never found in word-initial position. In disyllabic and trisyllabic nouns, it occurs only in the final position, following a high tone. It never occurs in the prefix position. Such restrictions on its occurrence disqualify it from being regarded as a mid tone and support its recognition as a non-automatic downstep. Below are a few examples:

155. a) ɔ́'ɲɔ́ 'honey'
 b) ɔ́'ɛ́tɔ́ 'land, ground'
 c) ú'p'ó'í'ró'í 'feather'
 d) á'má 'a mould'

ii) When a noun which has this third level is used in an utterance, it has the effect of setting a new level for all following high tones, such that after it, a following high tone assumes the level of the downstep and not that of the preceding high tone with which it is phonologically identical. As pointed out by Elugbe (1985), although in a language with three distinct tones and downstep, such as Ghotuo, the mid tone has a lowering effect on the following high tone, the lowered high tone is still phonetically distinct from the mid. In Urhobo, on the other hand, after a downstep, the following high tone becomes

phonetically identical with the downstep. In the following examples, we indicate the rate of downstepping of nonlow tones with the integers beneath them so that 1 means a step away from the initial nonlow tone, 2 means two steps away, and so on.

156. a) $\acute{w}g\acute{w} \grave{w}m\acute{\epsilon} \acute{d}\acute{\epsilon} \acute{u}r\acute{\epsilon}_1 \grave{w}n\grave{a}$ ---> $[\acute{w}g\bar{w} \ m\bar{\acute{\epsilon}} \ d\bar{u}r\bar{\acute{\epsilon}} \ n\bar{\grave{a}}]$
 H !H L H H H H L L [- - - -]
 in-law mine bought tree the 1 1 1 1
 'my in-law bought the tree' 210 195 195 195 195 150
H !H H H H L (Fig. 17)

b) $\acute{w}g\acute{w} \grave{w}n\grave{a} \acute{d}\acute{a} \acute{o}_2\acute{t}\acute{w} \acute{r}\acute{\epsilon} \acute{w}r\acute{w} \grave{w}n\grave{a}$ --->
 H !H L L H H !H H H !H L L
 in-law the drank bottom AM honey the
 $[\acute{w}g\bar{w} \ n\bar{\grave{a}} \ d\bar{o}t\bar{w} \ r\bar{w}r\bar{w}n\bar{\grave{a}}]$
[- - - - -]
1 1 2 2 3
 280 240 190 240 210 210 180 160 (Fig. 18)
 H !H L H !H H !H L

'the in-law drank the dregs of the honey'

c) $\acute{w}r\acute{w} \grave{w}n\grave{a} \acute{s}\acute{a} \acute{w}s\acute{\epsilon} \grave{w}m\acute{\epsilon} \acute{v}\acute{\epsilon} \acute{o}_2\acute{t}\acute{w} \acute{r}\acute{\epsilon} \acute{w}g\acute{w} \grave{w}n\grave{a}$ -->
 H !H L L H H !H L H !H H H !H L L
 bee the stung father my at land AM inlaw the

280 260 185 248 225 225 225 200 208 185 155

H !H L H !H H H !H H !H L

'the bee stung my father on the in-law's land'

If we regard this third level as a mid tone, the conditions under which the allotones occur cannot be described, as has already been pointed out by Elugbe (1985:74) (cf also 'in-law' and 'bee/honey' as alternated in (b) and (c) above). As the examples above show, it is possible to have repeated occurrences of the downstep leading to different levels of this 'mid' which cannot be explained. Examples such as these go to support our recognition of the third level as a downstep, since, as Winston (1960) has said, in a terraced level system, it is possible to have an indefinite number of downsteps within the same tone phrase and each new occurrence of the downstep sets a new level for the rest of the tone phrase.

(iii) Welmers (1969: 88) claims that the phenomenon of 'terracing' or 'downstep' within a phrase is not found in Urhobo and that up till the last syllable in any given utterance all tones can be described in terms of a two-tone system: high and low. A nonlow tone lower than an immediately preceding nonlow is heard only in utterance - final position (that is, before a pause). For this reason, Welmers (1973) identifies the

third level as a mid tone and claims that when a noun with high-mid in isolation is used in other than clause - final position, it has the tones high - low. However, our examples in 156 above show that there is a difference in pitch in the realisation of a low tone from that of the downstep. There are recognisable varied pitch levels that cannot simply be labelled high - low in the tone groups exemplified above.

The problem that arises at this stage concerns how to account for the phenomenon of downstep in this language. We have found that lost low tones do not account for it. It is not also syntactically or grammatically conditioned as has been found to happen in Igbo and Kikuyu. Thus, although in Igbo the string in 157(a) would be realised as 157(b).

157.	a)	í s í + é yú	--->	157(b)	í s í é yú
		H H H H			H H H!H
		head goat			'a goat's head'

In Urhobo, a similar string would not produce similar results. The following are

examples:

158.	a)	ú r é + r é + ó g b á	--->	[ú r é r ó g b á]
		H H H H H		H H H H
		wood AM hero		'a hero's wood'

b)	ú k ó ₁	+ rɛ	+ ɔ́ g ɔ́	---	[ú k ó r ɔ́ g ɔ́]
	H H	H L	H		H H H H
	Cup	AM	bottle		'a bottle's cup'

In the Igbo example, the two nouns are H - H in isolation but when they come together in the associative construction, a downstep appears on the second noun, a situation that has been accounted for as deriving from the insertion of a floating low tone (Williamson, 1970), a floating high tone (Goldsmith, 1976), or a grammatical downstep (Clark, 1980).

In Urhobo, on the other hand, example 158(a) shows that the high tones are realised on the same pitch throughout, while example 158(b) shows that the deletion of the low tone borne by the prefix vowel of the second noun does not result in a downstep. Moreover, the phenomenon is not found in any other context apart from being part of the lexical make-up of some nouns. If we were to account for an item such as [ɔ́ s̄] 'father' as deriving from the processes in 159 below:

159.	i)	H	(L)	H
		V	C	V
		ɔ	s	ɛ

Underlying representation

ii) $\begin{array}{c} \text{H} \quad \textcircled{\text{L}} \quad \text{H} \\ | \quad \cdot \quad | \\ \text{V} \quad \text{C} \quad \text{V} \\ | \quad | \quad | \\ \text{ɔ} \quad \text{s} \quad \text{ɛ} \end{array}$ by (L) segmentalisation

iii) $\begin{array}{c} \text{H} \quad \text{L} \quad !\text{H} \\ | \quad / \quad | \\ \text{V} \quad \text{C} \quad \text{V} \\ | \quad | \quad | \\ \text{ɔ} \quad \text{s} \quad \text{ɛ} \end{array}$ by downstep insertion

iv) $\begin{array}{c} \text{H} \quad \quad !\text{H} \\ | \quad \quad | \\ \text{V} \quad \text{C} \quad \text{V} \\ | \quad | \quad | \\ \text{ɔ} \quad \text{s} \quad \text{ɛ} \end{array}$ by L deletion

[ɔ́sɛ̃] 'father'

We should also be able to derive, for example, /dɛ́ ɔ̀nɛ́/ 'bought yam' in the same manner and arrive at similar results but this is not the case. The sequence /dɛ́ ɔ̀nɛ́/ is not realised as [dɔ́nɛ́] but as [dɔ́nɛ́̃].

In 160 below, it is the lexical downstep present in the first noun that lowers the pitch of the following high tone but this downstep is not derivable from any floating tones neither does it result from some grammatical evidence.

16.0	íyó, ré sgbá	[íyó rōgbā]
	H! H H H H	H !H !H !H
	Money AM hero	'hero's money'

In any case, a low tone lowers the pitch of a following high tone only when it is present in the phonetic string and this is accounted for by downdrift rules commonly found in many terraced level languages.

We, therefore, cannot synchronically or derivationally account for the downstep feature in this language as resulting from lost or floating low tones, a position popularly held by many linguists about the downstep. Based on our data, one way out is to follow Fromkin (1972) who suggests that accounting for downstep simply by always establishing a low tone which is always deleted is an ad-hoc device which is not warranted and as such we should grant a phonemic status to the downstep. On the basis of this, we can then assume that the downstep feature is marked underlyingly in the lexical representation of those nouns in which it is found, just like the more basic high and low tones in this language. We shall, thus, represent a High-Downstep noun such as [óṣḗ] in the underlying representation as /óṣḗ/ or H!H with the mark // representing the downstep feature.

4.6 FLOATING TONES

Within the standard theory, a floating tone is described as a segment specified only for tone which, at some point during the derivation, merges with some vowel, and passes on its tonal specification to that vowel. In autosegmental theory however, floating tones are regarded as 'melodic levels that map onto the syllabic structure' (Goldsmith, 1976: 45). Their occurrence is predictable in the phonological representation on autosegmental grounds.

In Urhobo, floating tones may result in a number of ways. In this section, we present only the highlights, more on the behaviour of floating tones would be treated in the following chapters.

i) A number of our examples so far attest to the fact that when morphemes come together at boundaries, processes such as vowel elision and glide formation may take place resulting in the loss of the vowel segment. Since the affected vowels are also tone bearing units, the tones they bear automatically become floating tones.

The following are examples:

161.	(a)	o ₁ zé ₁ + mÉ	---	o zé mÉ	---	[ò zémÉ]
		L H L H		L H $\text{\textcircled{H}}$ H		L H H
		basin my		by V.E		'my basin'

(b) $\text{ʔbè}_2 \text{ ɔ́vavà re}_2$ $\text{--> } \text{ɔ́ bj' ɔ́vavàre}$ $\text{--> } [\text{ɔ́ bj' ɔ́vavàre}]$
 L L H H L L L $\text{\textcircled{L}}$ H H L L L H H L L
 book red by G.F. ;a red book'

(c) $\text{é}_2\text{ka} + \text{ívé}$ $\text{--> } \text{ék' ívé}$ $\text{--> } [\text{ék' ívé}]$
 H L HL H $\text{\textcircled{L}}$ HL H $\text{\textcircled{L}}$ HL
 maize two by V.E. 'two maize'

ii) A number of grammatical constructions are marked by the occurrence of floating tones which affect the phonetic realisation of the inherent tones borne by neighbouring segments. An example is the associative construction which, apart from being marked segmentally by /rɛ/ is also marked tonally by a floating high tone which gets segmentalised in an appropriate position within the string. We present some examples below:

162. (a) `aje}_2 + \text{rɛ} + \text{ɔ́bo}_2$        $\text{--> } \text{`aje r' ɔ́bo $\text{--> } [\text{`aje rɔ́bo}]$
 LL H LL LL $\text{\textcircled{H}}$ LL LL H L
 woman AM+ATM doctor by V.E. 'doctor's wife'

(b) $\text{`aje}_2 + \text{rɛ} + \text{ɔ́bo} + \text{fáre}$        $\text{--> } \text{`aje r' ɔ́bo fáre} \rightarrow$
 LL $\text{\textcircled{H}}$ LL $\text{\textcircled{H}}$ HL LL LHH L
 woman AM doctor ATM flogged by V.E. and T.S.
 'a woman that a doctor flogged' $[\text{`aje rɔ́bo fáre}]$
 LL LHH L

iii) A number of tonal morphemes (tomorphs) occur in this language. For instance, tense is indicated mainly by tone. The present tense tomorph is a floating high tone that gets segmentalised on the final vowel of the subject noun phrase while the past tense tomorph is also a floating high tone that gets segmentalised on the only or final vowel of the verb stem.

163. (a) ɔ + / dɛ + ɔ̂ n é ---> [ɔ̂ ɔ́ d ɔ̂ n é̄]
 ∅ (H) ∅ L H L H L H
 he present tomorph buy yam 'he buys/is buying yam'

(b) é̂ s̄ e₂ + / t dɛ + é̂₁ wū̄ ---> [é̂ s̄ ē d̄ ē wū̄]
 H L (H) ∅ H L H L H L

Present

Name tomorph buy dress 'Ese buys/is buying a dress'

(c) ɔ + dɛ + / ɔ̂ n é ---> [ɔ̂ d ɔ́ n é̄]
 ∅ ∅ (H) L H L H H

Past

he buy tomorph yam 'he bought yam'

(d) ɔ + dɛ r e₂ + / ---> [ɔ̂ d é̂ r ē]
 ∅ ∅ (H) L H L

Past

he bought tomorph 'he bought'

In addition, the question morpheme is a floating low tone that gets segmentalised on the final vowel of a statement while the negative morpheme is a LH sequence that also gets segmentalised on the final vowel of the positive form, this time resulting in the lengthening of the final vowel (cf. 3.4.3 above). We present some examples:

164. (a) $\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{ɔ}} + \text{d}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{ɛ}} + \overset{\text{̀}}{\text{ɔ}}\text{n}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{ɛ}} \backslash \text{--->} \quad \overset{\text{̀}}{\text{ɔ}}\text{d}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{ɔ}}\text{n}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{ɛ}}$
 L H L H $\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{L}}$ L H HL
 he bought yam QM 'Did he buy yam?'
- (b) $\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{ɔ}} + \text{d}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{ɛ}} + \overset{\text{̀}}{\text{ɔ}}\text{n}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{ɛ}} + \text{v} \text{--->} \quad \overset{\text{̀}}{\text{ɔ}}\text{d}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{ɔ}}\text{n}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{ɛ}}\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{ɛ}}$
 L H L H $\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{LH}}$ L HHLH
 he bought yam NM 'He did not buy yam'

iv) Another instance of floating tones is found in the L...H tones borne by the discontinuous morpheme that marks the infinitive form of verbs, as discussed in 3.5.2.1 above. The prefix vowel bears the low tone while the suffix vowel (and where the suffix is not realised, the final vowel of the verb stem) bears the high tone. Below are some examples:

165. (a) mu 'carry' --> $\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{e}}_1 \text{mu}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{o}}$ [$\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{e}}\text{m}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{w}}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{o}}$] 'to carry'
- (b) fi 'throw' --> $\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{e}}_1 \text{fi}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{o}}$ [$\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{e}}\text{f}\text{j}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{o}}$] 'to throw'
- (c) $\overset{\text{~}}{\text{s}}\text{e}_2$ 'refuse' --> $\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{e}}\text{si}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{ɔ}}$ [$\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{e}}\text{s}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{j}}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{ɔ}}$] 'to refuse'
- (d) so_2 'sing' --> $\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{e}}\text{su}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{ɔ}}$ [$\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{e}}\text{sw}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{ɔ}}$] 'to sing'
- (e) se_1 'read' --> $\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{e}}\text{se}'$ 'to read'

- (f) $\int\epsilon$ 'sell' --> $\grave{\epsilon}\int\acute{\epsilon}$ 'to sell'
- (g) $k\tilde{\sigma}$ 'plant' --> $\grave{\epsilon}k\acute{\sigma}$ 'to plant'
- (h) da 'drink' --> $\grave{\epsilon}d\acute{a}$ 'to drink'

We now proceed to examine tonal alternations in grammatical constructions.

CHAPTER FIVE

TONAL ALTERNATIONS IN THE NOUN PHRASE

5.1 INTRODUCTION

In explaining tonal alternations and processes apparent in this language, we shall demonstrate in a principled way and within the framework of our chosen theory the role tone plays in the grammar. It is clear that tone exerts a lot of influence on the grammar of Urhobo since most of the grammatical information available are revealed through the manipulation of tones. There are, thus, a number of useful generalisations concerning tonal alternations and tonological processes which can be drawn from examining more closely various grammatical configurations.

The Urhobo tone system lends credence to the autosegmental proposal that tone belongs to an autosegmental tier which is independent of the segmental tier and that both tiers are linked, via the CV skeletal tier, by the establishment of association lines between the linked elements of the two tiers. It is this link that results in the simultaneous realisation of a segment and a tone phonetically. Furthermore, it is also claimed (Goldsmith, 1976) that there is a level in the grammar which contains as entries in it various melodic patterns which are independent of words or sound segments and which are assigned to particular grammatical configurations, thus making the melody a separate entity in the lexicon.

In order to successfully describe tonal alternations in Urhobo, it is necessary to recognise two types of tones, namely lexical tones and tonal morphemes or grammatical tones. Lexical tones are those that are borne by lexical items (not derived items) in the underlying representation and are similar in function to vowel and consonant segments, in that a difference in tone can result in a difference in the meaning of otherwise homophonous words. For example:

166.	(a)	è ₁ nì	L L	'elephant'
	(b)	è ₁ ní	L H	'head pad'
	(c)	ùkpe ₁	L L	'year'
	(d)	úkpe ₁	H L	'bed'

On the other hand, tonal morphemes (that is, tomorphs, cf Elugbe (1985)) are floating tones which are grammatically significant in the language and exist independently of 'segmental' phonological strings. They are mapped onto specific positions in the grammatical constructions in which they feature and affect the tonal output of the strings in the surface form. They may be single tone units or tonal melodies, that is, fixed tonal patterns. In autosegmental theory, floating tones are regarded as melodic levels. In Urhobo, the tones that indicate tense and aspect are tonal morphemes and their segmentalisation usually results in the modification of lexical tones borne by adjacent segments.

In this chapter, we shall examine tonal alternations which take place in noun phrases and account for them in a principled way. Only vowel segments bear tones in Urhobo. Consequently, tone is mapped onto a V slot on the CV tier from where it is linked to a vowel segment on the segmental tier. Any tone that is delinked from a V slot is assumed to float and, unless it is relinked, it does not get any phonetic realisation and so it is deleted. As a result, in the derivations that follow, we may not reflect a stage at which a delinked tone is deleted from the string.

5.2 TONE IN THE NOUN

Most nouns in Urhobo are either disyllabic or trisyllabic. The lexical function of tone is particularly obvious in the noun class because lexical items may differ in meaning only because they differ in tone. Moreover, words entering into this class from other word classes by derivation are required to display particular tone patterns.

On the basis of the patterning of the three pitch levels identified for the language in the last chapter, we can classify Urhobo disyllabic nouns in their citation form into five tone groups as follows:

167. Disyllabic Nouns.

Group 1	High-High (HH)	Nouns
a) úkó'	[- -]	'cup'
b) ǒgba'	[- -]	'hero'
c) úwé'	[- -]	'nose'

Group 2 High-Downstep (H !H) (H DS) Nouns

- a) ʒ'gɔ́ [- -] 'in-law' '
 b) í'xó₁ [- -] 'money' '
 c) ó₂'tɔ́ [- -] 'land, ground'

Group 3 High-Low (H L) Nouns

- a) úkpe₁ [- -] 'bed'
 b) ʒgbǎ [- -] 'thirty'
 c) é se₂ [- -] 'gift'

Group 4 Low-High (L H) Nouns

- a) ɔ́gɔ́ [- -] 'bottle'
 b) è ve₂ [- -] 'goat'
 c) è₁ ní [- -] 'head pad'

Group 5 Low-Low (L L) Nouns

- a) ùkpe₁ [- -] 'year'
 b) è ve₂ [- -] 'kola nut'
 c) è₁ nì [- -] 'elephant'

Similarly, trisyllabic nouns can be classified into ten groups as follows:

168. Trisyllabic Nouns

Group 1 High-High-High(HHH) Nouns

- a) ágáda' [- - -] 'machet'

- b) $\acute{e}h\acute{o}_1 h\acute{o}_1$ [- - -] 'hidden corner'
 c) $\acute{a}g\acute{o}_2 g\acute{o}_2$ [- - -] 'bell'

Group 2 High-High Downstep (HH !H) Nouns

- a) $\acute{o}_1 r\acute{e}_1 r\acute{e}_1$ [- - -] 'town'
 b) $\acute{u}k\acute{o}_1 k\acute{o}_1$ [- - -] 'association, meeting'
 c) $\acute{o}_2 h\acute{o}r\acute{o}$ [- - -] 'skin'

Group 3 High-High-Low (HHL) Nouns

- a) $\acute{o}_1 n\acute{o}_1 g\grave{b}\acute{o}_1$ [- - -] 'pussy cat'
 b) $\acute{\omega}f\acute{i}g\grave{b}\acute{o}_2$ [- - -] 'oil'
 c) $\acute{i}t\acute{a}b\grave{a}$ [- - -] 'tobacco'

Group 4 High-Low-High (HLH) Nouns

- a) $\acute{o}_1 d\grave{i}b\acute{o}_1$ [- - -] 'banana'
 b) $\acute{\omega}\chi\grave{e}n\acute{e}$ [- - -] 'God'
 c) $\acute{e}\upsilon\grave{e}r\acute{e}$ [- - -] 'earthen pot'

Group 5 High-Low-Low (HLL) Nouns

- a) $\acute{i}v\grave{i}r\grave{i}$ [- - -] 'smoke'
 b) $\acute{\omega}\grave{s}\grave{a}r\grave{e}_2$ [- - -] 'man'
 c) $\acute{e}g\acute{o}_1 d\acute{o}_1$ [- - -] 'compound'

Group 6 Low-High-High (LHH) Nouns

- a) $\grave{i}r\acute{i}b\acute{o}_1$ [- - -] 'pepper'

- b) ̀isɛ́nɛ́₁ [- - -] 'camwood'
 c) ̀ò₁ rú₁ [- - -] 'thread'

Group 7 Low-High-Downstep (LH!H) Nouns

- a) ̀ò₁ gbé₁ jí₁ [- - -] 'tortoise'
 b) ̀úkú₁ tá₁ [- - -] 'stone'
 c) ̀é₁ wé₁ rí₁ [- - -] 'monkey'

Group 8 Low-High-Low (LHL) Nouns

- a) ̀é₂ rá₂ kò₂ [- - -] 'dog'
 b) ̀ì₁ yé₁ rẹ₁ [- - -] 'road'
 c) ̀ù₁ tẹ₁ hrù [- - -] 'iron'

Group 9 Low-Low-High (LLH) Nouns

- a) ̀é₁ gbè₁ dé₁ [- - -] 'needle'
 b) ̀ò₁ gò₁ rǒ₁ [- - -] 'toad'
 c) ̀ò₁ kpè₁ tú [- - -] 'trouble'

Group 10 Low-Low-Low (LLL) Nouns

- a) ̀ò₁ dibò₁ [- - -] 'slave, servant'
 b) ̀ò₁ hɛ₂ rẹ₂ [- - -] 'neck'
 c) ̀é₂ rá₂ vẹ₂ [- - -] 'animal, meat'

There are a few nouns with more than three syllables but most of them are compound words or ideophones and their tone patterning is quite varied. It will not be a

5.4 TONE IN THE NOUN PHRASE

In Urhobo, the noun phrase consists of a noun and a modifier. These modifiers are of different types but they all follow their headnouns. We shall classify the noun phrases into two broad groups depending on whether or not we are dealing with an associative construction. This is because, associative noun phrases behave differently from non-associative noun phrases in a number of ways. We shall begin with the non-associative noun phrases.

5.4.1 NON-ASSOCIATIVE NOUN PHRASES

The modifiers in this group directly follow their headnouns and comprise a prefix vowel and a stem. The prefix vowel alternates to reflect number concord. We make a further sub-classification into three subgroups based on segmental and tonal behaviours.

5.4.1.1. SUBGROUP A

Our Subgroup A comprises the following:

i) Noun + Definite Article:

/ɔ̀nà/ 'the' (singular)

/è₂nà/ 'the' (plural)

ii) Noun + Demonstrative Pronoun:

/ɔ̀nàná/ 'this' ~ /è₂nàná/ 'these'

/ɔ̀jè₂nà/ 'that' ~ /è₂jè₂nà/ 'those'

iii) Noun + Possessive Pronoun (first and second person singular forms only).

lómé 'my, mine'

lówé 'your, yours'

Each of these modifiers except the last set is realised on the low tone in the citation form. When they occur as modifiers in the noun phrase, both the prefix vowel and the low tone it bears are elided. The following are some examples:

170. a) ò₂ b₂ + ò₂ nà --->

[òbòná]

L L LL

[]

hand the

L L L

'the hand'

b) íkó₁ + è₂ nà --->

[íkónǎ]

H H L L

--

[]

cups the

-

H H L

'the cups'

c) ǒkà + ò₂ nà nà --->

[ǒkà nǎ nǎ]

H L LLL

-

[]

maize this

H L L L

'the maize'

d) è₂ má + è₂ je₂ nà --->

[è^ámájè^ánǎ]

L H L L L

[]

cloths those

L H L L

'those (pieces of) cloth'

- e) $i\acute{\gamma}o_1 + \grave{o}m\acute{e} \rightarrow$ $[i\acute{\gamma}o\bar{m}\bar{e}]$
 H !H LH $\boxed{\quad - \quad - \quad}$
 money my H H H 'my money'
- f) $ukpe_1 + \grave{o}w\acute{e} \rightarrow$ $[ukpe\tilde{w}\bar{e}]$
 H L LH $\boxed{\quad - \quad - \quad}$
 bed your H L H 'your bed'
- g) $\grave{o}n\acute{e} + \grave{o}m\acute{e} \rightarrow$ $[\grave{o}n\acute{e}m\acute{e}]$
 LH LH $\boxed{\quad - \quad - \quad}$
 yam my L H H 'my yam'

We illustrate with some sample derivations in 171 below:

171. (a)

L	L	L	L
V	C	V+V	C V
o ₂	b	ɔ	ɔ n a

Underlying representation
- 'hand' 'the'

by vowel elision

by (L) deletion

[^ˈobɔn^ˈã] 'the hand'

by vowel elision

by (L) deletion

[eɣ^má jěná]

'those (pieces of) cloth'

Underlying Representation

5.4.1.2

SUBGROUP B

Our Subgroup B comprises:

i) Noun + Indefinite Article:

$/\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{ɔ}}\text{v}\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{o}}_2/$ 'a, an' ~ $/\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{e}}_2\text{v}\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{o}}_2/$ 'some'

ii) Noun + Numeral

Each of these modifiers also comprises a prefix vowel and a stem but it is the final vowel of the noun that is elided leaving the modifier intact segmentally but resulting in tonal modification taking place on the prefix vowel of the modifier. Both the prefix and stem vowels of the indefinite article bear low tones in the citation form. As for the basic numerals, all but $/\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{ɔ}}\text{v}\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{o}}_2/$ 'one' begin with a high tone. It might be useful to present

Urhobo basic numerals here:

$\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{ɔ}}\text{v}\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{o}}_2$	-	'one'	$\overset{\text{́}}{\text{e}}_2\overset{\text{́}}{\text{s}}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{a}}$	'six'
$\overset{\text{́}}{\text{i}}\text{v}\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{e}}$	-	'two'	$\overset{\text{́}}{\text{i}}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{y}}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{u}}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{r}}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{e}}$	'seven'
$\overset{\text{́}}{\text{e}}_2\overset{\text{́}}{\text{r}}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{a}}$	-	'three'	$\overset{\text{́}}{\text{e}}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{r}}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{e}}_2\overset{\text{́}}{\text{r}}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{e}}_2$	'eight'
$\overset{\text{́}}{\text{e}}\text{n}\overset{\text{̀}}{\text{e}}_2$	-	'four'	$\overset{\text{́}}{\text{i}}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{r}}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{i}}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{r}}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{i}}$	'nine'
$\overset{\text{́}}{\text{i}}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{j}}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{o}}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{f}}$	-	'five'	$\overset{\text{́}}{\text{i}}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{h}}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{u}}\overset{\text{́}}{\text{e}}_1$	'ten'

When the final vowel of the preceding noun gets elided, its tone remains and surfaces on the prefix vowel of the modifier resulting in four types of tonal modifications. We represent the final vowel of the noun as V_1 and the prefix vowel of the modifier as V_2 .

(i) If both V_1 and V_2 bear identical tones, relinking applies vacuously and so no tonal modification takes place. Example:

172. (a) $\text{`}\epsilon\text{d}\epsilon\text{ + `}\upsilon\upsilon\text{0}_2 \text{ ---> } [\text{`}\epsilon\text{d}\upsilon\upsilon\text{0}]$
 $\begin{matrix} \text{L L} & \text{L L} \\ \text{day} & \text{one} \end{matrix}$
 $\begin{matrix} \text{---} \\ \text{---} \\ \text{---} \end{matrix}$
 L L L
 'a/one day'

(b) $\text{`}\acute{\text{i}}\acute{\text{o}}_1 \text{ + } \text{`}\acute{\text{i}}\text{h}\acute{\text{u}}\grave{\text{e}} \text{ ---> } [\text{`}\acute{\text{i}}\acute{\text{i}}\text{x}\text{w}\acute{\text{e}}]$
 $\begin{matrix} \text{H H} & \text{H L L} \\ \text{cups} & \text{ten} \end{matrix}$
 $\begin{matrix} \text{---} & \text{---} \\ \text{---} & \text{---} \end{matrix}$
 H H L
 'ten cups'

(c) $\text{`}\epsilon_2\text{n}\acute{\text{e}} \text{ + } \text{`}\acute{\text{i}}\text{r}\acute{\text{i}}\text{r}\acute{\text{i}} \text{ ---> } [\text{`}\epsilon\text{n}\acute{\text{i}}\text{r}\acute{\text{i}}\text{r}\acute{\text{i}}]$
 $\begin{matrix} \text{L H} & \text{H H!H} \\ \text{yams} & \text{nine} \end{matrix}$
 $\begin{matrix} \text{---} & \text{---} \\ \text{---} & \text{---} \end{matrix}$
 L H H!H
 'nine yams'

ii) If V_1 bears a high tone (H) or a non-automatic downstep (!H) and V_2 bears a low tone (L), the relinking of H or !H results in the automatic delinking (and deletion) of L.

The following are examples:

173. (a) $\text{`}\epsilon_2\text{n}\acute{\text{e}} \text{ + } \text{`}\epsilon_2\text{v}\text{0}_2 \text{ ---> } [\text{`}\epsilon\text{n}\acute{\text{e}}\text{v}\text{0}]$
 $\begin{matrix} \text{L H} & \text{L L} \\ \text{yams} & \text{some} \end{matrix}$
 $\begin{matrix} \text{---} & \text{---} \\ \text{---} & \text{---} \end{matrix}$
 $\begin{matrix} \text{L} & \text{H} & \text{L} \\ \text{some} & \text{yams} \end{matrix}$

(b) $\overset{!}{\text{ɔ}}\overset{!}{\text{s}}\overset{!}{\text{ɛ}} + \overset{\text{ɔ}}{\text{v}}\overset{\text{v}}{\text{o}}_2 \rightarrow$

H!H L L
father one

$[\overset{\text{ɔ}}{\text{s}}\overset{\text{v}}{\text{v}}\overset{\text{v}}{\text{o}}]$
[- -]
H!HL
'one/a father'

iii) If V_1 is !H and V_2 is H the relinking of (!H) results in the downstepping of any following H to !H. Below are some examples:

174. (a) $\overset{!}{\text{e}}_2\overset{!}{\text{s}}\overset{!}{\text{ɛ}} + \overset{\text{e}}{\text{r}}_2\overset{\text{a}}{\text{r}}_2 \rightarrow$

H!H H L
fathers three

$[\overset{\text{e}}{\text{s}}\overset{\text{r}}{\text{r}}\overset{\text{a}}{\text{r}}]$
[- -]
H!HL

'three fathers'

(b) $\overset{\text{e}}{\text{g}}_2\overset{\text{ɔ}}{\text{ɔ}} + \overset{\text{ɛ}}{\text{r}}_2\overset{\text{ɛ}}{\text{r}}_2\overset{\text{ɛ}}{\text{r}}_2 \rightarrow$

H!H !H

in-laws eight

$[\overset{\text{e}}{\text{g}}\overset{\text{ɛ}}{\text{r}}\overset{\text{ɛ}}{\text{r}}\overset{\text{ɛ}}{\text{r}}]$
[- - -]

H!H!H!H

'eight in-laws'

iv) If V_1 is low and V_2 is H (note that !H cannot occur in this V_2 position since it is a prefix vowel) relinking of the low tone of V_1 onto V_2 which already bears a high tone results in a LH contour. The following are examples:

175. (a) $\overset{\text{ɪ}}{\text{k}}\overset{\text{p}}{\text{e}}_1 + \overset{\text{ɪ}}{\text{v}}\overset{\text{ɛ}}{\text{ɛ}} \rightarrow$

H L H L
beds two

$[\overset{\text{ɪ}}{\text{k}}\overset{\text{p}}{\text{v}}\overset{\text{ɛ}}{\text{ɛ}}]$
[- / -]
H $\hat{\text{L}}$ HL
'two beds'

(b) 'abɔ + ɛrɛrɛ₂ →

[abɛ rɛrɛ]

L L H H!H

H L̂H H!H

hands eight

'eight hands'

It should be noted that in fast/rapid speech, the LH contour gets simplified to H. In 176 below, we present some sample derivations.

176 (a) i)

Underlying Representation

day

one, a

ii)

by vowel elision

[e' gε̃ r̃ ẽ r̃ ẽ] 'eight in-laws'

5.4.1.3 **SUBGROUP C**

Our Subgroup C comprises

Noun + Attributive Modifier noun phrases

Most attributive modifiers in Urhobo are derived from verbs and bear the tones

H HL, for those that are trisyllabic, and H HLL for those that have four syllables. When they occur as modifiers of nouns, they also retain both their prefix vowels and the tones they bear. It is the final vowel of the noun that either gets elided or undergoes glide formation while the tone it bears is obligatorily deleted. Let us examine some examples:

177. (a) $\dot{e}_1 \text{r}\ddot{u}$ + $\acute{o}\acute{v}\acute{a}\acute{v}\ddot{a}\ddot{r}\ddot{e}_2$ ---> $[\text{erw}\acute{o}\acute{v}\acute{a}\acute{v}\ddot{a}\ddot{r}\ddot{e}]$
 L L H H L L
 cap red L HHL L 'a red cap'
- (b) $\acute{o}_1 \text{n}\acute{o}_1 \text{g}\ddot{b}\acute{o}_1$ + $\acute{o}_1 \text{r}\acute{o}_2 \acute{a}\ddot{r}\acute{o}_2$ ---> $[\text{on}\acute{o}\text{g}\ddot{b}\acute{o}\text{r}\acute{a}\ddot{r}\acute{o}]$
 H H L H HHL
 pussy cat big H H H H L 'a big pussy cat'
- (c) $\acute{u}\acute{r}\acute{e}_1$ + $\acute{o}_1 \text{g}\acute{r}\acute{o}_1 \text{g}\ddot{r}\acute{o}_1$ ---> $[\text{ur}\acute{o}\text{g}\acute{r}\acute{o}\text{g}\ddot{r}\acute{o}]$
 H H H H L
 tree long H H H L 'a tall tree'
- (d) $\acute{o}\acute{g}\acute{o}$ + $\acute{o}_1 \text{b}\acute{i}\acute{e}_1 \text{b}\acute{i}$ ---> $[\text{og}\acute{o}\text{b}\acute{i}\acute{e}\acute{b}\acute{i}]$
 H! H H HHL
 in-law black H H H L 'a black in-law'

The final vowels of the nouns in 177 above each bears one of the phonemic tone levels found in the language and in each case, the tone is elided along with the vowel that bore it. Thus, in 177(d) the non-automatic downstep found in the noun does not pull down the pitch of the following high tone. This shows that the lowering effect of the low tone and the non-automatic downstep on a following high tone is automatic only if these tones are present in the phonetic string. If they get deleted, automatic downstep is blocked. This is further evidence of our claim in 4.5.2 above that automatic downstep is a late rule in the grammar and applies only to surface forms.

We illustrate the noun + attribute^{iv} modifier with the sample derivations below:

5.4.2 ASSOCIATIVE CONSTRUCTIONS

The associative construction is marked underlyingly on both the segmental tier and on the tonal tier. On the segmental tier, it is marked by an independent grammatical morpheme /rɛ/ which we refer to as the associative marker (AM) and it occurs between the noun and its modifier. This morpheme is underlyingly toneless. The vowel of this associative marker is always elided in normal conversational speech, although it is easy to recover it in slow deliberate speech. On the tonal tier, the associative construction is marked by a floating high tone which we refer to as the associative tonal marker (ATM). We shall examine the behaviour of the associative tone marker (ATM) in two types of associative constructions, namely:

- d) $e_1 w\ddot{u} + r\acute{\epsilon} + \acute{o}_2 d\acute{\epsilon} \rightarrow$
 HL H H !H
 dress AM + ATM yesterday
 [e $\bar{w}\ddot{u}$ r $\bar{\acute{\epsilon}}$ d $\bar{\acute{\epsilon}}$]
 H L H !H 'yesterday's dress'
- e) $\acute{i}y\acute{o}_1 + r\acute{\epsilon} + e_1 w\ddot{u} \rightarrow$
 H!H H H L
 money AM + ATM dress
 [i $\bar{y}\acute{o}$ r $\bar{\acute{\epsilon}}$ w $\bar{\acute{\epsilon}}\ddot{u}$]
 H!H H L 'money for dress'
- f) $\acute{o}_2 b\grave{o} + r\acute{\epsilon} + \acute{a}j\acute{e}_2 + r\acute{\epsilon} + \acute{o}_1 v\grave{i}\acute{e}_1 \rightarrow$
 L L H L L H L L L
 hand AM+ATM woman AM+ATM king
 [o $\bar{b}\acute{o}$ r $\bar{\acute{\epsilon}}$ a $\bar{j}\acute{e}$ r $\bar{\acute{\epsilon}}$ o $\bar{v}\acute{i}\acute{e}$]
 L L H L H L
 'the hand of a king's wife'
- g) $\acute{a}y\acute{m}\acute{a} + r\acute{\epsilon} + \acute{r}\acute{o}\phi\acute{a} + r\acute{\epsilon} + \acute{r}\acute{y}\acute{a}r\acute{e}_2 + r\acute{\epsilon} + \acute{o}_2 d\acute{\epsilon} \rightarrow$
 L H H L H H L L H H !H
 cloth AM+ATM bride AM+ATM man AM^{+ATM} yesterday
 [a $\bar{y}\acute{m}\acute{a}$ r $\bar{\acute{\epsilon}}$ r $\bar{\acute{\epsilon}}$ o $\bar{\phi}\acute{a}$ r $\bar{\acute{\epsilon}}$ r $\bar{\acute{y}}\acute{a}r\acute{e}$ r $\bar{\acute{\epsilon}}$ o $\bar{d}\acute{\epsilon}$]
 [L H H H H L L H !H]
 'a cloth (belonging to) the bride of yesterday's man'

The last two examples in 179 above are recursive Noun + Noun phrases and, as can be noticed, they are similar in every respect to the simple Noun + Noun phrase, the only difference being that more nouns are added to the string to extend the noun phrase. The associative marker, bearing the associative tonal marker, precedes every additional

The associative marker, bearing the associative tonal marker, precedes every additional noun while the same processes of vowel elision, relinking of the floating high tone and the delinking of the inherent tone of the adjacent vowel segment take place. We illustrate the Noun + Noun phrase with some sample derivations below.

5.4.2.2 NOUN + RELATIVE CLAUSE

In the associative construction comprising a Noun + Relative Clause we also have both the AM and the ATM. However, the ATM is segmentalised, not on the AM, but on the final vowel of the subject of the relative clause (the subject immediately precedes the verb of the clause). Thus, since the associative marker is underlyingly toneless, when its vowel segment is elided, no tonal modification occurs on the prefix vowel of the following noun. Rather, tonal modification occurs on the last vowel segment of the subject of the relative clause. In this position, vowel elision does not occur. Consequently, it is the inherent tone in that position that is obligatorily delinked, with the effect applying vacuously if it is also a high tone. We shall examine some examples below:

b) $\acute{o}_2 t \acute{o} + r\epsilon + \acute{o} g \acute{o} + / + d\acute{e} r\epsilon_2 + \acute{o}_2 d\acute{e} \rightarrow$ [ot̄r̄ḡō d̄ɛr̄jod̄ɛ]
 H!H Ø H!H (H) HL H!H
 land AM in-law ATM bought yesterday
 H!HH HHH!H

'the (parcel of) land that in-law bought yesterday'

c) $\grave{o}_1 z\acute{e}_1 + r\epsilon + \acute{o} s\acute{e} + v\acute{e} + \grave{a}j\epsilon_2 + \acute{o} n\grave{a} + / + \int \acute{e}r\epsilon_2 \rightarrow$ [ozē r̄sɛvajē n̄ɛ̄sɛ̄r̄ē]
 LH Ø H!H H -LL LL (H) HL
 basin AM father and woman the ATM sold
 LHH!HHLHHL

'a basin that father and the woman sold'

d) $\acute{o} \int \grave{a}r\epsilon_2 + r\epsilon + o_1 + / + hu\acute{e}_1 + \acute{o} m \acute{o} \rightarrow$ [ɔ̄r̄ɛ̄ r̄ō xw̄om̄ɔ̄]
 HLL Ø Ø (H) HH H H
 man AM he ATM beat child
 HLLHHH

'a man that beat a child'

e) $\grave{a}j\epsilon_2 + r\epsilon + \acute{o} + / + t\acute{o}_2 r\acute{e} + uwev\grave{i} \rightarrow$ [ajē r̄ɔ̄tor̄uwēn̄]
 LL Ø Ø (H) LH LLL
 woman AM she ATM burnt house
 LLHLHLL

'a woman that burnt a house'

(Note the final low tone raising affecting the past tense suffix in 181(a) and (c) because these strings end with verbs). In 182 below we present some sample derivations:

182 (a) i) Underlying Representation

ii) by segmentalisation of ATM and delinking of L

iii) by vowel elision

iv) (Phonetic representation)

'the bed that we bought'

(b) i) Underlying Representation

ii) by segmentalisation of ATM and delinking of !H

iii) by glide formation

iv) by deletion of (L)

v) by vowel elision

vi)

(Phonetic Representation)

[ot̄ɔ̄ r̄ɔ̄ḡɔ̄ d̄ɛ̄r̄ j̄ōɛ̄]

'a (parcel of) land in-law bought yesterday'

(c) i) Underlying Representation

ii) by segmentalisation of ATM

iii) by glide formation

iv) by vowel elision

v) by relinking of (H) (vacuous)

vi) Phonetic realisation

'a man who beat a child'

5.4.3 NOUN REDUPLICATION

Like affixation, noun reduplication is a morphological process but it also has important tonal implications. In Urhobo, it is used to express the equivalent of the English noun phrases that signal 'every + noun' and 'only/so many or much + noun'. We name these two types of noun phrases the complete noun reduplication and the partial noun reduplication respectively.

5.4.3.1 COMPLETE NOUN REDUPLICATION

This construction conveys the meaning 'every/each + noun'. Like the associative construction, this noun phrase is marked on both the segmental tier and on the tonal tier. On the segmental tier, it is marked by the occurrence of an independent morpheme, the reduplication marker (RM) /kɛ/ which is underlyingly toneless and occurs before the noun. The entire string, that is, the reduplication marker and the noun, is then

reduplicated. The vowel of this reduplication marker is also obligatorily elided in normal conversational speech but it is recoverable in slow deliberate speech.

On the tonal tier, noun reduplication, whether complete or partial, is marked by the occurrence of a floating high tone which is segmentalised on the final vowel of the first occurrence of the noun resulting in automatic delinking of any inherent tone in that position. The effect of this segmentalisation is vacuous if the delinked tone is also a high tone. We refer to the tonal marker of this construction as the reduplication tone marker (RTM). We shall examine some examples:

183. a) $k\varepsilon + \overset{\cdot}{o}_2 b\overset{\cdot}{\upsilon} + / + k\varepsilon + \overset{\cdot}{o}_2 b\overset{\cdot}{\upsilon}$ ---> $[k\overset{\cdot}{o}b\overset{\cdot}{k}\overset{\cdot}{o}b\overset{\cdot}{\upsilon}]$
 $\emptyset \quad LL \quad (H) \quad \emptyset \quad L \quad L$ LHLL
 RM and RTM RM hand ‘every/each hand’
- b) $k\varepsilon + \overset{\cdot}{u}kpe_1 + / + k\varepsilon + \overset{\cdot}{u}kpe_1$ ---> $[k\overset{\cdot}{u}kpe\overset{\cdot}{k}\overset{\cdot}{u}kpe]$
 $\emptyset \quad HL \quad (H) \quad \emptyset \quad HL$ H H H L
 RM bed RTM RM bed ‘every/each bed’
- c) $k\varepsilon + \overset{\cdot}{e}v\overset{\cdot}{e}_2 + / + k\varepsilon + \overset{\cdot}{e}v\overset{\cdot}{e}_2$ ---> $[k\overset{\cdot}{e}v\overset{\cdot}{e}k\overset{\cdot}{e}v\overset{\cdot}{e}]$
 $\emptyset \quad LH \quad (H) \quad \emptyset \quad LH$ LH LH
 RM goat RTM RM goat ‘every/each goat’
- d) $k\varepsilon + \overset{\cdot}{\upsilon}gba' + / + k\varepsilon + \overset{\cdot}{\upsilon}gba'$ ---> $[k\overset{\cdot}{\upsilon}gba'k\overset{\cdot}{\upsilon}gba']$
 $\emptyset \quad HH \quad (H) \quad \emptyset \quad HH$ H H H H
 RM hero RTM RM hero ‘every/each hero’

- e) $k\varepsilon + \overset{!}{s}\overset{!}{\varepsilon} + / + k\varepsilon + \overset{!}{s}\overset{!}{\varepsilon} \quad \text{--->}$
 $\emptyset \text{ H!H (H) } \emptyset \text{ H!H}$
 RM father RTM RM father
 'every/each father'
 $[k\overset{!}{s}\overset{!}{\varepsilon} k\overset{!}{s}\overset{!}{\varepsilon}]$
 H H H !H
- f) $k\varepsilon + \overset{!}{u}\overset{!}{w}\overset{!}{\varepsilon}_1 \overset{!}{m}\overset{!}{\varepsilon}_1 + / + k\varepsilon + \overset{!}{u}\overset{!}{w}\overset{!}{\varepsilon}_1 \overset{!}{v}\overset{!}{\varepsilon}_1 \quad \text{--->}$
 $\emptyset \text{ L L L (H) } \emptyset \text{ L L L}$
 RM house RTM RM house
 'every/each house'
 $[k\overset{!}{u}\overset{!}{w}\overset{!}{\varepsilon}_1 k\overset{!}{u}\overset{!}{w}\overset{!}{\varepsilon}_1]$
 L L H L L L
- g) $k\varepsilon + \overset{!}{o}_1 \overset{!}{n}\overset{!}{o}_1 \overset{!}{g}\overset{!}{b}\overset{!}{o}_1 / k\varepsilon + \overset{!}{o}_1 \overset{!}{n}\overset{!}{o}_1 \overset{!}{g}\overset{!}{b}\overset{!}{o}_1 \quad \text{--->}$
 $\emptyset \text{ H H L (H) } \emptyset \text{ H H L}$
 RM pussy cat RTM RM pussy cat
 'every/each pussy cat'
 $[k\overset{!}{o}\overset{!}{n}\overset{!}{o}\overset{!}{g}\overset{!}{b}\overset{!}{o} k\overset{!}{o}\overset{!}{n}\overset{!}{o}\overset{!}{g}\overset{!}{b}\overset{!}{o}]$
 H H H H H L
- h) $k\varepsilon + \overset{!}{e}_1 \overset{!}{g}\overset{!}{b}\overset{!}{\varepsilon}_1 \overset{!}{d}\overset{!}{\varepsilon}_1 + / + k\varepsilon + \overset{!}{e}_1 \overset{!}{g}\overset{!}{b}\overset{!}{\varepsilon}_1 \overset{!}{d}\overset{!}{\varepsilon}_1 \quad \text{--->}$
 $\emptyset \text{ L L H (H) } \emptyset \text{ L L H}$
 RM needle RTM RM needle
 'every/each needle'
 $[k\overset{!}{e}\overset{!}{g}\overset{!}{b}\overset{!}{\varepsilon}\overset{!}{d}\overset{!}{\varepsilon} k\overset{!}{e}\overset{!}{g}\overset{!}{b}\overset{!}{\varepsilon}\overset{!}{d}\overset{!}{\varepsilon}]$
 L L H L L H
- i) $k\varepsilon + \overset{!}{a}\overset{!}{g}\overset{!}{o}_2 \overset{!}{g}\overset{!}{o}_2 + / + k\varepsilon + \overset{!}{a}\overset{!}{g}\overset{!}{o}_2 \overset{!}{g}\overset{!}{o}_2 \quad \text{--->}$
 $\emptyset \text{ H H H (H) } \emptyset \text{ H H H}$
 RM metal gong RTM RM metal gong
 'every/each metal gong'
 $[k\overset{!}{a}\overset{!}{g}\overset{!}{o}\overset{!}{g}\overset{!}{o} k\overset{!}{a}\overset{!}{g}\overset{!}{o}\overset{!}{g}\overset{!}{o}]$
 H H H H H H
- j) $k\varepsilon + \overset{!}{o}_1 \overset{!}{r}\overset{!}{\varepsilon}_1 \overset{!}{r}\overset{!}{\varepsilon}_1 + / + k\varepsilon + \overset{!}{o}_1 \overset{!}{r}\overset{!}{\varepsilon}_1 \overset{!}{r}\overset{!}{\varepsilon}_1 \quad \text{--->}$
 $\emptyset \text{ H H!H (H) } \emptyset \text{ H H!H}$
 RM town RTM RM town
 'every/each town'
 $[k\overset{!}{o}\overset{!}{r}\overset{!}{\varepsilon}\overset{!}{r}\overset{!}{\varepsilon} k\overset{!}{o}\overset{!}{r}\overset{!}{\varepsilon}\overset{!}{r}\overset{!}{\varepsilon}]$
 H H H H H !H

We present some sample derivations below:

184. a) i) Underlying Representation

ii) by segmentalisation of RTM and delinking of L

iii) by vowel elision

iv) Phonetic Representation

[kuwē uĩ kuweuĩ] 'every/each house'

b) i) Underlying Representation

R M bed RTM R M bed

ii) by segmentalisation of RTM and delinking of L

iii) by vowel elision

iv) Phonetic Representation

c) i) Underlying Representation

e) i) Underlying Representation

ii) by segmentalisation of RTM and delinking of !H

iii) by vowel elision

iv) Phonetic Representation

5.4.3.2 PARTIAL NOUN REDUPLICATION

This construction conveys the meaning 'only/so many or so much + noun' and affects only the plural form of the noun. Unlike the complete noun reduplication, this construction is marked only on the tonal tier by the reduplication tone marker (RTM). We say that this reduplication is partial because, on the first occurrence of the noun, all other segments, except the prefix vowel and the initial consonant segment(s) of the noun stem, are elided. The retained vowel and consonant segments are then prefixed to the second occurrence of the noun which appears in full.

In surface structure, the tone marker for the construction is borne by the prefix vowel of the noun duplicate. However, we assume that, like in the complete noun reduplication construction, the RTM is also segmentalised on the final vowel of the first noun resulting in the delinking of any inherent tone in that position. Also, all other inherent tones are deleted with the segments that bear them, only the RTM survives and is obligatorily relinked on the adjacent vowel segment which is the prefix vowel of the

noun duplicate, also causing the inherent tone in that position to delink. In either case, the effect of the linking of RTM is vacuous if the two tones are high.

185. a) $\begin{array}{l} \text{\`iwe}_1 \text{ u}_i + / \text{\`iwe}_1 \text{ u}_i \\ \text{LL L (H) LL L} \\ \text{houses RTM houses} \end{array} \quad \text{---->} \quad \begin{array}{l} [\text{\`iwiweu}_i] \\ \text{LHLL} \\ \text{'only/so many houses'} \end{array}$
- b) $\begin{array}{l} \text{\`e}_2 \text{j}\grave{\text{a}} + / \text{\`e}_2 \text{j}\grave{\text{a}} \\ \text{LL (H) LL} \\ \text{women RTM women} \end{array} \quad \text{---->} \quad \begin{array}{l} [\text{\`ejej}\grave{\text{a}}] \\ \text{LHL} \\ \text{'only/so many women'} \end{array}$
- c) $\begin{array}{l} \text{\`igbe}_1 \text{ de}'_1 + / \text{\`igbe}_1 \text{ de}'_1 \\ \text{LLH (H) LLH} \\ \text{needles RTM needles} \end{array} \quad \text{---->} \quad \begin{array}{l} [\text{\`igbigbede}] \\ \text{LHLH} \\ \text{'only/so many needles'} \end{array}$
- d) $\begin{array}{l} \text{\`e}_2 \text{g}\acute{\text{?}} + / \text{\`e}_2 \text{g}\acute{\text{?}} \\ \text{LH (H) LH} \\ \text{bottles RTM bottles} \end{array} \quad \text{---->} \quad \begin{array}{l} [\text{\`egeg}\acute{\text{?}}] \\ \text{LHH} \\ \text{'only/so many bottles'} \end{array}$
- e) $\begin{array}{l} \text{\`ikpe}_1 + / \text{\`ikpe}_1 \\ \text{HL (H) HL} \\ \text{beds RTM beds} \end{array} \quad \text{---->} \quad \begin{array}{l} [\text{\`ikpikpe}] \\ \text{HHL} \\ \text{'only/so many beds'} \end{array}$
- f) $\begin{array}{l} \text{\`e}_2 \text{gba}' + / \text{\`e}_2 \text{gba}' \\ \text{HH (H) HH} \\ \text{heros RTM heros} \end{array} \quad \text{---->} \quad \begin{array}{l} [\text{\`egbegba}] \\ \text{HHH} \\ \text{'only/so many heros'} \end{array}$

- g) $\begin{matrix} / & / \\ \text{ibro}_1 & + / & \text{ibro}_1 \end{matrix} \quad \text{-----} \rightarrow \quad \begin{matrix} / & \bar{ } \\ \text{[ibribo]} \end{matrix}$
- H !H (H) H !H H H !H
- halves RTM halves ‘only halves’
- h) $\begin{matrix} / & / & / \\ \text{ire}_1\text{re}_1 & + / & \text{ire}_1\text{re}_1 \end{matrix} \quad \text{-----} \rightarrow \quad \begin{matrix} / & / & \bar{ } \\ \text{[irirere]} \end{matrix}$
- HH !H (H) HH !H HHH !H
- towns RTM towns ‘only/so many towns’

We present some sample derivations below:

186. a) i) Underlying Representation

ii) by segmentalisation of RTM and delinking of L

iii) by deletion of segments from N1

iv) by relinking of (H) and delinking of L

v) Phonetic representation

 [iwiweɿ] 'only/so many houses'

b) i) Underlying Representation

bottles RTM bottles

ii) by segmentalisation of RTM and delinking of (H) (vacuous)

iii) by deletion of segments from N1

iv) by relinking of (H) and delinking of L

v) Phonetic Representation

c) i) Underlying Representation

ii) by segmentalisation of RTM and delinking of L

iii) by deletion of segments from N1

iv) by relinking of (H) (vacuous)

v) Phonetic Representation

d) i) Underlying Representation

ii) by segmentalisation of (H) and delinking of !H

iii) by deletion of segments from N1

iv) by relinking of (H) (vacuous)

v) Phonetic representation

[irirere] 'so many towns'

We have, in this chapter, examined tonal alternations in the noun phrase. In non-associative noun phrases, tonal alternations were necessitated by phonological processes such as vowel elision and glide formation at morpheme or word boundaries which set tones borne by the affected vowel segments afloat. These floating tones were shown to either elide with their vowel segments or relink onto the following vowel segment and the result is either the delinking of the following tone, the creation of contour tones or a vacuous application.

The associative construction and the complete noun reduplication are marked on both the segmental tier by an independent morpheme and on the tonal tier by a floating high tone. This floating high tone, by surface structure, is borne by a vowel of the second noun - the prefix vowel in the case of the Noun + Noun and the complete noun reduplication constructions, and the final vowel in the case of the Noun + Relative Clause construction. The partial noun reduplication which is marked only on the tonal tier realises the floating high tone on the prefix vowel of the second noun.

We shall now turn our attention to tonal alternations in verbal constructions.

CHAPTER SIX

TONAL ALTERNATIONS IN VERBAL CONSTRUCTIONS

6.1 INTRODUCTION

Most simple verb stems in Urhobo are either monosyllabic or disyllabic and begin with at least a consonant segment. There are no minimal pairs in the Urhobo verb class which differ in meaning only as a result of a difference in tone patterning. Thus, whereas we can classify nouns according to their tone patterning, verbs cannot be so classified. In the citation form and when they are not bearing a tomorph, all verbs and all monosyllabic subject and object pronouns are realised on the low tone. Although a number of tonal alternations are attested in the verb, these are usually motivated by the different grammatical configurations in which they function. Consequently, all verbs with the same syllable structure will behave alike in the same grammatical configuration. In other words, all monosyllabic verbs will behave alike in the same grammatical construction just like all disyllabic verbs will behave alike. It is for reasons such as these that the Urhobo verb class and the monosyllabic subject and object pronouns are usually regarded as being underlyingly toneless and receive tone depending on the grammatical construction in which they function (cf Elugbe 1973, 1989a). In this section, we shall follow this assumption and indicate verbs and monosyllabic subject and object pronouns in the underlying representation as toneless.

be single tone units or tonal melodies (that is, fixed tonal patterns) that are grammatically significant and exist independently of segmental phonological strings. They are also quite distinct from inherent or lexical tones. They are obligatorily segmentalised in appropriate positions within the grammatical configuration and their segmentalisation often causes inherent tones to delink or at best, form a glide. In other words, linked tomorphs often set lexical tones afloat but lexical tones may or may not be relinked.

In this section, we shall consider various grammatical constructions in the three basic tenses of the language, namely, the present tense, the past tense and the future tense. We are limiting ourselves to these three tenses because the others are indicated by the occurrence of independent morphemes attached to constructions in these three tenses.

Let us consider some examples:

188. (a) $\dot{\text{D}} + \text{d}\acute{\text{e}} + \dot{\text{z}}\text{n}\acute{\text{e}} + \text{n}\grave{\text{u}}\text{r}\acute{\text{e}}_1 \rightarrow [\dot{\text{D}}\text{d}\acute{\text{o}}\text{n}\acute{\text{e}} \text{n}\grave{\text{u}}\text{r}\acute{\text{e}}]$
 L H L H L H
 he bought yam completed 'he has/had bought yam'
- (b) $\acute{\text{e}}\text{s}\grave{\text{e}}_2 + \text{t}\grave{\text{o}}_2\text{r}\acute{\text{e}} + \acute{\text{a}}\text{y}\acute{\text{u}}\acute{\text{a}} + \text{n}\grave{\text{u}}\text{r}\acute{\text{e}}_1 \rightarrow [\acute{\text{e}} \text{s}\grave{\text{e}} \text{t}\acute{\text{o}}\text{r}\acute{\text{a}}\text{w}\acute{\text{a}} \text{n}\grave{\text{u}}\text{r}\acute{\text{e}}]$
 HL L H H H L H
 Name burnt bush completed 'Ese has/had burnt a bush'
- (c) $\acute{\text{e}}_1\text{z}\grave{\text{i}}\text{r}\acute{\text{o}}_1 + \text{s}\acute{\text{e}}_1 + \grave{\text{o}}_1\text{h}\acute{\text{u}}\acute{\text{o}}_1 + \text{n}\grave{\text{u}}\text{r}\acute{\text{e}}_1 \rightarrow [\acute{\text{e}}\text{z}\grave{\text{i}}\text{r}\acute{\text{o}} \text{s}\acute{\text{o}}\text{x}\text{w}\acute{\text{o}} \text{n}\grave{\text{u}}\text{r}\acute{\text{e}}]$
 HL H H L H H L H
 Name called person completed 'Ejiro has/had called a person'

(d) $\hat{\text{ɔ}} + \text{d}\acute{\text{e}} + \text{ɔ̀n}\acute{\text{e}} + \text{n}\grave{\text{u}}\acute{\text{r}}\acute{\text{e}}$ --> $[\hat{\text{ɔ}}\text{d}\acute{\text{ɔ}}\text{n}\acute{\text{e}} \text{n}\grave{\text{u}}\acute{\text{r}}\acute{\text{e}}]$
 $\widehat{\text{H}}\text{L} \quad \text{H} \quad \text{LH} \quad \text{LH}$ HL HH L H
 he+future bought yam completed ‘he should have bought
yam by now’

(e) $\acute{\text{e}}\hat{\text{s}}\acute{\text{e}}_2 + \text{s}\acute{\text{e}}_1 + \text{òh}\acute{\text{u}}\acute{\text{o}}_1 + \text{ɔ̀n}\grave{\text{a}} + \text{n}\grave{\text{u}}\acute{\text{r}}\acute{\text{e}}$ -->
 $\text{H}\widehat{\text{H}}\text{L} \quad \text{H} \quad \text{L} \quad \text{HH} \quad \text{LL} \quad \text{LH}$
 Name+future called person the completed
 $[\acute{\text{e}}\hat{\text{s}}\acute{\text{e}} \text{s}\acute{\text{o}}\text{xw}\acute{\text{o}} \text{n}\grave{\text{a}} \text{n}\grave{\text{u}}\acute{\text{r}}\acute{\text{e}}]$
 $\text{L} \widehat{\text{H}}\text{L} \quad \text{H} \quad \text{H} \quad \text{L} \quad \text{L} \quad \text{H}$

‘Ese should have called the person by now’

The sentences in 188 a-c are sentences in the present/past perfect. Apart from the occurrence of the morpheme /nùré/ which means ‘completed’ attached at the end of the construction, everything else about the sentences indicate constructions in the simple past tense. Similarly, those in 188 d-e are in the future perfect and this is indicated by the morpheme attached at the end of the sentence. We shall, therefore, be examining tonal alternations in the three basic tenses only. Like in the noun phrases considered in the last chapter, the importance of floating tones or tonal morphemes is even more obvious in verbal constructions.

Before we go into the main discussion, it is necessary to describe the structure of our simple sentence. It may be schematised as in 189 below.

189. The structure of the Urbobo simple sentence

In the structure above, S stands for the simple sentence, NP stands for the subject noun phrase and VP stands for the verb phrase. The subject noun phrase may be composed of any one of the following: a noun, a subject pronoun, or a noun phrase. The VP component comprises the verb, the object and the adverbial. The verb is the only obligatory part of the verb phrase while the object and adverbial elements are optional and this is indicated by the brackets around them. The verb may be monosyllabic, disyllabic or even a complex verb. Information regarding tense is usually borne between the subject noun phrase and the verb stem. If the verb stem is followed by another element within the verb phrase which begins with a prefix vowel, the final vowel of the verb stem is obligatorily elided or undergoes glide formation and if this verb stem vowel was bearing the tense tomorph the tomorph obligatorily relinks on the adjacent vowel segment and this may result in tonal alternations taking place on that vowel segment. The verb stem may be preceded by an auxiliary or a particle (as in the future tense construction) or has a suffix attached to it (as when a string in the past tense ends with

the verb). The object may be composed of a noun, an object pronoun or a noun phrase. The adverbial component comprises adverbs and adverbials that indicate time, manner and/or place of action.

We shall now proceed to examine the tenses, beginning with the present tense.

6.2 THE PRESENT TENSE

The present tense construction in Urhobo is used to convey a habitual as well as a present or continuous action. The morpheme marking the tense is a floating high tone which occurs at the end of the subject noun phrase. In order for this tomorph to be realised, the final vowel of the subject noun phrase is slightly lengthened to accommodate it. Thus, if the subject noun phrase already ends on a high tone, it is easy to perceive a lengthening of both the high tone and the final vowel. If, on the other hand, the subject noun phrase ends on a low tone, the present tense tomorph is segmentalised on the lengthened portion of the final vowel. As mentioned earlier, when the subject pronoun or verb is not bearing a tomorph, it is realised on the low tone. Consequently, the first part of the vowel bears a low tone while the lengthened portion bears the high tone. Let us

consider some examples:

190. (a) $\overset{\wedge}{\epsilon} \overset{\backslash}{se_2} + / + d\epsilon$ --> $[\overset{\wedge}{\epsilon} \overset{\backslash}{se_2} \overset{\wedge}{d\epsilon}]$
 H L (H) $\emptyset$ HLH L
 Name Present tomorph buy 'Ese buys/is buying'

- (b) $\acute{e}_1 \text{ } \grave{z} \text{ } \acute{i} \text{ } \acute{r} \acute{o}_1 + / + \text{ da}$ $\rightarrow$ $[\acute{e} \text{ } \grave{z} \text{ } \acute{i} \text{ } \acute{r} \acute{o} \text{ } \acute{o} \text{ } \acute{d} \text{ } \acute{a}]$
 H L H (H) $\emptyset$ HL H H L
 Name present tomorph drink 'Ejiro drinks/is drinking'
- (c) $o_1 + / + se_1$ $\rightarrow$ $[\acute{o} \text{ } \acute{o} \text{ } \acute{s} \acute{e}]$
 $\emptyset$ (H) $\emptyset$ L H L
 he present tomorph read 'he reads/is reading'
- (d) $\acute{z} \acute{s} \acute{e} + / + \text{ da} + \grave{u} \acute{d} \acute{i}$ $\rightarrow$ $[\acute{z} \text{ } \acute{s} \acute{e} \text{ } \acute{d} \text{ } \acute{u} \text{ } \acute{d} \text{ } \acute{i}]$
 H! H (H) $\emptyset$ L L H ! H H L L
 father drink present tomorph a drink 'father drinks/is drinking'
- (e) $\acute{z} \acute{g} \acute{b} \acute{a} + \grave{z} \acute{n} \acute{a} + / + \text{ } \acute{s} \text{ } \acute{e} + \acute{i} \acute{k} \acute{o}_1$ $\rightarrow$ $[\acute{z} \acute{g} \acute{b} \acute{a} \text{ } \acute{n} \acute{a} \acute{s} \text{ } \acute{i} \acute{k} \acute{o}]$
 H H L L (H) $\emptyset$ H H H H L H H H
 herothe present tomorph sell cups 'the hero sells/is selling cup'

We illustrate with some sample derivations below: (Pr. T stands for the Present tomorph)

ii) by segmentalisation of present tomorph and lengthening of final vowel of subject NP.

iii) H L (H) L Phonetic realisation

[^ˆε^ˈe^ˈe^ˈ d^ˈε] 'Ese buys/is buying'

b) i) (H) Underlying representation

he Present tomorph read

- ii) by segmentalisation of present tomorph and lengthening of final vowel of subject NP

- iii)

Phonetic realisation

[o o se] 'he reads/is reading'

- c)(i)

ii) by segmentalisation of present tomorph and lengthening of final vowel of NP

When, in this construction, we have both a direct and an indirect object, some additional tonal alternations occur. Let us present some examples for now.

192. (a) $\overset{\prime}{\text{e}}\overset{\prime}{\text{s}}\overset{\prime}{\text{e}}_2 + / + \text{ku} + \overset{\prime}{\text{u}}\overset{\prime}{\text{d}}\overset{\prime}{\text{i}} + \text{k}\epsilon + \overset{\prime}{\text{e}}\overset{\prime}{\text{j}}\overset{\prime}{\text{i}}\overset{\prime}{\text{r}}\overset{\prime}{\text{o}}_1 \text{--->}$
 H L (H) $\emptyset$ L L $\emptyset$ H L H

Name present tomorph pour a drink for Name

[$\overset{\prime}{\text{e}}\overset{\prime}{\text{s}}\overset{\prime}{\text{e}}\overset{\prime}{\text{e}} \text{ kwu}\overset{\prime}{\text{d}}\overset{\prime}{\text{i}} \text{ k}\epsilon\overset{\prime}{\text{j}}\overset{\prime}{\text{i}}\overset{\prime}{\text{r}}\overset{\prime}{\text{o}}$]

H L H L H H L H

'Ese is pouring Ejiro a drink'

(b) $\text{ɔ} + / + \text{d}\epsilon + \overset{\prime}{\text{a}}\overset{\prime}{\text{d}}\overset{\prime}{\text{a}}\overset{\prime}{\text{m}}\overset{\prime}{\text{a}} + \text{k}\epsilon + \overset{\prime}{\text{a}}\overset{\prime}{\text{j}}\overset{\prime}{\text{e}}_2 \text{--->}$

$\emptyset$ (H) $\emptyset$ L H $\emptyset$ L L

he present tomorph buy cloth for them

[$\overset{\prime}{\text{ɔ}}\overset{\prime}{\text{ɔ}}\overset{\prime}{\text{d}}\overset{\prime}{\text{a}}\overset{\prime}{\text{m}}\overset{\prime}{\text{a}} \text{ k}\overset{\prime}{\text{a}}\overset{\prime}{\text{j}}\overset{\prime}{\text{e}}$]

L H L H L L

'he is buying a cloth for them'

(c) $\overset{\prime}{\text{ɔ}}\overset{\prime}{\text{g}}\overset{\prime}{\text{b}}\overset{\prime}{\text{a}} + / + \text{f}\overset{\prime}{\text{i}} + \overset{\prime}{\text{i}}\overset{\prime}{\text{j}}\overset{\prime}{\text{o}}_1 + \text{k}\epsilon + \overset{\prime}{\text{ɔ}}\overset{\prime}{\text{s}}\overset{\prime}{\text{e}} \text{-->}$

H H (H) $\emptyset$ H!H $\emptyset$ H!H

hero present tomorph throw money at father

[$\overset{\prime}{\text{ɔ}}\overset{\prime}{\text{g}}\overset{\prime}{\text{b}}\overset{\prime}{\text{a}}\overset{\prime}{\text{a}} \text{ f}\overset{\prime}{\text{j}}\overset{\prime}{\text{i}}\overset{\prime}{\text{j}}\overset{\prime}{\text{o}} \text{ k}\overset{\prime}{\text{ɔ}}\overset{\prime}{\text{s}}\overset{\prime}{\text{e}}$]

H H H H H H!H

'a hero is "spraying" father with money'

(d) ɔ+ / + dɛ + \u028ad\u028a + kɛ + vɛ -->

∅ (H) ∅ LL ∅ ∅

he Present tomorph buy a drink for me

[ɔɔ\u028ad\u028a k \u028av\u028a]

LH L H L L

'he is buying me a drink'

From the examples above, it is obvious that the indirect object is introduced both segmentally by a conjunctive element /kɛ / and tonally by ensuring that the final vowel of the direct object is realised on the high tone, irrespective of the type of inherent tone in that position. The conjunctive element is equivalent to the English prepositions 'for' or 'at' and is underlyingly toneless. Its vowel segment is always elided when it immediately precedes a noun object.

To account for the tonal alternation on the final vowel of the direct object, we propose a floating high tone whose function is to link the two objects. We name this floating tone the object tone marker (OTM) and it is obligatorily segmentalised on the final vowel segment of the direct object resulting in the automatic delinking of the inherent tone in that position. However, the effect of this segmentalisation is vacuous if the inherent tone is also a high. We also propose that the segmentalisation of this second floating high tone is ordered immediately after the segmentalisation of the present tomorph. It is important to order the segmentalisation of the two floating tones

separately because they create different effects on adjacent tones. Whereas the tense tomorph does not cause the inherent tone of the subject noun phrase to delink, resulting instead in the creation of a contour tone if the subject noun phrase ends on a low tone, the object tone marker causes the inherent tone to delink obligatorily. We shall illustrate by presenting some sample derivations.

193. (a) (I) Underlying representation:

Name present tomorph pour a drink OTM for Name

(ii) by segmentalisation of present tomorph and lengthening of final vowel of subject NP

(iii) by segmentalisation of OTM and delinking of L

(iv) by glide formation

(v) by vowel elision

(vi) Phonetic realisation

[εsēé kwudī kēʒiro] 'Ese is pouring Ejiro a drink'

(b)(i) Underlying representation

he Present tomorph buy cloth OTM for them

ii) by segmentalisation of present tomorph and lengthening of final vowel of subject NP

iii) by segmentalisation of OTM (vacuous)

iv) by vowel elision

v) Phonetic realisation

[ɔ́ dǎɣ̃mā kǎjě] 'he is buying cloth for them'

(c) i) Underlying representation

hero present tomorph throw money OTM at father

ii) by segmentalisation of present tomorph and lengthening of final vowel of subject NP

iii) by segmentalisation of OTM and delinking !H

iv) by glide formation

v) by vowel elision

vi) Phonetic realisation

[ɔgbaa' fjʒo' kɔ'se] 'a hero is "spraying" father with money'

(b) $\text{ɔ} + \text{to}_2\text{r}_\epsilon \text{ re}_2 + / \quad \text{--->} \quad [\text{ɔ} \text{to}_2\text{r}_\epsilon \text{ r}_\epsilon]$
 (H) L L H L

he burnt past tomorph 'he got burnt'

(c) $\text{ɛ} \text{ u}_\epsilon + \text{jere}_2 + / \quad \text{--->} \quad [\text{ɛ} \text{u}_\epsilon \text{ j}_\epsilon \text{r}_\epsilon]$
 L H (H) L H H L

goat ran past tomorph 'a goat ran away'

(d) $\text{ɔ} \text{ s}_\epsilon + \text{de} \text{ re}_2 + / + \text{ɔ} \text{ n}_\epsilon \quad \text{--->} \quad [\text{ɔ} \text{s}_\epsilon \text{ d}_\epsilon \text{ n}_\epsilon]$
 H !H (H) L H H !H H H

father bought past *yam* 'father bought yam'

(e) $\text{ɛ} \text{ s}_\epsilon + \text{to}_\epsilon \text{ re}_2 + / + \text{u}_\epsilon \text{ w}_\epsilon \text{ u}_\epsilon \quad \text{--->} \quad [\text{ɛ} \text{s}_\epsilon \text{ to}_\epsilon \text{ r}_\epsilon \text{ u}_\epsilon \text{ w}_\epsilon \text{ u}_\epsilon]$
 H L (H) L L L H L L H L L

Name burnt past house 'Ese burnt a house'

(f) $\text{ɔ} \text{ m}_\epsilon + \text{jre}_2 \text{ re}_2 + / + \text{i}_\epsilon \text{ o}_\epsilon \quad \text{--->} \quad [\text{ɔ} \text{m}_\epsilon \text{ j}_\epsilon \text{r}_\epsilon \text{ r}_\epsilon \text{ i}_\epsilon \text{o}_\epsilon]$
 H H (H) H !H H H L H !H

child held past *money* 'a child held money'

The first three sentences in 194 above have no noun objects while the last three sentences do. It will be noticed that it is only the tone of the final vowel of the verb stem that is affected by tonal alternations, and where this vowel is elided, the prefix vowel of the noun object may be affected by tonal alternations. All other tones are as in their citation form, except the final low tone of the verb suffix which is realised on a raised

level. We believe that this low raising is an intonational factor and not due to tone spreading since, if it was, it should have been a more general principle, not restricted to verb suffix alone. In 195 below, we illustrate with some sample derivations. (Note: L^R stands for a raised low tone)

195. a) (i)

(H)

Underlying representation

he bought past tomorph

ii)

(H)

by segmentalisation of past tomorph

iii)

Phonetic realisation

[ɔ̃ dɛ́ rē] 'he bought'

underlying representation

goat ran past tomorph'

by segmentalisation of past tomorph

phonetic realisation

[εvε jεrε] 'a goat ran away'

(Note that the downstepping of the two final high tones in the phonetic string is due to the presence of an inherent downstep preceding them; it has nothing to do with the lost low tone)

We now examine past tense constructions in which we have both a direct and an indirect object. The following are some examples.

196. (a) [ẹ́j̣ ị ṛ ọ ḍ ạ ṃ ạ́ ḳ ẹ ṣ ẹ] 'Ejro bought a cloth for Ese'
- (b) [ɔ̣ ṣ ẹ ḍ ɔ̣ ṇ ẹ ḳ ạ j̣ ẹ] 'father bought yam for a woman'
- (c) [ɔ̣ ḍ ụ ḍ ị ḳ ɔ̣ ṃ ɔ̣] 'he bought a drink for a child'
- (d) [ɔ̣ ḍ ɔ̣ ṇ ẹ ḳ ẹ ṣ ẹ] 'he bought yam for Ese'
- (e) [ọ f̣ j̣ ị ɔ̣ ḳ ẹ ṣ ẹ] 'he 'sprayed' Ese with money'

The conjunctive particle /kɛ / also conjoins the direct and indirect objects and if the indirect object begins with a vowel, the vowel of the conjunctive particle is also elided.

However, whereas in the present tense construction the final vowel of the direct object obligatorily bears a high tone, in the past tense construction, tonal alternations occur on the final vowel of the direct object only if the two tones at the boundary between the two objects are high in the phonetic representation. In other words, if one or both of the tones at this boundary is a low or a downstep, tonal alternation does not

occur on the direct object. Thus, in 196(a) and (d), we have a high-low (falling) contour on the final vowel of the direct object which is absent from the other three examples in 196(b), (c) and (e).

To account for this situation, we propose a floating low tone between the direct and indirect objects. This floating low tone is segmentalised on the final vowel of the direct object but is given phonetic realisation only if the direct object ends with a high tone and the indirect object begins with a high tone also. The realisation of this floating tone is blocked if at least one of the tones at this boundary is a low or a non-automatic downstep, in which case, it is deleted from the phonetic string. So, unlike in the present tense construction where the high tone in a similar environment is obligatorily segmentalised and causes delinking for an inherent tone, in the past tense construction the low tone in this position has constraints attached to its realisation. However, there is a similarity in the sense that both the present and the past tense constructions have what we have called an object tone marker (OTM). We can then say that this tone marker has two variants, namely, a high tone variant if the string is in the present tense and a low tone variant if the string is in the past tense. The dominance of the high tone in this language is demonstrated in the object tone marker such that the high toned variant is obligatorily phonetically realised but the low toned variant observes some constraints in its realisation, although it is also obligatorily segmentalised in the underlying representation. To account for the constraint, we propose the following rule:

197: Past Tense Object Tone Marker Constraint:

Delete past tense object tone marker (OTM) if both or one of final tone of direct object and prefix tone of indirect object is a low or a downstep. With this rule in place, we can now derive the past tense forms with both direct and indirect objects:

198. Sample derivation.

a) i) Underlying representation.

ii) by segmentalisation of past tomorph

vi) by relinking of (H) and delinking of L

vii) Phonetic realisation

[eʒi r o d a ĵ m̂ a k ε s e] 'Ejiro bought a cloth for Ese'

b) (i) Underlying representation

ii) by segmentalisation of past tomorph

iii) by segmentalisation of OTM

iv) by delinking and deletion of OTM

v) by deletion of verb suffix

vi) by vowel elision

vii) by relinking of (H) and delinking of L

viii) Phonetic realisation

'father bought yam for a woman'

c) (i) Underlying representation

he bought past tomorph a drink OTM for child

ii) by segmentalisation of past tomorph

iii) by sementalisation of OTM

iv) by delinking of and deletion of OTM

v) by deletion of verb suffix

vi) by vowel elision

vii) by relinking of (H) and delinking of L

viii) Phonetic realisation

'he bought a child a drink'

d) (i) Underlying representation

he sold past tomorph money OTM for name

ii) by segmentalisation of past tomorph

iii) by segmentalisation of OTM

iv) by delinking and deletion of OTM

v) by deletion of verb suffix

vi) by vowel elision

vii) by relinking of (H) (vacuous)

viii) Phonetic realisation

'he sold money to Ese'

From the behaviour of the tones in the sequences just considered, it is obvious that the tone groups the nouns in the direct and indirect object positions belong to play a role in the realisation of this OTM variant. For it to be realised both the tones at the boundary between the direct and indirect objects must be high, otherwise it is deleted from the phonetic string. We believe that our proposal that it is obligatorily segmentalised but that its realisation may be blocked by the type of tones at the boundary

- b) $\acute{o}_1 \text{ c}\grave{e}_1 \text{ c}\acute{e}_1 \text{ r}\acute{e}_1$ $\rightarrow$ [$\acute{o} \text{ c}\bar{e} \text{ c}\bar{e}\bar{r}\bar{e}$]
 H L H H
 'she will cook'
- c) $\acute{\text{c}} \text{ c}\grave{a} \text{ j}\acute{\text{c}} \text{ r}\acute{e}_2 \text{ u}\grave{\text{d}}\text{i}$ $\rightarrow$ [$\acute{\text{c}} \text{ c}\bar{a} \text{ j}\bar{\text{c}} \text{ r}\bar{e}_2 \text{ u}\bar{\text{d}}\text{i}$]
 H L H H L L
 HL HHL
 'he will hold a drink'
- d) $\acute{m}\text{i} \text{ c}\grave{e}_1 \text{ h}\acute{u}\acute{e}_1 \text{ \text{e}}\text{s}\grave{e}_2$ $\rightarrow$ [$\acute{m}\text{i} \text{ c}\bar{e} \text{ xw} \text{ \text{e}}\bar{s}\bar{e}$]
 H L HH HL
 H L HL 'I will beat Ese'
- e) $\acute{\text{c}} \text{ \text{a}}\text{r}\acute{e}_2 \text{ \text{c}} \text{ n}\acute{a} \text{ c}\grave{a} \text{ d}\acute{\text{e}} \text{ \text{c}} \text{ b}\acute{e}_2$ $\rightarrow$ [$\acute{\text{c}} \text{ \text{a}}\text{r}\bar{e}_2 \text{ n}\bar{a} \text{ c}\bar{a} \text{ d}\bar{e} \text{ \text{c}} \text{ b}\bar{e}_2$]
 HLL LHL HLL
 HLL H L HL
 'the man will buy a book'
- f) $\acute{\text{e}}\text{s}\acute{e}_2 \text{ c}\grave{a} \text{ \text{y}} \text{ \text{a}}\text{r}\acute{e}_2 \text{ \text{e}}_2 \text{ n}\acute{\text{e}}$ $\rightarrow$ [$\acute{\text{e}}\text{s}\acute{e} \text{ c}\bar{a} \text{ \text{y}} \text{ \text{a}}\bar{r}\bar{e}_2 \text{ \text{e}}_2 \text{ n}\bar{e}$]
 HH LHH LH
 HH L HH H
 'Ese will share out yams'
- g) $\acute{\text{c}} \text{ g}\acute{b}\acute{a} \text{ c}\grave{e}_1 \text{ h}\acute{u}\acute{e}_2 \text{ \text{c}} \text{ m}\acute{\text{c}} \text{ \text{c}} \text{ n}\acute{a}$ $\rightarrow$ [$\acute{\text{c}} \text{ g}\bar{b}\bar{a} \text{ c}\bar{e} \text{ xw} \text{ \text{c}} \text{ m}\bar{\text{c}} \text{ \text{c}} \text{ n}\bar{a}$]
 H H L H H HH LL
 H H L HHL
 'a hero will beat the child'
- h) $\acute{\text{c}} \text{ s}\acute{e} \text{ c}\grave{a} \text{ t}\acute{o}_2 \text{ r}\acute{e} \text{ u}\acute{k}\text{p}\acute{e}_1$ $\rightarrow$ [$\acute{\text{c}} \text{ s}\bar{e} \text{ c}\bar{a} \text{ t}\bar{o}_2 \text{ r}\bar{e} \text{ u}\bar{k}\bar{p}\bar{e}_1$]
 HH L H HHL
 HH L HHL
 'father will burn a bed'

From the examples above, it is obvious that tonal alternations result from the segmentalisation of the two floating high tones marking the future tense. The segmentalisation of the first high tone of the subject noun phrase results in the automatic delinking of an inherent tone in that position. (This is unlike what happens with the present tomorph the segmentalisation of which results in the lengthening of the final vowel of the subject noun phrase in order to accommodate the tomorph). In the case of the second high tone of the future tense, this tone spreads onto other vowel segments within the verb stem if the verb stem is other than monosyllabic. This is unlike the past tense tomorph which does not spread. However, like the past tense tomorph, if the final vowel segment of the verb stem is deleted, this tomorph obligatorily relinks and the result is automatic delinking for a following inherent tone. In each case, the effect of segmentalisation is vacuous if the inherent tone is also a high. Let us illustrate with some derivations. (FTM stands for Future Tense Marker)

200. Sample derivations

a) i)

(H-L-H) Underlying representation

c)i) Underlying representation

ii) by segmentalisation of FTM and delinking of inherent tone

iii) by vowel elision

iv) by (H) relinking and L delinking

v) Phonetic representation

[ʃàrè nā cà dāʃā] 'the man will buy a broom'

d) i) Underlying representation

ii) by segmentalisation of FTM and delinking of inherent tone

iii) by spreading of second H of FTM

iv) by vowel elision

v) by (H) relinking (vacuous)

vi) Phonetic Representation

[ɔ́sɛ́ cǎ tór̥kpe] 'father will burn a bed'

e)i) Underlying representation

ii) by segmentalisation of FTM (vacuous on inherent tone)

iii) by glide formation

iv) by vowel elision

v) by (H) relinking (vacuous)

vi) Phonetic Representation

[ɔ̄ gbá cè xw̄ ɔ̄ m̄ nà] 'a hero will beat the boy'

Again, when the verb takes both a direct and an indirect object, we have a

situation that is similar to that found in identical constructions in the past tense. The following are some examples:

201. a) ɔ̄ cá dɛ́ aɲmá kɛ́ ɛ́sɛ₂ ----> [ɔ̄ cá d̄aɲm̄á kɛ́ sɛ̀]
 H L H L H(L) Ø HL 'he will buy a cloth for Ese'
- b) ɛ̄₁ ʒ̄iɾo₁ cá dɛ́ ūdì kɛ́ ɛ́ sɛ₂ ----> [ɛ̄₁ ʒ̄iɾō cá d̄ūdì kɛ́ sɛ̀]
 H LH L HLL Ø HL 'Ejiro will buy Ese a drink'

- c) $mí\ cè_1\ fí\ i\ yó_1\ k\epsilon\ \bar{\bar{c}}\bar{\bar{s}}\bar{\bar{e}}' \rightarrow [mí\ cè\ f\ j\ i\ y\bar{o}\ k\bar{\bar{c}}\bar{\bar{s}}\bar{\bar{e}}]$
 H L H H !H $\emptyset$ H !H
 H L H !H H !H
 'I will 'spray' father with money'
- d) $\bar{\bar{c}}\bar{\bar{a}}\bar{\bar{r}}\bar{\bar{e}}_2\ c\bar{a}\ d\bar{e}\ \bar{\bar{c}}\bar{\bar{b}}\bar{\bar{e}}_2\ k\bar{\bar{e}}\ \bar{\bar{a}}\bar{\bar{j}}\bar{\bar{e}}_2 \rightarrow [\bar{\bar{c}}\bar{\bar{a}}\bar{\bar{r}}\bar{\bar{e}}\ c\bar{a}\ d\bar{\bar{c}}\bar{\bar{b}}\bar{\bar{e}}\ k\bar{\bar{a}}\bar{\bar{j}}\bar{\bar{e}}]$
 HLH L HLL $\emptyset$ LL
 HLH L HL L L
 'a man will buy a book for a woman'
- e) $\bar{\bar{c}}\bar{\bar{m}}\bar{\bar{c}}\bar{\bar{a}}\ d\bar{e}\ \bar{\bar{c}}\bar{\bar{n}}\bar{\bar{e}}\ k\bar{\bar{e}}\ \bar{\bar{a}}\bar{\bar{j}}\bar{\bar{e}}_2 \rightarrow [\bar{\bar{c}}\bar{\bar{m}}\bar{\bar{c}}\bar{\bar{a}}\ d\bar{\bar{c}}\bar{\bar{n}}\bar{\bar{e}}\ \bar{\bar{k}}\bar{\bar{a}}\bar{\bar{j}}\bar{\bar{e}}]$
 HH L H L H $\emptyset$ L L
 H HL HH LL
 'a child will buy yam for a woman'

Between the verb stem and the direct object as well as between the direct and indirect object, we find the same tonal alternations identified in the past tense. The verb stem vowel bears a high tone which, after vowel elision has taken place, gets obligatorily segmentalised on the prefix vowel of the direct object. Similarly, in the boundary between the final vowel of the direct object and the prefix vowel of the indirect object, we notice that when both tones are high, a low tone is attached to that before the boundary which results in a HL sequence and consequently, the following high tone is realised as a downstep. In all other situations, namely L#H, !H # H, L # L, H # L, no such glide occurs. Thus, the only differences between the past tense and the future, apart from the low toned auxiliary /ca/ ~ /ce/, are the high tone which is segmentalised on the final vowel of the subject noun phrase and which causes an inherent low or non-automatic downstep

to delink and the fact that the high tone borne by the vowel of the verb stem can spread to other syllables within the verb stem.

One other construction that is in every way identical with the future tense except for the absence of the auxiliary /ce/ ~ /ca/ is the construction that describes an action that is urged or required, in other words, an assured future action. As a result of the absence of the auxiliary in this construction, both the high tone borne by the only or final vowel segment of the subject noun phrase and the low tone borne by the auxiliary are segmentalised on the final vowel of the subject noun phrase resulting in a HL contour. There is no vowel lengthening. Let us examine some examples:

202. a) $\overset{\hat{H}}{m\acute{e}_2} \text{ } \overset{\hat{H}}{d\acute{e}}$ ---> 'I should (must, certainly will) buy'

$\overset{\hat{H}}{HL} \text{ } H$

b) $\overset{\hat{H}}{\text{ʒare}_2} \overset{\hat{H}}{\text{ɔn}\acute{a}} \text{ } \overset{\hat{H}}{t\acute{o}_2r\acute{e}} \text{ } \overset{\hat{H}}{\varepsilon} \overset{\hat{H}}{v\acute{e}_2}$ ---> $[\overset{\hat{H}}{\text{ʒare}} \overset{\hat{H}}{\text{n}\acute{a}} \overset{\hat{H}}{\text{tor}} \overset{\hat{H}}{\varepsilon} \overset{\hat{H}}{ve}]$

$H \text{ } L \text{ } L \text{ } L \overset{\hat{H}}{HL} \text{ } H \text{ } H \text{ } L \text{ } H$

$H \text{ } L \text{ } L \text{ } HL \text{ } H \text{ } H \text{ } H$

'the man must or should burn a goat'

c) $\overset{\hat{H}}{\text{ʒs}\acute{e}} \overset{\hat{H}}{d\acute{e}} \text{ } \overset{\hat{H}}{u\acute{k}\acute{o}_1}$ ---> $[\overset{\hat{H}}{\text{ʒs}\acute{e}} \overset{\hat{H}}{\text{d}\acute{u}\text{k}\acute{o}}$

$H \text{ } HL \text{ } H \text{ } H \text{ } H$

$H \overset{\hat{H}}{HL} \text{ } H \text{ } H$

'father should/must buy a cup'

d) $\overset{\hat{H}}{e_1} \overset{\hat{H}}{\text{ʒiro}_1} \overset{\hat{H}}{ce_1} \overset{\hat{H}}{re_1} \overset{\hat{H}}{\text{ʒka}}$ ----> $[\overset{\hat{H}}{e_1} \overset{\hat{H}}{\text{ʒiro}} \overset{\hat{H}}{\text{cer}\acute{a}\text{k}\acute{a}}$

$H \text{ } L \overset{\hat{H}}{HL} \text{ } H \text{ } H \text{ } HL$

$H \text{ } L \text{ } HL \text{ } H \text{ } H \text{ } L$

'Ejiro must/should cook maize'

Since this construction is in every respect, except for the absence of the auxiliary, identical to the future tense construction, it will be deemed to be a type of future tense in this work (moreso it also expresses action that is expected to commence and be completed at a later date). Consequently, the same processes used to derive the future tense would also account for this construction. The only difference is that although in the underlying representation the auxiliary is present, both of its consonant and the vowel segments get deleted from the string but its low tone survives, and gets obligatorily relinked on the only or final vowel of the subject noun phrase resulting in a HL sequence.

We illustrate with some derivations below.

203. Sample derivation

a) i) Underlying representation

(H - L - H)

C	V	+	C	V	+	C	V	+
m	e ₂		c	a		d	ε	
I			aux			buy		FTM

ii) by segmentalisation of FTM

iii) by deletion of auxiliary

iv) by relinking of (L)

v) **Phonetic Representation**

(b) i) **Underlying representation**

ii) **by segmentalisation of FTM (Vacuous for inherent tone)**

iii) by spreading of second H of FTM

iv) by deletion of auxiliary

v) by (L) relinking

From our discussion so far, it is possible to summarise tonal behaviour in the three tenses considered here in their surface forms. Tonal alternations occur only on the final vowel of the subject noun phrase and on the verb stem. (from which it may affect the prefix vowel of the following noun object)

204 Tonal Alternations in the three tenses.

Tense	Final vowel of Subject NP	Verb stem
Present	LH , H	L
Past	L , H, !H	H
Future	H ... L, HL	H

In the table above, in the present tense, the final vowel of the subject noun phrase may be a LH glide or a H while the verb is L. In the past tense, subject noun phrases retain their tones in the citation form but the verb stem must end with a H. In the future tense, the final vowel of the subject noun phrase must be H and, if there is an auxiliary, the auxiliary is low, but if not, the two tones H and L are realised on the final vowel of the subject noun phrase, hence we have included the tone of the auxiliary with the subject noun phrase, the verb stem in this construction is all high.

6.5 CONCLUSION:

From the behaviour of the tones in the phonetic representation as manifested in the three tenses considered in this chapter, it appears that the sequence of tones in these

constructions is governed by a sort of polarity rule which gives the affixes opposite tone from the verb stem. Thus, when the verb stem is realised on a low tone, the subject pronoun must end on a high tone, as we have in the present tense. Conversely, when the verb stem bears a high tone, the subject pronoun must be realised on the low tone, as we have in the past tense. In the future tense where both the verb stem and the subject pronoun bear the high tone, the future tense auxiliary / ca ~ ce/ mediates between them and is realised on a low tone in order to maintain the polarity.

CHAPTER SEVEN

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

Our aim in this study has been to describe the tone system of Urhobo within the autosegmental model of generative phonology. In order to present our facts systematically, the work was divided into seven chapters.

Chapter One provided a background to the work and introduced the language, its speakers and a few facts about the language that were available in the literature.

In Chapter Two, we discussed, in some detail, in the autosegmental framework on which our study was based.

In Chapter Three, we presented relevant facts about the segmental phonology of the language and we also described and explained vowel harmony and nasality in Urhobo within our chosen theoretical framework.

In Chapter Four, we presented the general tonal phenomena with particular reference to the synchronic aspects of the tone system. We showed that there were only two basic tones, high and low, and, using instrumental evidence, that both downdrift and downstep occurred in the system. We also showed that downstep in Urhobo could not be derived from lost or floating low tones. As a result, we recognised a phonemic downstep feature as part of the tonal make-up of certain nouns and verbal constructions.

Chapters Five and Six dealt with tonal alternations in noun phrases and verbal constructions respectively.

On the whole, this work has presented fresh evidence in support of the preference for the autosegmental model over the linear model of generative phonology in the description of a number of phenomena found in language. It has contributed significantly to linguistic knowledge by being able to resolve a number of controversies surrounding the typology of the Urhobo tone system. In addition, it has been able to show convincingly that the popular view in the literature that downstep is derivable from lost or floating low tones cannot be sustained in all languages.

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FIG 1.

[Ésè dōkà]
H L H L

'Ese bought maize'

MITSUBISHI ELECTRIC

H L H L

H L H L

MITSUBISHI ELECTRIC

FIG 2

[Ésè d̄kàà̄] (Èsè did not buy maize)

H L H L L H H L H L L H

MITSUBISHI ELECTRIC

Fig 3
 [Ésè dókà] (Did Ese buy maize?)
 H L H L

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 'Ese bought maize'

'Did Ese buy maize?'

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FIG 4. [ò dóně] 'he bought yam'
L H H

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'he bought yam'

FIG 5. [éwù rājè] 'a woman's dress'
H L H L

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éwù rājè
H L H L
'a woman's dress'

FIG. 6a and 6b Ghotuo examples
(From Elugbe 1985)

Fig. 2a: F0 curve for /ðsɛ́súlmá/ 'cricket of a foreign land'.

Fig. 2b: F0 curve for /ðsɛ́sómá/ 'a cricket from Oma'.

Fig. 2c: F0 curve for /sólkpá/ 'about a cock'.

Fig. 7

[òbò] 'a hand'
L L

L L

Fig. 8. [òkò] 'a boat, canoe'
L L

A: [19500Hz]

(a) 3:A/Active/Stress

(b) 4:A/Active/Fsmooth

Fig. 9 [òdibò] 'a servant, slave'
L L L

(a) 110/4000Hz

(a) 3: A/Active/Struss

(b) 4: A/Active/Smooth

H H H
[ógógó] 'metal gong'

[òdibò] 'servant, slave'

FIG. 10 [ùsinã] 'the fame, popularity'
 L L L

FIG. 11. [òbò nã dót ò nã] 'the doctor bought the (parcel of) land'
 L L L H !H L

A: [19500Hz]

(a) 3: A/Active/Stress

(b) 4: A/Active/Fsmooth

FIG. 12 [òcé rámě] 'a water pot'
L H H L

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FIG. 13. [òbò rágmá rójè rájè] 'tail-end of a queen's wrapper'
 L L H H H L H L

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FIG. 14 [ɔ̃ dʰkà nǎ] 'he bought the maize'
 L H L L

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FIG 15 [Úré róbò nà v̄j̄n̄] 'the doctor's tree
 H H H L L H !H has honey'

A: [19500Hz]

(a) 3:A/Active/Stress

(b) 4:A/Active/Fsmooth

FIG. 16 [íyō rūçē rōgō rājē nā] 'money for the wood of
 H!H H H H!H H L L the woman's in-law'

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FIG 17 [ó g̃ mē dūrē nã] 'my in-law bought the wood'
 H !H H H H L

A: [19500Hz]

(a) 3: A/Active/Stress

(b) 4: A/Active/Fsmooth

FIG 18 [sɔ̃gɔ̃ nã dɔ̃tɔ̃ rɔ̃pɔ̃ nã] 'the in-law drank the dregs of the honey'
 H !H L H !H H !H L

H !H L H !H H !H L

FIG. 19 [sɔ̃pɔ̃ nã sɔ̃sɛ mɛ̃ vɔ̃tɔ̃ rɔ̃gɔ̃ nã] 'the bee stung my father on the in-law's land'
 H !H L H !H H H !H H !H L

H !H L H !H H H !H H !H L